

Impact of Open Access published research

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In this report we analyze the research impact of outputs forthcoming from FP07 funded research projects with bibliometric techniques, by distinguishing between Open and Closed Access formats. The period of analysis covers 2008-2015/2016. A variety of techniques is applied, focusing on the scientific cooperation patterns of FP-7 funded projects, the disciplinary background of the outputs involved. A particular focus is on the way science and technology are related by focusing on patent citations, and on societal impact by focusing on social media mentions of FP-7 funded research outputs.

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Executive Summary

In this report we present the outcomes of a bibliometric study on the impact of the research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. The outputs of these FP-7 funded research projects, as processed in the OpenAIRE data system are analyzed by the characteristics of openness, distinguishing whether publications were published in Open Access or not. As the formal running time of FP-7 was between 2008 and 2014, we included publications registered in these years, as well as the year 2015 (to include those publications in the pipeline), for the citation impact measurement we extended the period of analysis with one more year (2016).

A first step in the study consisted of analysis of the OpenAIRE data itself, on the aspect of openness. Here we analyzed all publications in the OpenAIRE data system, forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. We clearly observed a changing trend, based upon the distribution of Closed and Open access mode publications output. The observed change relates to the fact that in the later stages of the running period of the FP-7, Closed access mode output numbers are decreasing, while the Open access mode output numbers increase in the final stages, with 2015 still a year which contains relevant outcomes. This might indicate that there is a growing interest of OA publishing for scholars funded by the FP-7.

In our bibliometric study we analyzed a number of characteristics aspects, namely the disciplinary and geographical breakdown of the publications resulting from FP-7 funded research projects. But first some general observations. The impact related to the Open access format output is below the Closed access format published output from FP-7 funded research projects, but still at a very high level (60-80% above worldwide average impact level). The output is published in journals that have an impact that is somewhat below the impact of the journals related to Closed access output, but tends to increase in the later stages of FP-7 as well.

We notice that for some of the relative 'young' EU MS in Eastern Europe the impact of the Open access format output outperforms the Closed access format outputs, both when we look at the field normalized impact, as well as looking at the journal impact scores.

Publications in Open access format, resulting from international cooperation do show an increasing trend, while the impact of these publications is higher as compared to the impact of the single institute and national cooperation output resulting from Closed access format publishing.

With respect to the fields in which the output appeared we notice that among the STM domains, (natural sciences and biomedicine), we find some diversity as it comes to focus on Open access format outputs.

The analysis of the institutions in EU MS and their focus on Open access output, in perspective of the impact related to the Open access formatted output shows that the 'smaller and younger' EU MS have a somewhat stronger focus on Open access, which is then often combined with relatively high impact scores on their Open access format outputs. Yet another remarkable outcome is the apparent stronger focus of institutions revolving round engineering sciences, on Open access formatted output.

A first conclusion from the analysis of patents citing to outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects is the fact that the field normalized impact scores are very high, compared to the overall impact scores of all outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. This is something we

observed in previous studies as well, which might have something to do with the preference by patent examiners for highly prolific scientific outputs (which is underlined by the high impact levels of the journals in which the cited publications appeared).

A first conclusion based on the analysis of Mendeley usage of outputs of FP-7 funded research projects is of course the strong focus of particularly young research staff on the outputs registered in Mendeley. Both in the Open as the Closed realm of outputs forthcoming from FP-7 research projects, the PhD's and Postdoc population together form 50% of the users/readers of these publications. If we add students to this, we find 60% of the usage/readerships stems from young academics.

When observing the social media usage or mentioning of research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects, we notice a very strong presence of Twitter as the main form of social media attention (with tenfold as many Tweets as the next largest source of social media attention, namely Facebook). A general conclusion of the social media analysis is that in general, the research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects that are mentioned do get higher citation scores as compared to the overall impact scores, on both Closed as well as Open access format outputs. So the questions arises what is triggering what, is high impact triggering intensive mentioning in social media, or is intensive mentioning triggering a high impact ? Given the state of affairs in research on social media analysis, this is for now an open question.

1 | INTRODUCTION

In this study we have focused on whether and to what extent research publications from FP-7 funded research projects, and registered as such, in both Closed and Open access format, were cited within either scientific literature, patents, or mentioned in social media. FP-7 has a formal running time between 2008-2014, to include projects initiated late in the formal running time of the programme, we expand the analysis to the years 2008-2015 for this analysis, thereby also including later publications from the FP-7 funding. Since the information on projects in the programme was somewhat 'polluted' (various names for one single project), and the numbers of publications involved on project level is often small, we choose to conduct analyses on the level of the whole programme. The study covers a period of 2008-2015/2016 and is based on linking aggregated metadata from OpenAIRE to the WoS bibliometric database within CWTS, which covers mostly journal literature. As such, the main focus of the study is on the scientific disciplines best covered by the WoS, in which the main standard way of communication is formed by journal literature, including the natural and life sciences, biomedicine, the engineering sciences, and to a smaller extent those social sciences in which journal publishing is also important. Therefore, output numbers in total may differ from those found in the Expert Group Report of FP-7 (Commitment and coherence, November 2015). The analysis is focused on three aspects of measuring impact of registered Open Access (OA) research outputs from FP-7 funded research projects. The first is focusing on the academic research performance, i.e., on academic impact, while the other two elements of the study focus on what is nowadays considered as part of the socio-economic impact, namely the economic impact dimension and the societal impact dimension. The first part is based upon a classical bibliometric approach on the journal publications registered as OA outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects, while the second centers around the interlinkage between science and technology, in the sense that research papers are cited within the content of patents indicates that science is important for technological development. And finally, we focus on the ways social media communication focuses on OA research outputs from FP-7 funded research projects, as that tells us about the way the awareness around science develops and can be interpreted and becomes meaningful from a wider societal perspective.

It should be noted that it is difficult to assess the total number of publications originating from FP7, however in the context of this study the data related to FP7 provided by OpenAIRE was considered only. OpenAIRE data is aggregated from a network of Open Access repositories, archives and journals from Europe and beyond. There are four primary sources of data used for this study: (1) Research output data supplied by OpenAIRE, (2) the CWTS bibliometric database, which is a modified version of the Web of Science (WoS) bibliometric dataset, (3) patent data collected by the CWTS and (3) social media data collected by the CWTS. We have to state here that whenever material did not match with the WoS database (due to either missing data, or non-compatibility due to the scope of the both information sources), these publications were not taken into consideration in the study. No claims on the impact of these publications can be made.

In the next sections of this report we provide a description of the datasets and some general background information about bibliometrics. Next we provide an outline of the methods and indicators used, and then a

discussion of the analysis of scientific collaboration and the basic elements of bibliometric indicators. This is followed by the analysis of FP7 research output, which is divided into three parts: scientific impact, economic impact, and societal impact. Throughout the analysis we will focus on activity indicators, the numbers of publications, or the related numbers to patents and social media data, on impact indicators as indicated by citation impact scores, and positional indicators as expressed by field and cooperation indicators.

2 | OUTPUT DATA

OpenAIRE provided FP7 research output data in the form of publication metadata. OpenAIRE, like other aggregators, rely on the information and metadata quality provided by repositories, other aggregators, publishers and journals. For the OpenAIRE dataset we categorized accessibility of publications by one of five possible states:

1. Open – the resource is declared open because publication full text or dataset files can be accessed openly, free of charge. In case the resource is provided by a journal or publisher or DOAJ data provider it is likely published as Gold-OA. A large amount of repository content is then Green-OA, but e.g. Europe PMC is an example where you can find a lot of Gold-OA articles. Knowing the type of data provider might help to determine if the resource is green or gold.
2. Closed - the resource is declared closed because full text / files are not available from the data provider or not available free of charge.
3. Restricted - the resource is declared restricted because full text files are available only on campus / member of an institution or on request.
4. Embargoed - the resource is declared embargoed and an embargo end date must be provided in the metadata. After the embargo period the resource can be accessed openly.
5. Unknown - neither information was provided in the metadata about the access mode nor it can be concluded from the data provider information.

2.1 Data used in the study

2.1.1 Bibliometric data

CWTS has a license to the WoS database, to be used for commercial purposes, on top of the usage of the database for academic purposes. This version of WoS is commonly referred to as the CWTS in-house bibliometric data-system. The system covers the period 1981-current, for this study we will use the period 2008-2015 for publications, and add 2016 as an additional year for citation impact measurement. Another source of data used in this study comes from the OpenAIRE platform. From OpenAIRE, we received an updated set of publications (delivery 4th April 2017) registered by researchers funded under the EU 7th Framework Program (from here on FP-7).

The publication data collected in this study are publication years: papers are included for the year in which they were published in the journal, which does not necessarily coincide with the moment the publications are processed for the WoS.

We considered only papers classified in the WoS as normal articles, letters and reviews, published in source serials processed for the WoS database. Please note that in the indicator set of CWTS (see below), letters are weighted with 0.25. Other document types, such as meeting abstracts, 'editorials', 'editorial material', corrections, comments, and book reviews were not included. Also, papers in non-WoS source journals are not counted. A few journals are only partially processed for the WoS. Here, only papers processed for the WoS were included.

A statement needs to be made on a specific type of articles in the WoS database. This concerns the articles published in journals, but forthcoming from a scientific conference. These regular journal articles were in 2008 reclassified as proceedings papers, but after a short while, realizing this was an error, this was changed again in to article/proceeding paper. For this study, this does not influence the results, as we still consider these publications as regular journal articles, and they are treated as such.¹

CWTS has a license on the WoS database from Thomson Reuters, allowing us to conduct bibliometric analyses, under strict regulations. One of these regulations is that we are not allowed to publish material derived directly from the WoS database. As such, aggregated statistics generated from this project can be made public.

CWTS applied its longstanding experience in linking the input set to the WoS database. The most obvious step to take was using the doi that was available in the input set from the OpenAIRE platform. However, in an additional next step we also applied the more elaborate linking by using publication meta data, such as title of the source, title of the publication, author names, publication year, volume number, and page numbers.

2.1.2 Social Media data

Two datasets on social media analysis were used (1) *Mendeley*, which tells us about readership, and (2) *Altmetric.com* data, which informs us about various social media (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, news, and blogs, to name a few). Both sets, for Mendeley information as well as for Altmetrics.com information are stored in in-house sql datasets within CWTS. Direct links between these sets and the WoS database are made using doi's of the publications, which means that everything item without a doi was not included in the analysis.

¹ In the future, when the CWTS WoS database also contains proceedings publications, a new situation arises, and adequate steps will be taken to handle these new document types correctly (for a report of this issue see Gonzalez-Albo & Bordons, 2011)

2.1.3 Patent data

The Spring 2015 Version of the EPO Worldwide Patent Statistical Database (PATSTAT) was used to support the economic impact analysis. Twice a year a snapshot of the EPO master documentation database is taken to produce a new version of the PATSTAT-databases. This spring 2015 version of PATSTAT contains bibliographic data for over 81 million patent applications from more than 80 regional or national patent offices. For all patent publications the database contains information on: Patent applicants — names, addresses; Inventors — names, addresses; Various dates — date of application, of publication, of grant, and lapse; Area of technology — based on the fine grained patent classification systems; Citation links to other patents; Citation links to so called non-patent literature references (NPLRs), e.g. scholarly publications; The origin of a citation link — applicant, employee of a patent office, third party; and Title and abstract of an invention.

3 | LIMITATIONS OF THIS STUDY

In this section we will discuss some of the limitations of the current study. These relate to the underlying dataset, to the way publications are processed in the OpenAIRE system, and what this might mean for bibliometric analysis, the context in which this study is taking place, and finally the definition of Open Access operationalized in the study.

3.1 Completeness of the FP-7 set

The question on the completeness and representativeness of the OpenAIRE dataset in comparison with WoS. First, it seems appropriate to state that WoS is a subscription based bibliographic database, with light research metrics attached to it, mainly consisting of internationally oriented, mostly English language journals. With respect to the coverage, particularly regarding social sciences, law and the humanities, coverage can be called moderate to poor. On the other end, OpenAIRE harvests from repositories, hence many other types of documents are included, not only strictly academic, but also other types of scientific communication, such as grey literature. It is unclear what portion the OA publications are of total FP-7 output. Therefore, we have analyzed the publications in the CWTS/WoS database, that carry in their Funding Acknowledgments (FA) a reference to the FP-7 instruments (keep in mind that OpenAIRE might also include publications with a funding acknowledgement, but lacking a DOI). The OpenAIRE dataset carried in total 83.809 unique publications in WoS in the period 2008-2016. This set was compared with a set of 44.216 publications in WoS with a FA referring to FP-7 in some sense. The overlap was 27.573 publications. This implies that we have much more in the OpenAIRE dataset as compared to identifiable to FP-7 related output in WoS (in total 56.236 publications). However, it also means we do not have 16.643 publications that are identifiable in WoS as related to FP-7 which are not in OpenAIRE. At present, we are unable to establish an overview of the total output from FP-7 so that we can somehow benchmark our findings with the datasets used in this the study.

3.2 Duplicate doi's

We have discarded all publications that we found that carry a duplicate doi. Due to matching via the doi, publications outside the range of journals processed for the WoS are seen as potential candidates for inclusion in the analysis. Although these publications do not get an internal WoS UT-code attributed, they still might distort analyses. As hypothetically, when citation linking is based on doi's, citation impact measures might be influenced by these double attributions of publications to one single doi. It goes beyond the range of this current study, to further investigate whether this influences our analyses, and to what extent, therefore, we have removed publications that have two distinct instances for the same title.

3.3 Matthew Effect Hypothesis

That we are measuring the impact of OA publication from FP-7 funded projects is complicated by the so-called 'Matthew effect. Is higher impact an effect of OA or that it is an FP-7 funded project (i.e. the Matthew effect)? This biblical reference, originally coined by RK Merton, says that the rich get richer, and the poor get poorer. How does that relate to our analysis? Previous studies (Noyons et al, 2009, Lepori et al, 2015) have shown that success in getting EU-funding has a repetitive effect, once you have been in, you can win a second attempt more easily. Given this situation, where the Matthew Effect becomes visible in the grant winning level, one can also see that these researchers have an advantageous situation when it comes to publishing, and the impact their work generates. That is why we call this a double Matthew Effect. To address in future studies, it would be prudent to compare FP7/OA with either FP7/non-OA or FP7 as a whole.

3.4 Confounding factors, Green OA

Prior research on Green OA shows that high citation impact can be explained by numerous confounding factors. This complicates any claim of attributing higher impact from FP7/OA publications, as it is not possible to separate the effects of Green OA from the effects of FP7/OA. According to Archambault, et al (2014), "There is a huge citation advantage to publishing in Green OA, as has been demonstrated time and again in other serious studies conducted previously" (p20). The authors explain that the Green OA citation advantage varies across fields. Nevertheless, they show a general ranking of OA citation impact, from high to low: "Green OA, Other OA, Not OA, and Gold OA" (p24). The following factors can each explain higher citation advantage associated with Green OA: self-selection bias (Kurtz M. et al. 2005), availability at multiple access points (Xia et. al 2010), physical proximity of researchers—related to collaborative research (Lee et al. 2010), and early exposure to draft versions (Moed 2007). Most (if not all) of these factors appear to be relevant to the FP7/OA dataset. As such, in future analyses, it would be important to identify the precise types of OA in the OpenAIRE dataset (green, gold, hybrid, etc.).

4 BACKGROUND, BIBLIOMETRICS

Bibliometrics is the quantitative study of written products of research. It is assumed that scientific subjects develop at an international research front (Price, 1963). Research results are communicated in publications that are submitted to evaluation by professional colleagues. In the references of their papers, scientists acknowledge relevant publications by others, as they build on previous work, thereby indicating a certain degree of influence of others on their own work. Therefore, the number of times a publication is referred to gives a partial indication of the 'impact' of a publication, its reception and use by scientists at the research front.

In many scientific fields, the scientific journal is by far the most important medium of communication. The Web of Science database (from here on WoS), which consists of the citation indexes known under acronyms such as SCI, SSCI and A&HCI claims to cover the most important 'leading' international journals and serials (such as Annual Reviews) with a well-functioning referee system. In addition, the overall citation rate of journals is considered, as well as their timeliness of publication, and adherence to international editorial conventions. Regularly, a limited number of new journals are added, while other journals are no longer covered. More 'peripheral' journals, often national in scope, are usually not covered by the WoS. The WoS database counts about 11,000 journals during the last decade.

Both statistical requirements and imperfections in the citation process (for a discussion see Nederhof, 1988) make it desirable to aggregate across individuals, publications, and citations. As scientific (sub)fields differ in publication and citation patterns (as visible in differences in for example length of reference lists, or age of cited literature), it is usually not meaningful to compare directly the raw impact of publications from one (sub)field with those of a different (sub)field. Therefore, in our studies raw impact scores are compared to the impact of similar publications within the same (sub)field.

5 METHODOLOGY AND INDICATORS

For this study we calculated the following indicators (numbering of the indicators corresponds to the position these indicators have in the data tables).

A first statistic gives the total number of papers published by the research unit during the entire period (p). We considered only papers classified as normal articles, letters, and reviews. Meeting abstracts, corrections, and editorials are not included. In a few cases, a paper is published in a journal for which no citation data are available, or that is not assigned to a journal subject category. These papers are not considered in the calculation of the indicators presented in the tables below.

The next indicator gives the total number of citations received, without self-citations (tcs). A self-citation (sc) to a paper is a citation given in a publication of which at least one author (either first author or co-author) is also an author of the cited paper (either first author or co-author). A next indicator is the average number of citations per publication calculated while self-citations are not included (mcs).

International reference values: fcs and jcs

In the creation of the CWTS bibliometric system, two international reference values are computed. A first value represents the expected mean citation rate of the subfields (journal categories) in which the research unit is active (fmcs, the Field Mean Citation Score). Our definition of subfields is based on a classification of scientific journals into categories developed by Thomson Reuters. Although this classification is certainly not perfect, it is at present the only classification available in the WoS. In calculating fmcs, we apply the following procedure. The fmcs takes into account both the type of paper (e.g., normal article, review, and so on), as well as the specific years in which the research unit's papers were published. For example, the number of citations received during the period 2005 - 2012 by a letter published by a research unit in 2005 in field X is compared to the average number of citations received during the same period (2005 - 2012) by all letters published in the same field (X) in the same year (2005). Self-citations are excluded from the computation of fmcs.

In most cases, a research unit is active in more than one subfield (i.e., journal category). In those cases, we apply various field impact scores, as related to the individual publications, the selection of the fields being determined by the journals the research unit has used to publish its' research findings. When a journal is classified in multiple subfields, as happens frequently in the WoS, citation scores are computed as follows. Basically, a paper in a journal classified in N subfields is counted as 1/N paper in each subfield, and so are its fmcs scores, so this creates per individual publication an expected mean field citation score.

The second reference value presents the expected mean citation rate of the journals in which the research unit has published (jmcs, the Journal Mean Citation Score). We apply the same exact method for calculating jmcs as we did for fmcs.

6 MAIN INDICATORS

The most important indicators compare the number of citations per individual publication within the oeuvre of a research unit (C) to the two international reference values, namely the corresponding field and journal expected citation scores of individual publications (jmcs and fmcs, respectively), by calculating the ratio for every single publication against both expected citation scores. Self-citations are excluded in the calculation of the ratios $c/fmcs$ and $c/jmcs$, to prevent that citation scores are affected by divergent self-citation behavior. Over all ratios of individual publications, we calculate a mean impact score, for both the fields as well as the journals in which the institute has published.

The overall field normalized impact indicator for an institute output is mnsc, the mean normalized citation score (Waltman et al, 2011a and Waltman et al, 2011b). As this indicator focuses on the broader environment of the group's output, this indicator seems the most suitable indicator of the international position of a research unit. If the mnsc is above (below) 1.0, this means that the output of the research unit is cited more (less) frequently than an 'average' publication in the subfield(s) in which the research unit is active. The fmcs values of the individual publications constitute a world subfield average in a specific (combination of) subfield(s). In this way, one may obtain an indication of the international position of a research unit, in terms of its impact compared to a 'world' average. This 'world' average is calculated for the total population of articles published in WoS journals assigned to a particular subfield or journal category. As a rule, about 70-80 percent of these papers are authored by scientists from the United States, Canada, Western Europe, Australia and Japan. Therefore, this 'world' average is dominated by the Western world.

A second important indicator, mnjs, is above (below) 1.0 if the citation score of the journal set in which the research unit has published exceeds the citation score of all papers published in the subfield(s) to which the journals belong. In this case, one can conclude that the research unit publishes in journals with a relatively high (low) impact. It should be noted that the mnsc and mnjs indicators are not independent. The value of each one of these follows directly from the values of the other indicator.

In addition to the mnsc indicator, we use another important impact indicator. This is the proportion of publications belonging to the top 10% most highly cited publications segment, denoted by pp(top 10%). For each publication of a research group, we determine whether it belongs to the top 10% based on its number of citations of all WoS publications in the same field (i.e., the same WoS subject category) and from the same publication year. The pp(top 10%) indicator of a research entity equals the proportion of its publications belonging to this top 10%. As for mcs and mnsc indicators, letters are given less weight than articles and reviews in the calculation of the pp(top 10%) indicator. If a research group has a pp(top 10%) indicator of 10%, it means that the actual number of top 10% publications of the group equals the expected number. A pp(top 10%) indicator of, for instance, 20% means

that a group has twice as many top 10% publications as expected. Of course, the choice to focus on top 10% publications is somewhat arbitrary. In the main tables, we use the $pp(\text{top } 10\%)$ indicator, as this indicator has a clear focus on high impact publications, and the top 10% is used more often in bibliometric analyses (“first percentile”).

Another indicator is the percentage of articles not cited during the time period considered (pp_{uncited}), excluding self-citations. As an indication of the self-citation rate we present the percentage of self-citations (prop-self-cits), relative to the total number of citations received ($sc/(C+sc)$).

Finally, we present the so-called coverage indicator. This percentage indicates the degree to which a unit refers themselves to the literature covered in the WoS. The reference behavior of a unit thus indicates whether the journal literature is important for the scholarly communication for that unit, and as such can be interpreted as indicator of the applicability of bibliometrics in an assessment context. Having a high percentage of references covered indicates that WoS database supported bibliometrics function fine as supporting instruments of research assessment, and on the other hand, lower percentages indicate that WoS based metrics do only partially contribute to an understanding of the research performance of a unit (van Leeuwen, 2013).

7 ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC COLLABORATION

The analysis of the various types of scientific cooperation is based upon a typology of papers, which is based on the addresses attached to the publications. In case of the paper carrying only one address, the publication is automatically labeled as a single institute publication. In case of the appearance of at least two country names on one publication, the publication is automatically considered an international cooperation. The remaining set of publications, carrying two or more addresses within one country, the publication is considered to be the result of national cooperation.

Any classification such as this one has drawbacks, in this case the typology applied has the disadvantage that in the case of international cooperation publications, if a paper also carries two addresses from one country, the international dimension is the dominant factor in labeling that publication. Furthermore, in case of publications labeled as national cooperation, it can happen that these are actually two addresses of one and the same main institution, which makes it an intra-mural cooperation. However, the typology has been designed as such that mutually exclusive classes are created, thereby mainly focusing on the international vs national dimension.

8 BASIC ELEMENTS OF BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

All above discussed indicators are important in a bibliometric analysis as they relate to different aspects of publication and citation characteristics. Generally, we consider mncs as an important indicator for analyzing research performance. This indicator relates the measured impact of a research unit, be it a group, institute, or even a whole country to a worldwide, field-specific reference value. Therefore, it is a powerful internationally standardized impact indicator. This indicator enables us to observe immediately whether the performance of a research institute/group or institute is significantly far below (indicator value < 0.5), below (indicator value $0.5 - 0.8$), about ($0.8 - 1.2$), above ($1.2 - 2.0$), or far above (>2.0) the international (western world dominated) impact standard of the field. The higher the aggregation level, the larger the volume in publications and the more difficult it is to have an average impact significantly above the international level. At the 'meso-level' (e.g., a large institute, or faculty, about 500 – 1,000 publications per year), a mncs value above 1.2, such as in this case, means that the institute's impact as a whole is significantly above (western-) world average. The institute can be considered as a scientifically strong organization, with a high probability to find very good to excellent groups. Therefore, it is important to split up large institutes into smaller groups. Only this allows a more precise assessment of research performance. Otherwise, excellent work will be 'hidden' within the bulk of a large institute or faculty. We stress that the other indicators provided in the tables, such as pp_uncited or pp_self_cits do contribute to a further understanding of the research performance analysis of units under study. Together these indicators tend to inform the user of bibliometrics on a variety of aspects in research performance analysis.

OVERVIEW OF BIBLIOMETRIC INDICATORS

p	Number of papers (normal articles, letters, and reviews) published in journals processed for the Web of Science (WoS).
tcs	Number of citations recorded in WoS journals to all papers involved. Self-citations are excluded.
mcs	Average number of citations per publication, or citation per publication ratio. Self-citations are excluded.
jmcs	Average citation rate of all articles published in the journals in which an institute/group has published (excluding self-citations) (not printed in the data-tables).
fmcs	Average citation rate of all articles in the fields in which the institute/group is active. Also indicated as the world citation average in those fields. Fields are defined by means of WoS journal subject categories (excluding self-citations) (not printed in the data-tables).
mnscs	The impact of a research unit's articles, compared to the world citation average in the subfields in which the research unit is active.
mnjs	The impact of the journals in which a research unit has published (the research unit's journal selection), compared to the world citation average in the subfields covered by these journals.
pp_uncited	Percentage of articles not cited during the time period considered.
pp_self_cits	Percentage of self-citations. A self-citation is defined as a citation in which the citing and the cited paper have at least one author in common (first author or co-author).
pp_top10%	The share of the number of papers that are among the 10% most frequently cited of all similar papers in the period 2008-2015/2016.
int_cov	This indicates the degree to which a unit refers themselves to the literature covered in the WoS. The reference behavior of a unit thus indicates whether the journal literature is important for the scholarly communication in a field, and as such can be interpreted as indicator of the applicability of bibliometrics in an assessment context.

9 RESULTS OF ACADEMIC IMPACT OF FP7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS

In this section we will focus on a number of aspects. First we will describe the context against which to interpret the results of the study on the impact of open access outputs from FP-7 funded projects. After this descriptive part, we will focus on the evaluative elements in the analysis of FP-7 funded projects outputs. Here we will focus on a number of aspects:

- Overall impacts of the various access modes.
- Impact scores for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.
- Coverage issues related to funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.
- Country analysis of funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.
- Country/institutional analysis of funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.
- Field specific analysis of funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.

9.1 Description of the basic outcomes

The input dataset from the OpenAIRE platform (delivered to CWTS on 4th April 2017) contained in total 173.116 publications, consisting of basic bibliographic information, metadata on the publications, as well as a number of important aspects/variables attached to it, namely the access mode as registered in OpenAIRE, the project that registered the publication as forthcoming from an EU funded project under the 7th Framework Programme, and as registered in OpenAIRE, the funding agency as registered in OpenAIRE, and the registered publication type in OpenAIRE. From this set of publications, we managed to link 83.875 publications to the CWTS in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS). Of the remaining set, 78.076 publications were unique within WoS, with 4.799 publications appearing more than once in the database. This is mainly due to the fact that publications are registered under two or more EU funded projects, and/or related to more than one funding agency.

If we take a look at the registered outputs to FP-7 funded research projects, we find the following timeline on the outputs. This is displayed in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 OVERVIEW OF FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS IN TIME.

As FP-7 started formally in 2008, we are confronted with a phenomenon we observe more often while conducting bibliometric analysis, namely the fact that researchers register more outputs to a funding source than they actually should. This becomes most clearly visible when registering outputs to a funding body from beyond the starting point of the funding. In this study, we will ignore outputs registered before 2008.

From that initial identification of publication outputs related to FP-7 funded research projects, we switch to access modes indicated to FP-7 registered outputs as incorporated in the OpenAIRE platform. Again, we only focus on outputs registered from 2008 onwards. We distinguish five types of access modes, Closed, Open, Embargo, Restricted, and Unknown. The numbers are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF VARIOUS ACCESS MODES RELATED TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

Access mode	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
CLOSED	320	1809	5395	10308	15181	20578	8622	230
EMBARGO			1	4	23	25	68	59
OPEN	58	455	1128	2345	4009	5846	5514	2080
RESTRICTED	8	19	50	83	83	65	93	63
UNKNOWN			1		5	5	12	29

As becomes immediately apparent from the table, the two most important access modes for the analysis are Closed and Open access types. The other three types are relatively small, and thus less important for the understanding of changing cultures in publication practices in Europe, when it comes to open science. The data in Table 1 are graphically displayed in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 OVERVIEW OF ACCESS MODES TO FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS IN TIME.

Figure 2 points us at an interesting phenomenon, namely the fact that when the number of publications published under the Closed access mode is starting to decrease from 2013 to 2015, the number of publications published under the Open access mode shows a stabilization, and ends up slightly higher in terms of the output in 2015 as compared to the Closed access mode publications. The figure also clearly demonstrates the relative unimportance of the other three modes of access in the study.

A next element in the descriptive part of the study, using OpenAIRE based outputs in relation to WoS retrieved outputs relates to the document types indicated. While WoS has a variety of document types that is clearly described for the most occurring document types (articles), some other types are rather ambiguous, such as letters and reviews (Van Leeuwen et al, 2007; Harzing, 2013) or are in terms of a bibliometric analysis less relevant (such as corrections, editorials, meeting abstracts, etc., van Leeuwen et al, 2013.). Below we will give an overview of the variety of document types in both databases, and the way these are connected in the comparison of the two sets. Please note that the numbers are here for all publications with an internal WoS tag, which means that multiple

assignments per publication are possible. This is done as perhaps publications registered to OpenAIRE from various projects might have different document type codes, and de-duplication would distort the overall picture, ending up somewhere between the total number of publications before de-duplication, and the total de-duplicated number of publications in the study.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE CONCORDANCE OF DOCUMENT TYPES IN OPENAIRE AND WOS RELATED TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

WoS
Classificatio

OpenAIRE classification	Article	Review	Editorial Material	Letter	Correction	Meeting Abstract	News Item	Reprint	Hardware Review	Software Review
Article	78466	1654	281	88	44	19	10	3	2	1
Review	2	3755	5		2		1			
Unknown/Other	301	13	9		1	2				

Table 2 clearly illustrates that for the bulk of publications, the document type assignments in both systems are similar, e.g. for articles are 93% of all publications labels as such in both systems, and for reviews we find that in total 4% of all publications are labeled as reviews in both systems. This means that at least 97% of all publications in the study are labeled in the exact same way in both data sources.

A next descriptive step relates to the scientific production in terms of scientific cooperation. We distinguish three types of scientific activity related to scientific collaboration, namely single authored/address output, output resulting from national, and international scientific cooperation. These three types are determined in a quite straightforward way, as indicated previously. Given the limited amount of publications found under three types of access modes, we only present the Open and Closed access modes in the table and graph. The results are displayed in Table 3, and Figure 3. The full data are shown in Appendix 2.

TABLE 3: NUMBERS OF PUBLICATIONS UNDER VARIOUS TYPES OF SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION AND ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

Access mode	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
CLOSED/1=SI	110	544	1458	2673	3740	4973	2077	44
CLOSED/2=NC	54	334	1023	1899	2874	3874	1589	61
CLOSED/3=IC	156	931	2914	5736	8567	11731	4956	125
OPEN/1=SI	16	123	236	442	767	1093	1107	417
OPEN/2=NC	11	75	190	376	708	1049	986	399
OPEN/3=IC	31	257	702	1527	2534	3704	3421	1264

In Table 3 we can clearly observe that open access publishing takes off later in comparison with closed access format outputs from FP7-funded research projects, similar to the overall pattern distinguished in Figure 2. However, the number of open access publications resulting from international cooperation is increasing rapidly, and as Figure 3 clearly shows, this type of publishing is keeping the same pace as the closed format publishing under single address and national cooperation, finally ending up with a higher number of publications in 2015 as compared to the international closed format output. A first conclusion could be that international scientific cooperation is at least more beneficial for open access publishing, as the international open access mode output is very much different compared to the other two types of cooperation and the open access mode output related to these two types.

FIGURE 3 OVERVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION AND ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015.

A next shift would be to have a look at the number of countries attached to the types of access modes that is a further zooming in into the international cooperation dimension.

In Table 4a, we present the relative shares of publications per number of countries attached to the publications resulting from FP-7 funded research projects under the Closed access mode (with relative shares expressed over the column/numbers of authors, and the absolute numbers available in the appendix). As was to be expected, the relative shares show a very stable pattern, with papers with one, two, or three country names attached to it covering some 80% of the output within the Closed access formatted output .

TABLE 4A: RELATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF OUTPUT OVER COUNTRIES, CLOSED ACCESS MODE, IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

n_countries	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	51%	48%	46%	44%	44%	43%	43%	46%
2	30%	32%	33%	33%	32%	32%	32%	30%
3	12%	12%	13%	13%	14%	14%	14%	10%
4	3%	4%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	4%
5	2%	1%	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%	3%
6	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%
7	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	3%
8	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%
9	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%
10	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
11-20	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	0%
>21	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

TABLE 4B: RELATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF OUTPUT OVER COUNTRIES, OPEN ACCESS MODE, IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

n_countries	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	47%	44%	38%	35%	37%	37%	38%	39%
2	31%	32%	33%	35%	33%	33%	31%	32%
3	17%	15%	16%	17%	16%	16%	16%	16%
4	0%	5%	7%	6%	7%	7%	7%	7%
5	5%	2%	2%	3%	3%	3%	3%	2%
6	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%	1%
7	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
8	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
9	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%
10	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
11-20	0%	1%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
>21	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 4b shows the relative share per number of countries attached to FP-7 funded research outputs per year, under the Open access mode. Again, we find the output by one, two, or three countries together as most prominent, however we also notice a shift when it comes to multi country output, as in the period of analysis, the relative share

of output with four or five countries attached is increasing, while the share of single country publications decreases. Compared to the Closed access mode, these peaks are somewhat later in time. Another remarkable outcome is the large share in 2015 in the Open access mode, as compared to the Closed access mode. This indicates that the Open access mode is really taking off under the FP-7 funded research projects in the later stages of the FP-7 timeframe.

TABLE 5A: RELATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF OUTPUT OVER AUTHORS, CLOSED ACCESS MODE, IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

n_authors	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	4%	3%	3%	3%	3%	2%	2%	1%
2	13%	13%	12%	11%	11%	11%	10%	6%
3	21%	17%	17%	16%	16%	16%	15%	13%
4	16%	16%	15%	16%	15%	16%	15%	17%
5	12%	12%	12%	12%	12%	13%	13%	15%
6	8%	9%	9%	10%	10%	9%	10%	10%
7	4%	7%	8%	7%	8%	7%	8%	7%
8	6%	5%	5%	6%	6%	6%	6%	5%
9	3%	4%	4%	4%	5%	4%	4%	7%
10	2%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%	4%
11	3%	2%	2%	3%	3%	2%	2%	1%
12	2%	1%	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%
13	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	0%
14	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
15	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%
16	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
17	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	0%
18	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%
19	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
20	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
>21	1%	2%	2%	2%	3%	3%	3%	6%

In Table 5a, we present a similar analysis as presented in Tables 4a, now focused on authors rather than countries. We observe that most publications are produced by two to five authors, while increasingly multi-authored publications tend to become more important. Table 5b shows the same results, now for the Open access mode.

PUBLIC

Here we find a more spread distribution of the shares with increasingly, towards the end of the period of analysis, multi-authored publications becoming more prominent, with papers up to 8-9 authors not being unique.

TABLE 5B: RELATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF OUTPUT OVER AUTHORS, OPEN ACCESS MODE, IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015

n_authors	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	3%	5%	4%	3%	3%	2%	3%	3%
2	17%	16%	14%	11%	12%	11%	9%	10%
3	19%	21%	18%	17%	16%	15%	14%	14%
4	19%	17%	17%	16%	16%	15%	14%	13%
5	10%	11%	11%	11%	11%	11%	12%	11%
6	7%	7%	8%	9%	8%	9%	9%	9%
7	7%	6%	5%	6%	7%	8%	7%	8%
8	0%	5%	4%	5%	6%	6%	6%	6%
9	2%	2%	4%	4%	4%	4%	5%	5%
10	0%	2%	3%	3%	4%	4%	4%	4%
11	5%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%
12	2%	1%	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%	3%
13	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%	2%
14	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%
15	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%
16	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	1%	1%	1%
17	0%	0%	1%	1%	0%	1%	1%	1%
18	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	1%
19	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
20	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
>21	5%	2%	3%	3%	3%	3%	4%	4%

From the descriptive analysis of the material in the study, we can draw already one important conclusion, based upon the distribution of Closed and Open access mode publications output. This conclusion relates to the fact that Open access mode outputs increase in the later stages of the running period of the FP-7, in which Closed access mode output is decreasing, while the Open access mode increase in the final stages, with 2015 still a year which contains relevant outcomes. This conclusion is supported by a break-down in various aspects of the data material. These outcomes support the general, overall outcomes so far.

9.2 Results: overall output and impact trends 2008-2015/2016

In this section we will focus on the output and impact scores of the various modes of openness in scientific publishing for the outputs of the FP-7 funded research projects. For the sake of completeness, we will show in the first two tables 6 and 7 the five types of access modes. From there on we will further focus on only Closed and Open access mode outputs. This is due to the small numbers involved, which make little sense when we move into further detailed analyses in the next paragraphs.

TABLE 6: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	61478,50	1140167,00	18,55	1,91	1,59	22%	7%	23%	85%
EMBARGO	178,25	1543,00	8,66	1,76	1,55	22%	13%	28%	85%
OPEN	21175,75	301987,75	14,26	1,78	1,38	20%	8%	25%	88%
RESTRICTED	454,25	5758,50	12,68	1,52	1,34	17%	15%	26%	75%
UNKNOWN	52,00	245,00	4,71	1,49	1,43	17%	10%	41%	82%

In Table 6 we present the results on five types of access modes. All types of access modes related to outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects display high impact scores, in particular for Closed and Open access modes of publishing. The publications resulting from FP-7 funded research projects were published in high impact journals, which mean that the Open access mode publications in the study appear in high impact journals.

When we look at the results presented in Table 7, we notice that output numbers for the Closed and Open access mode outputs is increasing rapidly within the period 2008-2011 to 2012-2015. This trend is graphically shown in Figure 4. In line with the output increase, we notice an increase of the average impact for these two types of access modes. Shifting our attention to the impact, we notice that the Closed and Open access mode outputs do have the highest impact scores, with mncs scores varying between 1.8-1.9 for Closed and 1.6-1.7 for Open, respectively. Furthermore, the impact of the journals of choice was high, and remains high (some 60% above worldwide average impact level for Closed, and 30-40% for Open access mode outputs).

TABLE 7: TRENDS IN OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED									
2008 - 2011	17548,50	121443,25	6,92	1,83	1,61	20%	21%	27%	85%
2009 - 2012	32200,50	270200,50	8,39	1,84	1,59	21%	18%	27%	86%
2010 - 2013	50682,00	476487,75	9,40	1,85	1,59	21%	16%	26%	85%
2011 - 2014	53859,00	650114,75	12,07	1,95	1,59	22%	11%	25%	85%
2012 - 2015	43930,00	677457,50	15,42	1,93	1,59	22%	8%	24%	85%
EMBARGO									
2008 - 2011	5,00	17,00	3,40	1,27	1,19	20%	20%	45%	86%
2009 - 2012	27,25	116,50	4,28	1,45	1,33	22%	18%	34%	89%
2010 - 2013	52,25	352,75	6,75	1,89	1,41	30%	17%	31%	87%
2011 - 2014	119,25	779,50	6,54	1,57	1,40	20%	19%	29%	85%
2012 - 2015	173,25	1451,00	8,38	1,76	1,56	21%	14%	27%	85%
OPEN									
2008 - 2011	3951,25	26646,50	6,74	1,66	1,37	19%	19%	28%	87%
2009 - 2012	7870,50	60838,50	7,73	1,67	1,34	19%	17%	27%	88%
2010 - 2013	13200,75	108763,25	8,24	1,65	1,32	19%	16%	27%	88%
2011 - 2014	17518,50	166189,50	9,49	1,69	1,36	19%	13%	27%	88%
2012 - 2015	17224,50	208752,00	12,12	1,79	1,38	20%	9%	26%	88%
RESTRICTED									
2008 - 2011	154,00	901,00	5,85	1,44	1,42	16%	29%	33%	75%
2009 - 2012	228,00	1675,00	7,35	1,80	1,43	21%	21%	31%	74%
2010 - 2013	276,00	2469,00	8,95	1,74	1,36	22%	20%	29%	74%
2011 - 2014	316,25	2316,25	7,32	1,41	1,26	16%	23%	29%	74%
2012 - 2015	300,25	2451,50	8,16	1,46	1,30	15%	19%	27%	74%
UNKNOWN									
2008 - 2011	1,00	2,00	2,00	0,84	1,20	0%	0%	71%	78%
2009 - 2012	6,00	7,00	1,17	0,50	1,17	1%	50%	61%	76%
2010 - 2013	11,00	26,00	2,36	1,21	1,16	7%	18%	41%	77%
2011 - 2014	22,00	53,00	2,41	1,09	1,11	9%	14%	37%	72%
2012 - 2015	51,00	226,00	4,43	1,47	1,43	16%	10%	41%	82%

In the Figures below, the trend scores presented in Table 7 are graphically displayed. The output presented in Figure 4 is discussed above. Figure 5 shows the increase of absolute citation impact, which shows an even sharper

increase as compared to the output (which explains for the increase of average impact scores for Closed and Open access mode research outputs).

FIGURE 4 OVERVIEW OF TRENDS IN OUTPUT NUMBERS ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 5 OVERVIEW OF TRENDS IN ABSOLUTE CITATION NUMBERS ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

Figure 6, 7, and 8 show information on the impact development of FP-7 funded research outputs. In Figure 6, the development of mncs values is displayed. Only Closed and Open access modes show stable patterns, which is due to the smaller numbers of publications involved in the other three types. The mnjs values of the five types of output, as displayed in Figure 7, show more stability, due to the fact that there are even more publications underlying this analysis. Closed access mode output from FP-7 research projects is published in the highest impact journals.

FIGURE 6 OVERVIEW OF TRENDS IN MEAN NORMALIZED CITATION SCORES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 7 OVERVIEW OF TRENDS IN MEAN NORMALIZED JOURNAL CITATION SCORES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 8 OVERVIEW OF SHARES OF TOP 10% HIGHLY CITED PUBLICATIONS ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

In Figure 8, the presence in the top 10% of the fields in which the output is published is shown. Again, we observe the more stable patterns for Closed and Open access mode outputs.

Following this general perspective, we now switch to the level of the national contributions to the outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects . This perspective of course contains a wide variety of countries, EU member States and their international partners. In Table 8, we show the output and impact scores for the EU Member States only.

TABLE 8: OUTPUT AND IMPACT ACROSS COUNTRIES OF VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AUSTRIA	CLOSED	2393,50	54452,00	22,75	2,30	1,78	26%	6%	28%	84%
	OPEN	1033,50	17107,25	16,55	2,08	1,61	26%	7%	28%	86%
BELGIUM	CLOSED	4175,25	87359,00	20,92	2,03	1,63	23%	6%	26%	86%
	OPEN	1058,50	14931,75	14,11	1,76	1,44	22%	6%	32%	87%
BULGARIA	CLOSED	230,00	3559,00	15,47	1,63	1,28	16%	9%	33%	81%
	OPEN	57,00	552,00	9,68	1,63	1,10	20%	11%	30%	81%

PUBLIC

CYPRUS	CLOSED	193,00	2228,00	11,54	1,48	1,39	17%	5%	25%	74%
	OPEN	75,00	807,00	10,76	1,41	1,26	19%	8%	35%	85%
CZECH REPUBLIC	CLOSED	1219,00	19272,00	15,81	1,63	1,51	18%	7%	29%	86%
	OPEN	434,25	6016,50	13,85	1,75	1,48	20%	9%	31%	87%
DENMARK	CLOSED	2546,75	63710,25	25,02	2,34	1,79	25%	5%	28%	87%
	OPEN	920,00	16501,00	17,94	2,15	1,51	26%	6%	30%	87%
ESTONIA	CLOSED	318,25	10699,25	33,62	2,72	1,93	35%	5%	30%	85%
	OPEN	154,00	4445,00	28,86	2,91	1,56	36%	7%	30%	87%
FINLAND	CLOSED	2166,75	47054,25	21,72	2,00	1,61	22%	7%	29%	86%
	OPEN	821,00	14260,00	17,37	1,96	1,39	24%	8%	32%	89%
FRANCE	CLOSED	11176,25	241540,25	21,61	2,16	1,73	25%	6%	26%	87%
	OPEN	3934,25	60707,00	15,43	1,85	1,42	22%	7%	30%	89%
GERMANY	CLOSED	13751,50	301153,00	21,90	2,19	1,76	25%	5%	26%	87%
	OPEN	5282,25	84631,50	16,02	1,96	1,42	22%	6%	29%	89%
GREAT BRITAIN	CLOSED	13454,00	309242,75	22,99	2,35	1,79	26%	5%	24%	85%
	OPEN	5450,00	93934,75	17,24	2,15	1,50	25%	6%	26%	88%
GREECE	CLOSED	2545,25	36047,25	14,16	1,55	1,37	18%	8%	28%	81%
	OPEN	735,00	11241,00	15,29	1,78	1,31	20%	9%	32%	87%
HUNGARY	CLOSED	1207,25	17735,50	14,69	1,56	1,27	18%	9%	29%	87%
	OPEN	522,00	7376,00	14,13	1,87	1,39	23%	9%	30%	86%
IRELAND	CLOSED	1205,00	31024,00	25,75	2,48	1,78	26%	6%	25%	86%
	OPEN	333,00	5660,00	17,00	2,04	1,46	24%	7%	31%	87%
ITALY	CLOSED	10962,00	201978,00	18,43	1,92	1,55	21%	7%	27%	84%
	OPEN	3708,25	53944,25	14,55	1,80	1,36	20%	7%	29%	88%
LATVIA	CLOSED	91,00	1001,00	11,00	1,19	1,14	15%	12%	39%	84%
	OPEN	30,00	465,00	15,50	1,79	1,53	27%	7%	43%	83%
LITHUANIA	CLOSED	193,25	2092,00	10,83	1,32	1,04	14%	9%	43%	86%
	OPEN	56,00	611,00	10,91	1,59	1,61	24%	5%	39%	85%
LUXEMBOURG	CLOSED	94,00	1445,00	15,37	1,99	1,50	26%	7%	29%	80%
	OPEN	27,00	318,00	11,78	1,61	1,24	21%	0%	26%	89%
MALTA	CLOSED	22,00	418,00	19,00	1,90	1,51	24%	5%	28%	73%
	OPEN	7,00	195,00	27,86	3,75	1,12	43%	14%	18%	68%
NETHERLANDS	CLOSED	6459,75	157619,50	24,40	2,34	1,84	28%	4%	26%	87%
	OPEN	2219,75	37051,00	16,69	2,02	1,43	25%	5%	31%	89%
POLAND	CLOSED	1842,25	23489,25	12,75	1,39	1,28	15%	9%	37%	85%
	OPEN	790,50	9623,00	12,17	1,54	1,26	16%	9%	36%	87%
PORTUGAL	CLOSED	1741,25	25690,25	14,75	1,66	1,42	19%	8%	30%	84%

	OPEN	889,25	11851,75	13,33	1,79	1,29	20%	9%	31%	86%
ROMANIA	CLOSED	477,00	5546,00	11,63	1,48	1,21	17%	10%	32%	80%
	OPEN	184,00	2515,00	13,67	2,08	1,19	28%	9%	34%	82%
SLOVAKIA	CLOSED	303,00	3893,00	12,85	1,39	1,21	14%	8%	31%	86%
	OPEN	154,25	2324,00	15,07	2,17	1,48	26%	8%	33%	85%
SLOVENIA	CLOSED	493,00	7588,00	15,39	1,62	1,50	19%	8%	31%	84%
	OPEN	256,00	3872,00	15,13	1,93	1,34	24%	6%	36%	84%
SPAIN	CLOSED	9185,25	175279,50	19,08	1,96	1,62	22%	7%	26%	85%
	OPEN	3537,75	50188,50	14,19	1,77	1,38	20%	8%	29%	87%
SWEDEN	CLOSED	3941,00	86550,75	21,96	2,10	1,72	24%	5%	27%	87%
	OPEN	1364,50	20148,25	14,77	1,77	1,36	20%	7%	31%	87%

Table 8 shows us that in all cases, for all EU Member States, the share of Open access mode outputs is smaller as compared to the Closed access mode outputs in the study. Remarkably, for some of the smaller MS we observe somewhat higher average impact scores (mcs) for the Open access mode outputs as compared to the Closed access mode outputs (Greece, Latvia, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia), while for some of the younger MS we observe average impact levels that are nearly equal for both Closed as well as Open access mode outputs. Consequently, the normalized impact scores (mnscs) are higher or equally high in those cases the Open access mode format outputs as compared to the Closed access format outputs. And this is some cases coupled with publishing in journals with relatively higher impact scores (Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, and Slovakia).

Figure 9 shows the output numbers for the two types of access modes for the 27 EU MS, with the Closed access mode still the dominant mode, but with the Open access mode most certainly very well visible. When we shift our attention to the impact scores related to the two modes of scientific publishing, we notice in Figure 10 that the differences between the two modes of publishing on the field normalized impact is relatively small. For most countries we observe the mnscs of the Closed access mode outputs to be higher, while for a small number of countries mnscs values for the Open access mode outputs is higher (Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia). Looking at the impact of the journals in which the outputs appeared (Figure 11), we notice a more or less similar pattern, in which only a few countries published their Open access outputs in journals with a relatively higher impact as compared to the Closed access mode parts of their output: Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, and Slovakia.

FIGURE 9 OUTPUT NUMBERS OF COUNTRIES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 10 FIELD NORMALIZED IMPACT (MNCs) OF COUNTRIES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 11 JOURNAL/FIELD NORMALIZED IMPACT (MNJS) OF COUNTRIES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 12 DIFFERENCES OF MNCS AND MNJS VALUES FOR EU COUNTRIES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

In Figure 12, the differences between the mncs and mnjs scores are shown, against the ordering of the countries by numbers of publications. The figure clearly shows that the larger countries all display lower mncs and mnjs values on their Open access mode published research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects (as the % Diff on both indicators is below the line 0%). In the middle of the figure, where we find countries with somewhat lower outputs, the variable % Diff starts to fluctuate, while in the right hand part of the figure the countries are found with positive scores on the % Diff, indicating higher mncs and mnjs values for the Open access mode outputs.

After the level of the countries, we shift our focus on scientific cooperation patterns. As indicated in the introduction, we distinguish three types of scientific activity, SI (Single Institute, NC (National Cooperation), and IC (International cooperation). These three types are mutually exclusive.

TABLE 9: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	SI	15270,50	246748,50	16,16	1,69	1,43	19%	9%	20%	83%
	NC	11490,00	194819,25	16,96	1,70	1,51	20%	7%	21%	86%
	IC	34718,00	698599,25	20,12	2,07	1,69	23%	6%	25%	86%
OPEN	SI	4115,50	56264,50	13,67	1,73	1,31	19%	11%	19%	87%
	NC	3745,50	48896,00	13,05	1,64	1,31	18%	8%	22%	89%
	IC	13314,75	196827,25	14,78	1,83	1,42	22%	7%	27%	88%

Table 9 contains the overall scores for the whole dataset in the study, distinguishing between the two modes of access for scientific publishing, and the three types of scientific activity. What is remarkable here is that the variation in mncs values for the three types for the Closed access mode outputs is larger as compared to the Open access mode outputs, with in both instances the IC share of the output being related to the highest impact levels. We observe a similar situation for the variable mnjs, albeit not as high as the mncs scores.

Figures 13-15 displays the trend scores for output numbers, mncs and mnjs values for the two types of output modes and the three types of scientific activity. Figure 13 shows us the development of output numbers, in which we observe a similar trend as observed earlier on in the results, namely that the output trend is decreasing for the Closed access mode research outputs, while the Open access mode research output is still increasing in the last block of years, with the IC Open share even surpassing the NC share of Closed access mode publications.

FIGURE 13 TRENDS IN OUTPUT NUMBERS FOR SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

In Figure 14, the development of mncs values is displayed for the two types of access modes and three types of scientific cooperation type. Impact levels for all the six combinations are high, ranging between 50-110 % above worldwide average field impact level. As we observe often in bibliometric studies, international cooperation is rewarding, and that is clear for both modes of scientific publishing.

FIGURE 14 TRENDS IN FIELD NORMALIZED IMPACT SCORES (MNCS) FOR SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

In Figure 15, the journal to field impact scores for the two types of scientific publishing and three types of scientific activity are displayed. Here we find that the impact levels in which the Closed access mode research outputs are published, tend to have higher impact scores as compared to the Open access mode research outputs. However, these are still higher as found in previous studies of openness, indicating that this sample of research outputs is not a random sample from national outputs, but clearly belong to the most prolific researchers in the European research landscape.

FIGURE 15 TRENDS IN JOURNAL/FIELD NORMALIZED IMPACT SCORES (MNJS) FOR SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPES ACROSS VARIOUS ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

After this focus on the geographical composition of outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects, we now shift our attention to the breakdown in fields. Therefore we apply the composition of the scientific landscape in terms of major disciplines of scholarly activity as applied in the former NOWT (NOWT 2010, page 170). This classification system is an aggregation of the journal subject categories from the WoS, and applied in the Dutch and international policy context in numerous studies. Table 10a contains the distribution of FP-7 research outputs over 34 disciplines of science, published in Closed access mode format, while Table 10b contains similar data for Open access mode format.

TABLE 10A: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES FOR CLOSED ACCESS MODE IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SCIENCE	1345,50	16485,00	12,25	1,84	1,41	23%	5%	25%	82%
ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	3878,00	60255,00	15,54	1,45	1,11	17%	4%	36%	89%
BASIC LIFE SCIENCES	9149,75	224881,00	24,58	1,81	1,58	22%	3%	20%	94%
BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES	1495,00	15961,00	10,68	1,23	1,07	13%	6%	31%	85%
BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	3068,50	51334,00	16,73	1,94	1,48	23%	4%	24%	85%

PUBLIC

BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES	5954,50	124148,50	20,85	1,76	1,47	22%	3%	22%	93%
CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	11590,00	237624,00	20,50	1,84	1,75	20%	4%	23%	92%
CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION	355,00	3385,00	9,54	1,89	1,41	24%	6%	24%	62%
CLINICAL MEDICINE	5574,50	123867,75	22,22	1,98	1,63	25%	3%	21%	92%
COMPUTER SCIENCES	4319,25	29939,00	6,93	1,40	1,16	15%	18%	23%	43%
CREATIVE ARTS, CULTURE AND MUSIC	21,00	93,00	4,43	5,01	2,99	27%	19%	21%	41%
EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	3150,00	43250,00	13,73	1,85	1,34	22%	5%	30%	79%
ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS	176,00	1315,00	7,47	1,60	1,49	20%	11%	21%	59%
EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES	42,00	346,00	8,24	1,83	1,40	14%	21%	16%	41%
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION	4943,25	39259,00	7,94	1,49	1,22	17%	14%	23%	52%
ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	1405,00	22286,00	15,86	1,92	1,55	22%	10%	22%	78%
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	3479,25	58607,25	16,84	1,96	1,52	23%	4%	24%	79%
GENERAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	583,00	4605,00	7,90	1,82	1,42	22%	11%	27%	62%
HEALTH SCIENCES	510,00	5995,00	11,75	1,62	1,28	20%	6%	26%	81%
HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION	104,00	732,00	7,04	2,72	1,67	27%	13%	29%	51%
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SCIENCES	87,00	1038,00	11,93	2,19	1,36	19%	6%	19%	42%
INSTRUMENTS AND INSTRUMENTATION	887,00	5900,00	6,65	1,20	0,92	13%	19%	35%	73%
LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS	16,00	60,00	3,75	1,26	1,24	11%	31%	36%	49%
LAW AND CRIMINOLOGY	33,00	255,00	7,73	1,51	1,30	20%	12%	38%	70%
MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING	23,00	121,00	5,26	1,07	1,04	14%	13%	22%	56%
MATHEMATICS	1940,00	9433,00	4,86	1,81	1,36	20%	24%	34%	66%
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND AEROSPACE	1333,00	9918,00	7,44	1,59	1,14	18%	11%	31%	73%
MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS	1654,00	122045,00	73,79	7,22	5,72	61%	1%	15%	92%
PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE	17674,25	274657,00	15,54	1,74	1,52	19%	8%	25%	89%
POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	16,00	81,00	5,06	1,13	1,23	12%	13%	21%	49%
PSYCHOLOGY	307,00	4145,00	13,50	1,59	1,29	16%	3%	25%	81%
SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES,	80,00	424,00	5,30	1,07	0,94	9%	15%	25%	56%

INTERDISCIPLINARY									
SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY	67,00	833,00	12,43	2,79	1,59	40%	3%	31%	59%
STATISTICAL SCIENCES	475,00	2877,00	6,06	1,49	1,21	15%	15%	26%	60%

TABLE 10B: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES FOR OPEN ACCESS MODE IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SCIENCE	124,00	1107,00	8,93	1,72	1,24	19%	10%	26%	89%
ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	3255,25	45043,25	13,84	1,42	1,14	17%	5%	34%	90%
BASIC LIFE SCIENCES	3154,50	71800,00	22,76	2,25	1,62	26%	4%	18%	94%
BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES	161,00	1264,00	7,85	1,24	1,18	13%	11%	27%	83%
BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	1403,25	19057,75	13,58	2,05	1,40	22%	10%	21%	88%
BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES	1549,50	23644,25	15,26	1,80	1,51	25%	5%	21%	93%
CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	930,25	16068,50	17,27	2,09	1,62	22%	5%	22%	90%
CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION	21,00	184,00	8,76	1,69	1,23	27%	10%	30%	69%
CLINICAL MEDICINE	1602,75	22624,75	14,12	1,88	1,51	27%	6%	24%	89%
COMPUTER SCIENCES	367,00	2540,00	6,92	1,76	1,09	15%	23%	24%	55%
EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	1280,25	17549,75	13,71	1,67	1,24	19%	5%	35%	83%
ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS	21,00	210,00	10,00	2,00	1,88	26%	14%	17%	57%
EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES	4,00	4,00	1,00	0,54	0,91	0%	25%	20%	56%
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION	408,00	2820,00	6,91	1,37	0,90	13%	27%	20%	53%
ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	134,00	1718,00	12,82	1,50	1,31	21%	14%	24%	80%
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	870,25	11451,75	13,16	1,84	1,34	23%	4%	28%	79%
GENERAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	52,00	244,00	4,69	1,21	1,28	13%	25%	37%	75%
HEALTH SCIENCES	170,25	1222,00	7,18	1,56	1,17	14%	12%	31%	75%
HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION	7,00	28,00	4,00	3,12	1,35	55%	43%	39%	33%
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SCIENCES	8,00	26,00	3,25	1,81	1,21	16%	25%	26%	48%
INSTRUMENTS AND	205,00	1506,00	7,35	1,07	0,74	12%	20%	29%	66%

PUBLIC

INSTRUMENTATION										
LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS	11,00	47,00	4,27	2,68	1,38	29%	18%	19%	30%	
LAW AND CRIMINOLOGY	6,00	40,00	6,67	1,17	1,36	17%	33%	44%	78%	
MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING	5,00	32,00	6,40	0,87	1,27	0%	20%	18%	46%	
MATHEMATICS	436,00	1548,00	3,55	1,65	1,23	16%	36%	31%	64%	
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND AEROSPACE	141,00	898,00	6,37	1,59	1,18	19%	12%	38%	80%	
MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS	3641,00	47336,00	13,00	1,70	1,45	18%	7%	23%	89%	
PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE	6101,75	83924,50	13,75	1,81	1,39	21%	9%	26%	89%	
POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	14,00	34,00	2,43	1,23	1,32	16%	21%	40%	45%	
PSYCHOLOGY	216,25	1615,00	7,47	1,37	1,24	18%	12%	26%	83%	
SOCIAL BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES, INTERDISCIPLINARY	9,00	28,00	3,11	1,12	0,86	21%	22%	28%	51%	
SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY	6,00	76,00	12,67	2,05	1,42	40%	0%	19%	57%	
STATISTICAL SCIENCES	83,00	330,00	3,98	1,27	0,87	16%	31%	27%	65%	

Table 11 contains results of a comparative analysis of three indicators P, mncs and mnjs. With respect to the output indicator p we show the share of the output being published in Open access mode. The table presents the shares in Open access mode as compared to the Closed access mode output, and shares that stand out among the disciplines are: MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS, ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS, POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION, PSYCHOLOGY, and LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS. However, it is still interesting to look at those fields that have not the highest share, but have the highest absolute number of Open access mode research outputs. These disciplines are: PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS, ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS, BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, CLINICAL MEDICINE , BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES and BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES. Fields with a higher mncs value for the Open access mode published research outputs are : LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS, ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION, COMPUTER SCIENCES , and BASIC LIFE SCIENCES. Again, we also want to include the perspective on the high values on mncs for Open access mode. Fields with high mncs values for Open access mode are: LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS, SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY, ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, and more or less at the same level, HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION and CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING. Finally, we focus on the mnjs indicator distribution across fields and access modes. As observed earlier in this study, we find that mnjs scores hardly deviate, the only two fields that show a clear difference between journal impact scores for

Closed and Open access mode outputs are ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS and MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING. Fields in which we find high journal impact levels in which the Open access modes outputs were published are: ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY, and CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING , and BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES.

A clear conclusion following this analysis is that whenever social scientists and humanities scholars, funded by FP-7 research projects, publish in journals, they find their way into high impact Open Access journals. And although numbers might be small, the fact that these publications appear in high impact journals is quite indicative of the changing focus on open science in SSH research funded by FP-7 projects.

TABLE 11: SHARES IN OUTPUT AND DIFFERENCES IN IMPACT OF SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES FOR ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	CLOSED			OPEN			Diff		CLOSED			OPEN			Diff
	p	p	% OA	mncs	mncs				mnjs	mnjs		mnjs	mnjs		
AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SCIENCE	1345,50	124,00	8%	1,84	1,72	-7%		1,41	1,24					-12%	
ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	3878,00	3255,25	46%	1,45	1,42	-2%		1,11	1,14					3%	
BASIC LIFE SCIENCES	9149,75	3154,50	26%	1,81	2,25	24%		1,58	1,62					3%	
BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES	1495,00	161,00	10%	1,23	1,24	1%		1,07	1,18					10%	
BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	3068,50	1403,25	31%	1,94	2,05	5%		1,48	1,40					-5%	
BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES	5954,50	1549,50	21%	1,76	1,80	2%		1,47	1,51					3%	
CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	11590,00	930,25	7%	1,84	2,09	14%		1,75	1,62					-7%	
CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION	355,00	21,00	6%	1,89	1,69	-10%		1,41	1,23					-12%	
CLINICAL MEDICINE	5574,50	1602,75	22%	1,98	1,88	-5%		1,63	1,51					-7%	
COMPUTER SCIENCES	4319,25	367,00	8%	1,40	1,76	25%		1,16	1,09					-6%	
CREATIVE ARTS, CULTURE AND MUSIC	21,00		0%	5,01		-100%		2,99						-100%	
EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	3150,00	1280,25	29%	1,85	1,67	-10%		1,34	1,24					-7%	
ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS	176,00	21,00	11%	1,60	2,00	24%		1,49	1,88					26%	
EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES	42,00	4,00	9%	1,83	0,54	-70%		1,40	0,91					-35%	
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION	4943,25	408,00	8%	1,49	1,37	-8%		1,22	0,90					-27%	
ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	1405,00	134,00	9%	1,92	1,50	-22%		1,55	1,31					-15%	
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	3479,25	870,25	20%	1,96	1,84	-6%		1,52	1,34					-12%	

PUBLIC

GENERAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	583,00	52,00	8%	1,82	1,21	-33%	1,42	1,28	-10%
HEALTH SCIENCES	510,00	170,25	25%	1,62	1,56	-3%	1,28	1,17	-9%
HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION	104,00	7,00	6%	2,72	3,12	15%	1,67	1,35	-19%
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SCIENCES	87,00	8,00	8%	2,19	1,81	-17%	1,36	1,21	-11%
INSTRUMENTS AND INSTRUMENTATION	887,00	205,00	19%	1,20	1,07	-11%	0,92	0,74	-20%
LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS	16,00	11,00	41%	1,26	2,68	113%	1,24	1,38	11%
LAW AND CRIMINOLOGY	33,00	6,00	15%	1,51	1,17	-22%	1,30	1,36	4%
MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING	23,00	5,00	18%	1,07	0,87	-19%	1,04	1,27	23%
MATHEMATICS	1940,00	436,00	18%	1,81	1,65	-9%	1,36	1,23	-9%
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND AEROSPACE	1333,00	141,00	10%	1,59	1,59	0%	1,14	1,18	3%
MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS	1654,00	3641,00	69%	7,22	1,70	-76%	5,72	1,45	-75%
PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE	17674,25	6101,75	26%	1,74	1,81	4%	1,52	1,39	-9%
POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	16,00	14,00	47%	1,13	1,23	9%	1,23	1,32	8%
PSYCHOLOGY	307,00	216,25	41%	1,59	1,37	-14%	1,29	1,24	-4%
SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES, INTERDISCIPLINARY	80,00	9,00	10%	1,07	1,12	4%	0,94	0,86	-9%
SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY	67,00	6,00	8%	2,79	2,05	-26%	1,59	1,42	-11%
STATISTICAL SCIENCES	475,00	83,00	15%	1,49	1,27	-15%	1,21	0,87	-28%

In the next analysis we focus on the orientation of actors within the national science systems in each EU MS. We combine in this analysis for the top producing institutions per MS the output with impact scores. Please note that we vary the number of intuitions in perspective of the volume of the science system we are analyzing, which means more institutions for the larger MS as compared to the smaller MS. This is mainly due to the fact that for the smaller MS, we only had that few institutions in the study. The graphs contain bar charts that present the shares of the institutional outputs in Open access mode as compared to the Closed access mode (by definition, this is a positive value, which is indicated in blue bars in the graphs), while the indication of the impact (mncs) can be either negative (mncs of Closed output outperforms the Open access mode related output), or positive (the mncs related to the

Open access mode part of the output outperforms the Closed access mode related output). The negative is indicated in red, and is leftward oriented, while the positive is indicated in green, and is rightward oriented. Figures 16 – 41 display these graphs for the 27 EU MS.

For clarity reasons, we will discuss the first graph, Figure 16. Here we find for the top producing Austrian institutions the shares of Open access mode outputs, in combination with their impact scores on Closed and Open access format outputs. The Open access mode output shares range between 45-70%, which is quite varied among the top most producing institutions. Among those institutions displayed here, only two have a higher impact on their Open access mode outputs as compared to the Closed access mode outputs. These two are the Tech Univ Wien, and the AIT, the Austrian Institute of Technology. In all other cases, mncs values of the Closed access format output are higher as compared to the Open access mode output. Remarkably, two institutions in the technical realm do display the higher impact scores for the Open access mode outputs.

FIGURE 16 INSTITUTIONS FROM AUSTRIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 17 INSTITUTIONS FROM BELGIUM, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 18 INSTITUTIONS FROM BULGARIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 19 INSTITUTIONS FROM CYPRUS, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 20 INSTITUTIONS FROM THE CZECH REPUBLIC, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 21 INSTITUTIONS FROM DENMARK, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 22 INSTITUTIONS FROM ESTONIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 23 INSTITUTIONS FROM FINLAND, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 24 INSTITUTIONS FROM FRANCE, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 25 INSTITUTIONS FROM GERMANY, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 26 INSTITUTIONS FROM GREAT BRITAIN, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 27 INSTITUTIONS FROM GREECE, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 28 INSTITUTIONS FROM HUNGARY, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 29 INSTITUTIONS FROM IRELAND, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 30 INSTITUTIONS FROM ITALY, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 31 INSTITUTIONS FROM LATVIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 32 INSTITUTIONS FROM LITHUANIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 33 INSTITUTIONS FROM LUXEMBOURG, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 34 INSTITUTIONS FROM THE NETHERLANDS, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 35 INSTITUTIONS FROM POLAND, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 36 INSTITUTIONS FROM PORTUGAL, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 37 INSTITUTIONS FROM ROMANIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 38 INSTITUTIONS FROM SLOVAKIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 39 INSTITUTIONS FROM SLOVENIA, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 40 INSTITUTIONS FROM SPAIN, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 41 INSTITUTIONS FROM SWEDEN, CONTRIBUTIONS TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHED OUTPUTS OF FP-7 PROJECTS AND THE IMPACT OF BY THESE OUTPUTS, COMPARED TO CLOSED ACCESS MODE OUTPUTS, 2008-2015/2016.

In general, we observed the situation as we described for Austria more often: institutions of technology tend to have higher impact scores on their Open access mode outputs. And another observation is the situation that institutions in the top of the graphs in the young EU MS tend to show higher Open access mode as compared to their Closed access mode (Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia). Finally, for two older EU MS we find also very high impact on the Open access mode, namely Greece and Portugal.

The overall trend of the output in the various types of publishing from FP-7 funded research projects, we notice that while the Closed access format output starts to top off in the later stages of the FP-7 Framework, the Open access is still increasing in numbers. This indicates the growing interest of OA publishing for scholars funded by the FP-7, probably stimulated by active policies by the EU and various national open access mandates. The impact related to the Open access format output is below the Closed access format published output from FP-7 funded research projects, but still at a very high level (60-70% above worldwide average impact level). The output is published in journals that have an impact that is somewhat below the impact of the journals related to Closed access output, but of a high impact themselves, and tend to increase in the later stages of FP-7 as well. We notice that for some of the younger EU MS the impact of the Open access format output outperforms the Closed access format outputs, both when we look at the field normalized impact, as well as looking at the journal impact scores.

Publications in Open access format, resulting from international cooperation do show an increasing trend, while the impact of these publications is higher as compared to the impact of the single institute and national cooperation output resulting from Closed access format publishing.

With respect to the fields in which the output appeared we notice that among the STM domains, (natural sciences and biomedicine), we find some diversity as it comes to focus on Open access format outputs. Fields with relative low shares of Open access format outputs are CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING, CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION, ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION, ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, GENERAL INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING and COMPUTER SCIENCES. Fields with large quantities of output numbers with a relative strong focus on Open access format outputs are: ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS, BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY, EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY, HEALTH SCIENCES, and PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE. These fields have over 25% of their outputs publishes as Open access format outputs.

The analysis of the institutions in EU MS and their focus on Open access output, in perspective of the impact related to the Open access formatted output shows that the 'smaller and younger' EU MS have a somewhat stronger focus on Open access, which is then often combined with relatively high impact scores on their Open access impact outputs. Yet another remarkable outcome, as it contrasts the overall observation a on field level when it comes to the engineering disciplines, is the apparent stronger focus of institutions revolving round engineering sciences, on Open access formatted output.

10 RESULTS OF ECONOMIC IMPACT OF FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS

In this section we will focus on the link between research outputs and technology, that is, patents. Here we use references in patents to research outputs in our set in order to be able to analyze any kind of economic value of research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 registered research outputs. In this case the assumption is that references in patents towards research publications indicate a relevance for a technological development, as expressed by patents. We will focus our analysis on a number of issues:

- Overall impacts of the various access modes of publications cited by patents.
- Output and impact scores for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, by citing technology sectors.
- Output and impact scores for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, by citing technology fields.
- Country analysis of funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, as cited by patents.

The Spring 2015 Version of PATSTAT² was used. Twice a year a snapshot of the EPO master documentation database is taken to produce a new version of the PATSTAT-databases. This spring 2015 version of PATSTAT contains bibliographic data for over 81 million patent applications from more than 80 regional or national patent offices. For all patent publications the database contains information on:

- Patent applicants — names, addresses;
- Inventors — names, addresses;
- Various dates — date of application, of publication, of grant, and lapse;
- Area of technology — based on the fine grained patent classification systems;
- Citation links to other patents;
- Citation links to so called non-patent literature references (NPLRs), e.g. scholarly publications;
- The origin of a citation link — applicant, employee of a patent office, third party;
- Title and abstract of an invention;

Around 50% of the more than 27 million so-called NPLRs consist of preferences to scholarly publications. At CWTS around 20% of the NPLR references, which are embedded in free format text strings, could be matched with corresponding information in the WoS database. The matching is hindered by several factors, e.g.

1. the free format nature of the text strings that needs to be parsed;
2. not all referenced scholarly publications are covered in the WoS, as not all journals are covered, the CWTS version of the WoS contains data on publications from 1980 onwards;
3. incomplete NPLR information;

² The official name for PATSTAT is 'the EPO Worldwide Patent Statistical Database'

Patstat contains a table that links the more than 70.000 patent classification codes to five technology sectors covering 35 technology fields³. By combining the information on the technology fields of a patent with the NPLR, using the CWTS PATSTAT-WoS matching table, and combining with the information on Open or Closed access is possible to link a scholarly publication to a specific technology field.

10.1 Description of the basic outcomes

In Table 12 we present the outcomes of the analysis of cited output by patents in a global sense. For all cited publications, we can generate similar bibliometric statistics as we calculated for the registered outputs of FP-7 funded projects. Due to the fact that most registered outputs of FP-7 funded research projects are still relatively 'young', and the fact that patent citation analysis tends to capture cited literature of a very recent nature, due to the gap between research done and technology developed, and the time involved in filing the patent, and getting it granted. Therefore, we have a small sample of the full set of registered FP-7 outputs. Given this situation, the composition of the cited outputs in terms of Closed and Open access format publications is somewhat distorted, in the advantage of the Closed access formatted outputs: as we have seen these outnumber the Open access formatted publications, except for the later years of the total running time of the FP-7 funding instrument (that is less visible in patent citation analysis).

TABLE 12: PUBLICATIONS REFERRED TO IN PATENTS , ACCESS MODES IN FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	1262,00	112348,00	89,02	5,90	2,86	49%	1%	13%	90%
OPEN	133,00	10779,00	81,05	5,38	2,41	50%	2%	13%	91%

So after having given the context against which to interpret these scores, we can clearly notice that the selected publications cited in patents do have high impact scores, as the mncs scores of the closed and open access format publication sets stand out compared to the overall impact scores of both sets of publications. Furthermore, also the contribution to the top publications in the respective fields these publications belong to is extremely high, and higher as compared to the overall set of publications forthcoming from FP7 funded projects.

³ More information on this technology classification can be found in "Concept of a Technology Classification for Country Comparisons" by Ulrich Schmoch, July 2008; http://www.wipo.int/edocs/mdocs/classifications/en/ipc_ce_41/ipc_ce_41_5-annex1.pdf

TABLE 13: PATENT TECHNOLOGY SECTORS REFERRING TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov	
Chemistry	CLOSED	892,00	89037,00	99,82	6,12	3,00	50%	0%	13%	95%
	OPEN	102,00	7171,00	70,30	4,17	2,39	49%	1%	15%	96%
Electrical engineering	CLOSED	342,00	37808,00	110,55	8,29	3,22	52%	3%	10%	75%
	OPEN	27,00	3609,00	133,67	10,72	3,10	52%	4%	7%	76%
Instruments	CLOSED	331,00	29007,00	87,63	5,21	2,82	51%	2%	15%	90%
	OPEN	38,00	2356,00	62,00	4,04	2,08	48%	8%	14%	90%
Mechanical engineering	CLOSED	50,00	6422,00	128,44	7,71	3,71	56%	2%	10%	88%
	OPEN	7,00	667,00	95,29	4,35	1,81	71%	0%	14%	97%
Other fields	CLOSED	7,00	366,00	52,29	3,98	4,40	35%	0%	16%	79%

In Table 13 the technology sectors in which the patents are organized are shown that refer to the FP-7 research outputs, distinguishing between Open en Closed access format outputs. In all sectors, the Closed access mode outputs are referred to more often as compared to the Open access mode outputs. What is particularly striking is the impact related to the publications that are cited in patents, and the technology sectors attached to the patents. The mncs values related to the outputs cited by patents is very high, in all cases at least 3 times the worldwide average impact level, and in most cases even much higher. The only technology sector in which the Open access mode outperforms the Closed access mode is the sector Electrical engineering, in which the 27 publications have tenfold the worldwide average impact level. Another interesting finding is the contribution these publications have to the global scientific literature: in nearly all cases the share of top 10% publications is five times as high as one might expect. All in all, these scores show that publications referred to in patents are not a random sample from the total pile of scientific literature, the most prolific publications are apparently cited by patents.

In Table 14, the scores for publications and the two modes of publishing, as cited by patent technology fields are shown.

TABLE 14: PATENT TECHNOLOGY FIELDS REFERRING TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov	
Analysis of biological materials	CLOSED	179,00	21039,00	117,54	6,22	3,15	57%	0%	14%	96%
	OPEN	21,00	1201,00	57,19	3,02	1,77	59%	0%	15%	96%
Audio-visual technology	CLOSED	25,00	1371,00	54,84	4,67	3,09	52%	8%	12%	52%
Basic communication processes	CLOSED	15,00	757,00	50,47	6,04	2,57	47%	7%	17%	63%
	OPEN	3,00	244,00	81,33	9,44	1,47	33%	0%	7%	78%
Basic materials chemistry	CLOSED	63,00	13889,00	220,46	13,14	3,37	60%	0%	8%	94%
	OPEN	3,00	94,00	31,33	2,04	1,19	44%	0%	24%	92%
Biotechnology	CLOSED	509,00	50782,00	99,77	5,73	3,13	52%	0%	14%	95%
	OPEN	75,00	6475,00	86,33	4,87	2,24	55%	0%	14%	96%
Chemical engineering	CLOSED	62,00	10157,00	163,82	10,79	3,53	51%	0%	8%	91%
	OPEN	5,00	127,00	25,40	1,76	2,73	33%	0%	17%	93%
Civil engineering	CLOSED	1,00	7,00	7,00	0,38	1,37	0%	0%	42%	91%
Computer technology	CLOSED	135,00	11652,00	86,31	6,49	3,34	49%	5%	11%	66%
	OPEN	12,00	2148,00	179,00	12,76	3,71	42%	8%	4%	76%
Control	CLOSED	9,00	201,00	22,33	3,60	1,55	56%	11%	9%	45%
Digital communication	CLOSED	37,00	1123,00	30,35	4,51	1,78	37%	0%	17%	37%
	OPEN	2,00	230,00	115,00	13,58	1,89	50%	0%	2%	57%
Electrical machinery, apparatus, energy	CLOSED	64,00	12996,00	203,06	14,42	4,36	61%	0%	10%	95%
	OPEN	3,00	93,00	31,00	3,74	1,34	100%	0%	33%	98%
Engines, pumps, turbines	CLOSED	4,00	48,00	12,00	1,49	0,73	25%	0%	34%	90%
	OPEN	1,00	28,00	28,00	4,33	1,23	100%	0%	32%	96%
Environmental technology	CLOSED	14,00	2171,00	155,07	10,12	4,71	54%	0%	10%	91%
Food chemistry	CLOSED	30,00	1778,00	59,27	3,67	2,89	51%	0%	15%	94%
	OPEN	4,00	370,00	92,50	6,01	1,67	63%	0%	12%	93%
Furniture, games	CLOSED	1,00	12,00	12,00	2,10	2,47	0%	0%	0%	28%
Handling	CLOSED	1,00	42,00	42,00	8,13	1,31	100%	0%	13%	27%

PUBLIC

IT methods for management	CLOSED	7,00	1703,00	243,29	19,67	2,40	43%	0%	6%	58%
	OPEN	1,00	1585,00	1585,00	119,39	9,50	100%	0%	1%	65%
Machine tools	CLOSED	1,00	32,00	32,00	4,16	1,73	100%	0%	29%	51%
Macromolecular chemistry, polymers	CLOSED	50,00	3855,00	77,10	4,52	2,36	49%	0%	16%	93%
Materials, metallurgy	CLOSED	42,00	7868,00	187,33	13,08	4,25	63%	0%	9%	94%
	OPEN	2,00	20,00	10,00	0,75	3,83	0%	50%	38%	87%
Measurement	CLOSED	95,00	7303,00	76,87	5,56	3,08	50%	2%	15%	83%
	OPEN	12,00	1322,00	110,17	7,54	2,84	49%	8%	11%	83%
Mechanical elements	CLOSED	1,00	992,00	992,00	52,77	13,88	100%	0%	3%	96%
Medical technology	CLOSED	57,00	4088,00	71,72	4,49	2,25	46%	2%	15%	87%
	OPEN	4,00	82,00	20,50	1,23	1,53	25%	25%	25%	93%
Micro-structural and nano-technology	CLOSED	52,00	4449,00	85,56	6,46	4,63	62%	0%	15%	94%
	OPEN	6,00	130,00	21,67	2,16	3,76	33%	17%	23%	93%
Optics	CLOSED	46,00	2876,00	62,52	4,88	3,06	54%	4%	17%	85%
	OPEN	5,00	119,00	23,80	2,10	1,93	30%	20%	21%	89%
Organic chemistry fine	CLOSED	182,00	17572,00	96,55	5,48	2,74	47%	0%	15%	95%
	OPEN	13,00	555,00	42,69	2,18	1,31	24%	0%	10%	95%
Other goods consumer	CLOSED	5,00	347,00	69,40	5,07	5,39	50%	0%	16%	82%
Other machines special	CLOSED	28,00	4106,00	146,64	7,27	3,35	61%	0%	11%	96%
	OPEN	5,00	619,00	123,80	4,96	1,90	80%	0%	12%	98%
Pharmaceuticals	CLOSED	385,00	35311,00	91,72	5,31	2,65	47%	0%	15%	96%
	OPEN	39,00	2370,00	60,77	3,49	2,23	51%	0%	14%	96%
Semiconductors	CLOSED	111,00	20810,00	187,48	13,09	4,22	64%	0%	9%	93%
	OPEN	7,00	924,00	132,00	10,31	3,41	57%	0%	10%	96%
Surface technology, coating	CLOSED	28,00	3420,00	122,14	9,01	3,96	59%	0%	10%	93%
	OPEN	3,00	115,00	38,33	3,49	0,91	33%	33%	18%	87%
Telecommunications	CLOSED	39,00	2299,00	58,95	6,72	2,50	43%	5%	14%	56%
	OPEN	4,00	277,00	69,25	8,20	2,75	75%	0%	16%	55%
Textile and paper machines	CLOSED	11,00	1312,00	119,27	8,54	3,74	64%	0%	10%	96%
	OPEN	1,00	20,00	20,00	1,32	1,95	0%	0%	20%	95%
Thermal processes	CLOSED	3,00	169,00	56,33	6,42	10,66	36%	0%	16%	66%

and apparatus										
Transport	CLOSED	5,00	106,00	21,20	3,48	1,48	40%	20%	10%	37%

In Table 15 the geographical spreading of patent citations over FP-7 research outputs is presented, again taking into account the distinction between Closed and Open access modes of publishing. Not surprisingly, as a general observation, the Open access mode part of the national outputs under the FP-7 funded projects is smaller in all cases. With respect to the impact scores related to these two forms of scientific publishing, we observe high impact scores for both the Closed and the Open access mode outputs. Another remarkable finding is the apparent strong preference for high impact research outputs of the larger EU MS France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Spain, completed by the Netherlands. For Great Britain, Italy and Spain the impact (mncs) of the Open access mode publication output resulting from FP-7 funded research projects is higher as compared to the Closed access mode research outputs.

TABLE 15: PATENTS REFERRING TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, BY COUNTRY AND TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AUSTRIA	CLOSED	69,00	4685,00	67,90	3,74	2,78	49%	0%	24%	89%
	OPEN	10,00	1072,00	107,20	5,25	2,65	68%	0%	13%	88%
BELGIUM	CLOSED	94,00	11572,00	123,11	7,44	3,03	52%	1%	15%	93%
	OPEN	9,00	989,00	109,89	6,61	3,04	67%	0%	26%	98%
BULGARIA	CLOSED	3,00	67,00	22,33	1,98	1,41	35%	0%	17%	74%
CZECH REPUBLIC	CLOSED	17,00	1094,00	64,35	3,89	4,13	47%	0%	23%	94%
	OPEN	2,00	140,00	70,00	6,56	6,53	50%	0%	23%	100%
DENMARK	CLOSED	73,00	9671,00	132,48	7,65	3,27	43%	0%	18%	94%
	OPEN	3,00	53,00	17,67	1,41	3,23	11%	0%	30%	98%
ESTONIA	CLOSED	6,00	1327,00	221,17	9,33	2,99	92%	0%	30%	96%
	OPEN	2,00	587,00	293,50	15,37	7,81	100%	0%	34%	100%
FINLAND	CLOSED	68,00	9013,00	132,54	8,17	3,01	64%	1%	20%	89%
	OPEN	7,00	753,00	107,57	5,78	3,59	43%	0%	32%	94%
FRANCE	CLOSED	247,00	26302,00	106,49	6,62	3,22	48%	0%	15%	91%
	OPEN	21,00	2257,00	107,48	5,82	3,11	66%	5%	20%	96%
GERMANY	CLOSED	290,00	28188,00	97,20	6,18	3,20	51%	0%	17%	92%
	OPEN	30,00	3097,00	103,23	5,79	3,02	50%	0%	19%	96%
GREAT BRITAIN	CLOSED	264,00	31956,00	121,05	7,83	3,61	57%	0%	14%	88%
	OPEN	32,00	4530,00	141,56	8,18	3,08	53%	3%	14%	95%
GREECE	CLOSED	36,00	1575,00	43,75	3,13	2,42	31%	0%	18%	87%
	OPEN	2,00	420,00	210,00	12,33	8,03	50%	0%	41%	97%
HUNGARY	CLOSED	13,00	483,00	37,15	1,83	1,93	48%	0%	29%	92%
	OPEN	2,00	104,00	52,00	2,98	1,99	100%	0%	21%	100%

PUBLIC

IRELAND	CLOSED	31,00	4909,00	158,35	10,91	4,89	49%	0%	21%	93%
	OPEN	4,00	252,00	63,00	4,75	1,35	62%	0%	13%	94%
ITALY	CLOSED	205,00	17743,00	86,55	5,48	2,92	48%	1%	18%	88%
	OPEN	26,00	3112,00	119,69	8,64	2,92	51%	0%	15%	87%
LITHUANIA	CLOSED	2,00	48,00	24,00	1,52	1,18	50%	0%	19%	89%
	OPEN	1,00	26,00	26,00	1,73	2,18	0%	0%	13%	98%
LUXEMBOURG	CLOSED	2,00	40,00	20,00	1,84	1,29	0%	0%	41%	88%
NETHERLANDS	CLOSED	145,00	17192,00	118,57	7,42	3,65	65%	0%	18%	94%
	OPEN	14,00	1289,00	92,07	6,10	3,21	63%	0%	26%	96%
POLAND	CLOSED	16,00	1659,00	103,69	6,33	3,29	55%	0%	29%	94%
	OPEN	3,00	649,00	216,33	12,70	6,27	100%	0%	33%	96%
PORTUGAL	CLOSED	19,00	725,00	38,16	3,72	2,08	40%	0%	18%	84%
	OPEN	1,00	17,00	17,00	2,05	1,63	50%	0%	45%	83%
ROMANIA	CLOSED	7,00	290,00	41,43	2,32	2,61	50%	0%	22%	83%
	OPEN	1,00	19,00	19,00	1,67	0,97	0%	0%	17%	56%
SLOVAKIA	CLOSED	4,00	168,00	42,00	2,26	2,69	75%	0%	26%	95%
SLOVENIA	CLOSED	4,00	715,00	178,75	9,19	5,44	75%	0%	14%	97%
	OPEN	1,00	7,00	7,00	0,52	1,29	0%	0%	42%	88%
SPAIN	CLOSED	165,00	21551,00	130,61	8,10	3,69	64%	1%	14%	91%
	OPEN	12,00	1707,00	142,25	8,92	3,26	44%	0%	20%	97%
SWEDEN	CLOSED	113,00	10487,00	92,81	6,51	3,24	55%	1%	20%	90%
	OPEN	12,00	1046,00	87,17	4,42	2,70	60%	0%	29%	93%

In Table 16, the science fields related to the publications resulting from FP-7 funded research projects are shown, by the two types of scientific publishing. The fields that are most often cited by patents are BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES, CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING, CLINICAL MEDICINE, ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION, and PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE.

TABLE 16: PATENTS REFERRING TO FP-7 FUNDED PROJECTS, BY SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE AND TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SCIENCE	CLOSED	13,00	339,00	26,08	2,23	1,33	40%	0%	22%	88%
	OPEN	1,00	17,00	17,00	2,05	1,63	50%	0%	45%	83%
ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	CLOSED	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,45	0%	100%	100%	82%
	OPEN	57,00	4530,00	79,47	4,25	1,95	49%	0%	10%	95%
BASIC LIFE SCIENCES	CLOSED	363,00	29765,00	82,00	4,63	2,40	48%	0%	16%	95%
	OPEN	57,00	4530,00	79,47	4,25	1,95	49%	0%	10%	95%
BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES	CLOSED	50,00	1018,00	20,36	1,87	1,36	24%	0%	35%	87%
	OPEN	2,00	26,00	13,00	1,61	1,06	24%	0%	38%	94%

Impact of Open Access published research PUBLIC

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	CLOSED	34,00	2833,00	83,32	8,30	2,12	44%	0%	9%	91%
	OPEN	4,00	164,00	41,00	2,93	2,39	63%	0%	10%	93%
BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES	CLOSED	198,00	11477,00	57,96	3,45	2,18	43%	1%	19%	95%
	OPEN	15,00	993,00	66,20	4,39	2,45	59%	0%	13%	97%
CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	CLOSED	314,00	26354,00	83,93	5,38	2,81	50%	0%	14%	93%
	OPEN	14,00	1082,00	77,29	5,65	1,72	46%	0%	12%	95%
CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION	CLOSED	2,00	22,00	11,00	2,30	1,75	50%	0%	19%	42%
CLINICAL MEDICINE	CLOSED	176,00	12301,00	69,89	3,91	2,34	46%	1%	14%	96%
	OPEN	16,00	596,00	37,25	2,61	1,64	40%	0%	20%	96%
COMPUTER SCIENCES	CLOSED	64,00	1578,00	24,66	3,64	1,35	41%	5%	16%	37%
	OPEN	2,00	396,00	198,00	23,36	1,76	100%	0%	7%	74%
EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	CLOSED	6,00	229,00	38,17	3,65	1,42	60%	0%	41%	79%
	OPEN	1,00	19,00	19,00	1,67	0,97	0%	0%	17%	56%
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION	CLOSED	108,00	2901,00	26,86	3,71	1,58	38%	6%	18%	47%
	OPEN	7,00	573,00	81,86	9,64	2,17	71%	0%	10%	60%
ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	CLOSED	25,00	1505,00	60,20	5,79	2,28	38%	0%	14%	91%
	OPEN	2,00	47,00	23,50	2,12	2,16	50%	0%	27%	98%
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY	CLOSED	12,00	1214,00	101,17	9,77	3,11	48%	0%	14%	90%
GENERAL INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	CLOSED	2,00	16,00	8,00	0,85	1,14	0%	50%	24%	27%
HEALTH SCIENCES	CLOSED	5,00	267,00	53,40	3,32	1,46	60%	0%	18%	99%
INSTRUMENTS AND INSTRUMENTATION	CLOSED	16,00	286,00	17,88	2,11	1,18	29%	6%	27%	75%
	OPEN	3,00	114,00	38,00	3,74	1,12	78%	0%	18%	95%
MATHEMATICS	CLOSED	3,00	6,00	2,00	0,38	1,84	0%	33%	45%	54%
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND AEROSPACE	CLOSED	7,00	184,00	26,29	2,94	0,99	29%	14%	19%	48%
MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS	CLOSED	72,00	24913,00	346,01	23,64	9,52	83%	0%	9%	95%
	OPEN	16,00	1359,00	84,94	4,82	3,52	40%	0%	25%	96%
PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE	CLOSED	249,00	23540,00	94,54	7,20	3,41	54%	1%	11%	89%
	OPEN	23,00	2845,00	123,70	9,55	3,71	44%	13%	8%	83%
PSYCHOLOGY	CLOSED	1,00	49,00	49,00	2,26	4,72	67%	0%	21%	96%

A first conclusion from the analysis of patents citing to outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects is the fact that the field normalized impact scores are very high, compared to the overall impact scores of all outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. This is something we observed in previous studies as well, which might have something to do with the preference by patent examiners for highly prolific scientific outputs (which is underlined by the high impact levels of the journals in which the cited publications appeared).

When looking at the technology sectors, we notice that the Closed access format outputs are cited most frequently, and these outputs have the higher impact scores, except for the sector Electrical engineering, in which the mncs is tenfold worldwide average impact level for the Open access format outputs.

Among the technology fields, we find six technology fields that cite Closed access outputs from FP-7 funded projects over 100 times each: Analysis of biological materials, Biotechnology, Computer technology, Organic fine chemistry, Pharmaceuticals, and Semiconductors. Impacts related to these outputs are high to very high. We find in some technology fields high impact scores on the Open access format outputs, but this is related to very small numbers in most cases.

In terms of the geographical spreading, the larger EU MS are most cited, while the impacts of the smaller EU MS is often somewhat higher. Among these smaller EU MS, the Open access formatted outputs cited by patents are having higher impact scores as compared to their Closed access formatted outputs, albeit that this is based on sometimes smaller outputs (Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, and Poland).

When looking at the science fields cited by patents, a few stand out: BASIC LIFE SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES, CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING, CLINICAL MEDICINE, ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION, and PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE.

1.1 RESULTS OF SOCIETAL IMPACT OF FP-7 REGISTERED OUTPUTS

In this section we will focus on the link between research outputs and societal impact, as can be measured by altmetrics, or social media analysis. Altmetrics stands for alternative metrics, which were launched as a reaction to an increasing demand to indicate societal relevance of research, something classical bibliometric methods were not capable of doing properly. Initially proposed by Jason Priem and colleagues (Priem et al, 2011), the research has taken off seriously in the bibliometrics community, forming already a special line of research within bibliometrics with a dedicated community working on the topic. After initial optimism, more and more critical comments are made by these researchers on social media metrics (Thelwall et al. 2013), which is particularly important given the use already made of these new metrics in science policy in various levels of the science system, and in particular in relationship to the open science/open access discussion. A recent EU Report, by an Expert Group on Altmetrics indicated that the use of altmetrics should, similar to more traditional metrics, be accompanied by expertise as found in peer review, while at the same time stated that currently altmetrics as relative new form of research metrics is not yet fully reliable (<https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/report.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none>).

Here we use mentions in two datasets on social media analysis, that is Mendeley, which tells us about readership, and Altmetric.com data, which informs us about various social media (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, news, and blogs, to name a few) related to research outputs in our set in order to be able to analyze any kind of societal relevance value of research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 registered research outputs. In this case the assumption is that mentions in these social media datasets towards research publications indicate a relevance for a society, as expressed by readership, Tweets, Facebook mentions, etc.. We will focus our analysis on a number of issues:

- Overall description of users/readerships within the Mendeley system.
- Output and impact scores for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, as mentioned overall by Mendeley user/readerships.
- Output and impact scores by scientific activity types for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, as mentioned overall by Mendeley user/readerships.
- Output and impact scores by Mendeley user/readerships for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.
- Overall description of social media types within the Altmetric.com system.
- Output and impact scores for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, as mentioned overall by Altmetric.com.
- Output and impact scores by scientific activity types for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects, as mentioned overall by Altmetric.com.
- Output and impact scores by Altmetric.com social media types for funded projects, and the various access modes related to the projects.

Mendeley is a free desktop and web program for managing and sharing research papers, discovering research data and collaborating online, addressing the academic social network. Mendeley requires the user to store all

basic citation data on its servers—storing copies of documents is at the user's discretion. Mendeley, named after the biologist Gregor Mendel and chemist Dmitri Mendeleev, was founded in 2007. In 2012, Mendeley was one of the repositories for green Open Access. The system Mendeley was purchased by the Elsevier publishing company in 2013. CWTS has the Mendeley information stored in an in-house version, containing the user/readership counts of academics of scientific literature, as covered in the WoS.

Altmetric.com is a database system that contains various qualitative sources of social media attention, quantified in one single score. While the various contributing parts all deliver a certain weight to the final score, we have worked with the most important types of social media attention in a loose fashion with respect to the scientific publications mentioned in the Altmetrics.com system (to see how the various contributing parts are weighted in the altmetrics.com system, please visit <https://help.altmetric.com/support/solutions/articles/6000060969-how-is-the-altmetric-attention-score-calculated->).

Both sets, for Mendeley information as well as for Altmetrics.com information are stored in in-house sql datasets within CWTS. Direct links between these sets and the WoS database are made using doi's of the publications.

1 1.1 Description of the basic outcomes

The Mendeley data system centers around readership, as defined by various actors within the science system. Below we find in Table 17 the various groups of users/readers as distinguished in Mendeley. For both realms, Closed and Open, we notice that relatively young staff within academic belong to the most frequent users/readers among the total user/reader [population of research output forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. Ph.D. Students and PostDoc's together form nearly 25% of the total users/readers of the Mendeley system. Various combinations of students together form yet another 30% of the users/readers of Mendeley, while the ranks related to professorship use the system relatively little (in total some 18%). However, we have to keep in mind that this last group is the relatively smaller one in numbers, students are very early career, while Ph.D. and Postdoc ranks are in the middle of starting up a research career.

TABLE 17: OVERVIEW OF MENDELEY READER GROUPS ON FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH OUTPUTS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	CLOSED		OPEN	
Professor	30916	8%	10259,25	9%
Professor > Associate Professor	36663,25	10%	11937	11%
Lecturer > Senior Lecturer	7393	2%	2322	2%
Lecturer	13642,75	4%	4195,25	4%
Researcher	52468,75	14%	18230,25	16%

Librarian	6774,25	2%	2075,5	2%
Student > Postgraduate	27555,5	8%	9392,75	8%
Student > Ph. D. Student	55080,75	15%	18775,75	17%
Student > Doctoral Student	33377,25	9%	10606,25	9%
Student > Master	45307	12%	15170	14%
Student > Bachelor	32044,75	9%	11110,75	10%
Other	23648,75	6%	8203,75	7%
	364872		112019,3	

In Table 18, the publications forthcoming from the FP-7 funded research projects, mentioned in Mendeley, and distinguished by Closed and Open access mode, are presented. Nearly all publications in the study under the two types of scientific publishing are mentioned via Mendeley.

TABLE 18: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH OUTPUTS AS USED BY MENDELEY USERS/READERS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	59583,75	1126952,25	18,91	1,94	1,61	22%	6%	23%	85%
OPEN	20429,00	297190,50	14,55	1,81	1,39	21%	7%	25%	88%

In Table 19 the various types of scientific cooperation combined with the two types of scientific publishing. Due to the strong overlap of the overall analysis and the Mendeley based analysis, the analysis of the various types of scientific cooperation strongly resembles the overall analysis.

TABLE 19: OUTPUT AND IMPACT BY SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPE OF FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH OUTPUTS AS USED BY MENDELEY USERS/READERS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	SI	14686,75	243195,50	16,56	1,72	1,45	19%	8%	19%	83%
	NC	11181,00	193322,25	17,29	1,73	1,53	20%	6%	21%	87%
	IC	33716,00	690434,50	20,48	2,10	1,71	24%	5%	25%	86%
OPEN	SI	3926,75	55398,50	14,11	1,77	1,32	19%	10%	18%	87%
	NC	3649,75	48269,50	13,23	1,66	1,32	18%	8%	22%	89%
	IC	12852,50	193522,50	15,06	1,86	1,43	22%	6%	27%	88%

In Table 20 we present the distribution of the output over the various user/reader groups of Mendeley, over the two types of scientific publishing. What is striking is that most literature is used by the academic staff ranks that are

in the middle of their academic training, with impact levels that approach the levels of the whole set (which is understandable, as it is nearly one-on-one), in comparison with the literature used by the more senior academic staff rank (for whom we observe much smaller sets of publications sued, but with relatively higher impact levels attached to those publications). This suggests that the more senior, the more one is focused on a small set of the literature, but apparently the most prolific part of that.

TABLE 20: OUTPUT AND IMPACT BY MENDELEY USERS/READERS OF FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH OUTPUTS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
Closed									
Professor	30916,00	870563,75	28,16	2,72	1,99	32%	3%	20%	87%
Professor > Associate Professor	36663,25	941540,00	25,68	2,52	1,89	30%	3%	21%	86%
Lecturer > Senior Lecturer	7393,00	356533,00	48,23	4,28	2,54	43%	2%	16%	87%
Lecturer	13642,75	529581,00	38,82	3,71	2,33	41%	2%	17%	85%
Researcher	52468,75	1086606,50	20,71	2,08	1,68	24%	5%	22%	86%
Librarian	6774,25	234829,50	34,67	3,33	2,14	33%	4%	19%	84%
Student > Postgraduate	27555,50	823144,75	29,87	2,90	2,03	34%	3%	19%	86%
Student > Ph. D. Student	55080,75	1101632,25	20,00	2,04	1,66	23%	5%	23%	86%
Student > Doctoral Student	33377,25	900259,25	26,97	2,64	1,93	31%	3%	20%	86%
Student > Master	45307,00	1026252,25	22,65	2,27	1,76	26%	4%	21%	86%
Student > Bachelor	32044,75	890997,00	27,80	2,70	1,95	32%	3%	20%	86%
Other	23648,75	722729,00	30,56	2,93	2,07	34%	3%	19%	87%
Open									
Professor	10259,25	213563,50	20,82	2,49	1,61	30%	4%	22%	89%
Professor > Associate Professor	11937,00	230093,00	19,28	2,32	1,56	28%	4%	22%	89%
Lecturer > Senior Lecturer	2322,00	72225,25	31,10	3,55	1,82	39%	3%	18%	88%
Lecturer	4195,25	116302,75	27,72	3,30	1,76	37%	4%	18%	87%
Researcher	18230,25	282651,00	15,50	1,91	1,43	22%	6%	24%	89%
Librarian	2075,50	47326,25	22,80	2,73	1,57	28%	6%	22%	85%
Student > Postgraduate	9392,75	199008,50	21,19	2,54	1,59	30%	4%	21%	89%
Student > Ph. D. Student	18775,75	287571,00	15,32	1,90	1,42	22%	6%	24%	88%

Student > Doctoral Student	10606,25	209415,25	19,74	2,41	1,58	29%	4%	22%	89%
Student > Master	15170,00	257490,00	16,97	2,10	1,48	25%	5%	23%	88%
Student > Bachelor	11110,75	216435,25	19,48	2,37	1,55	28%	4%	22%	89%
Other	8203,75	172963,75	21,08	2,54	1,61	30%	4%	21%	88%

In table 21 we present the numbers of Altmetric.com social media types. This is a list of 13 different types, of which the top four is going to be taken in to consideration, given the somewhat larger numbers of social media hits, and thus making the analysis somewhat more robust, given the various analyses applied on these data.

TABLE 21: SOCIAL MEDIA MENTIONS OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS FORTHCOMING FROM FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	Overall	% CLOSED	% OPEN
twitter	247263	59%	41%
facebook	21133	56%	44%
news	20990	69%	31%
blog	13581	67%	33%
googleplus	7618	58%	42%
f1000	2393	77%	23%
reddit	1015	46%	54%
video	511	59%	41%
policy	395	65%	35%
peer_reviews	253	55%	45%
q_and_a	201	66%	34%
pinterest	52	65%	35%
linkedin	44	77%	23%

In Table 22 we show the division between Closed and Open access modes from the overall Altmetric.com system. It becomes clear that Closed access mode outputs do have a high impact ($mncs=3,29$), and these publications mentioned through social media do contribute strongly to the global scientific top literature. However, as the Open access mode outputs have high impact scores, albeit somewhat more modest as compared to the Closed access mode research outputs from FP-7 funded research projects.

TABLE 22: OUTPUT AND IMPACT OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS FORTHCOMING FROM FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS, BASED UPON ALTMETRIC.COM SOCIAL MEDIA MENTIONS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	P	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	18443,50	605209,00	32,81	3,22	2,33	36%	3%	19%	89%
OPEN	9950,25	180933,25	18,18	2,37	1,60	28%	6%	22%	89%

In Table 23 we present the division over the various types of scientific activity (SI, NC, and IC) for the two types of publishing types. In both publishing types, Closed and Open), we observe more or less similarly large numbers of publications resulting from either Closed (N=3753,25 for SI and NC=3373,25) or Open (N=1804,50 for SI and 1841,50 for NC), whereas the impact for the SI is higher as compared to the NC parts of these two types of scientific publishing. This is different as compared to the overall outcomes of the study, where the impacts related to these two types are of more or less similar level.

TABLE 23: OUTPUT AND IMPACT BY SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION TYPE OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS FORTHCOMING FROM FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS, BASED UPON SOCIAL MEDIA MENTIONS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov	
CLOSED	SI	3753,25	113825,00	30,33	2,94	2,05	32%	4%	14%	88%
	NC	3373,25	96220,25	28,52	2,72	2,16	32%	3%	16%	90%
	IC	11317,00	395163,75	34,92	3,47	2,48	38%	3%	21%	89%
OPEN	SI	1804,50	33330,25	18,47	2,43	1,53	25%	7%	15%	89%
	NC	1841,50	28496,75	15,47	2,06	1,50	23%	6%	19%	90%
	IC	6304,25	119106,25	18,89	2,44	1,65	30%	5%	24%	89%

In Table 24 we show the output and impact scores of the various social media types. First we show the overall outcome, for the whole Altmetric.com system, including all types described in Table 21. A general observation is that throughout this analysis, the Closed access mode published outputs do have higher impacts when mentioned in social media, as compared to the Open access mode published research outputs. However, there is some differentiation here, as the outputs mentioned by Twitter do resemble the overall picture for Altmetric.com, due to its' volume, but when focusing on Facebook mentioned research outputs from FP-7 funded research projects, we observe increasing impact scores for these publications, both in the Closed as well as the Open access modes published outputs. In all instances, the number of Closed access mode published outputs is roughly twice as many as the Open access modes published outputs, in terms of numbers of publications mentioned. The impact of the

research outputs mentioned in social media is very high, and the outputs mentioned clearly belong to the global top literature in the fields to which they belong.

TABLE 24: SOCIAL MEDIA MENTIONS OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS FORTHCOMING FROM FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS, FOR TWO ACCESS MODES IN 2008-2014/2017

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
Altmetrics	CLOSED	18443,50	605209,00	32,81	3,22	2,33	36%	3%	19%	89%
	OPEN	9950,25	180933,25	18,18	2,37	1,60	28%	6%	22%	89%
Twitter	CLOSED	15363,00	493197,75	32,10	3,28	2,39	36%	3%	19%	89%
	OPEN	8801,50	154411,25	17,54	2,39	1,61	27%	6%	22%	89%
Facebook	CLOSED	3787,25	195290,00	51,57	5,24	3,36	49%	2%	17%	90%
	OPEN	2326,50	52572,00	22,60	3,26	1,90	36%	4%	20%	88%
News	CLOSED	2251,25	166857,00	74,12	7,66	4,77	63%	1%	15%	90%
	OPEN	1041,50	32836,25	31,53	4,36	2,74	48%	2%	19%	89%
Blogs	CLOSED	2951,25	208298,00	70,58	6,59	4,05	59%	1%	15%	89%
	OPEN	1533,75	55079,00	35,91	4,28	2,25	44%	2%	18%	87%

In Figures 42-44 we display the impact levels attached to various outputs under Closed and Open format. For reasons of comparison, we show the overall situation in the top of the graphs for all publications forthcoming from the FP-7 funded research projects, under these two types. In Figure 42 we show the mncs values related to the overall and different social media types mentioning FP-7 funded research projects outputs. For Facebook mentions, News and Blogs, the mncs of the Open share of the outputs is around or above the value 3 for mncs, while for the Closed part of the output mentioned through social media we observe that in all instances.

FIGURE 42 COMPARING NORMALIZED IMPACT SCORES (MNCs) FOR OUTPUTS FOR FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS MENTIONED BY SOCIAL MEDIA SOURCES FOR TWO ACCESS MODES, 2008-2015/2016.

The journals in which these publications appeared do have high impact levels, as the overall altmetric.com mentioned research outputs in Closed format do display mncs levels of 2 or higher, while we observe this only for the Open access mode published outputs mentioned through news and Blogs. In Figure 44, the visibility among the top of the global scientific literature is presented, and we clearly observe that the outputs mentioned through social media do belong to the most visible research outputs of global science.

Interesting question is of course to what extent is the one the result of the other, or vice versa, in other words, do these publications get high numbers of social media mentions, as they are high quality research papers, and therefore are mentioned, or do these research papers get a high visibility through social media attention, and then get a high citation attention and consequently, high impact score ?

FIGURE 43 COMPARING NORMALIZED JOURNAL IMPACT SCORES (MNJS) FOR OUTPUTS FOR FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS MENTIONED BY SOCIAL MEDIA SOURCES FOR TWO ACCESS MODES, 2008-2015/2016.

FIGURE 44 COMPARING TOP 10% SCORES FOR OUTPUTS FOR FP-7 FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS MENTIONED BY SOCIAL MEDIA SOURCES FOR TWO ACCESS MODES, 2008-2015/2016.

A first conclusion based on the analysis of Mendeley usage of outputs of FP-7 funded research projects is of course the strong focus of particularly young research staff on these outputs. Both in the Open as the Closed realm of outputs forthcoming from FP-7 research projects, the PhD's and Postdoc population together form some 25% of the users/readers of these publications. If we add students to this, we find over 50% of the usage/readerships stems from young people. This strong focus by these young people in the research system through these internet facilities on research outputs are characteristic for new forms of usage of scientific knowledge, and new forms of scientific communication. Next to this fact that young researchers tend to get their hands more often around research papers, to get to know the literature, there is clearly also the attractiveness of new internet-based methodologies and instruments such as Mendeley. Remarkably enough, whenever the somewhat older academic staff use Mendeley, the impact of the used research output is somewhat higher as compared to the outputs used by the younger academic staff, which is indicative of a higher degree of selectivity.

When observing the social media usage or mentioning of research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects, we notice a very strong presence of Twitter as the main form of social media attention (with tenfold as many Tweets as the next largest source of social media attention, namely Facebook). A general conclusion of the social media analysis is that in general, the research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects that are mentioned do get higher citation scores as compared to the overall impact scores, on both Closed as well as Open access format outputs. So the questions arises what is triggering what, is high impact triggering intensive mentioning in social media, or is intensive mentioning triggering a high impact? Given the state of affairs in research on social media analysis, this is for now an open question.

12 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The main research question is quite interesting and important for open access and also in the broader context of open science. Below we will give a list of major conclusions of the study:

- The study conducted showed us that for the monitoring of open access publishing having stable and reliable datasets on open access output is crucial. In that respect, the most used methods around now to monitor and measure open access publishing are based on methods that do not qualify as such.
- Within all constraints of this study, both such as not having access to the full set of FP-7 publications (OA and no-OA) and the selection of only FP-7 funded research projects, in the WoS world, we can still conclude that open access monitoring is feasible if reliable datasets are available.
- The study shows that in young EU MS, as well as some southern EU MS, open access publishing has taken off differently as compared to the vested scientific powerhouses of north Western Europe. We clearly see that in some of the countries in the EU, open access publishing has a higher impact as compared to the non-open access published outputs.
- At the same time, and related to the previous issues, we notice that in these countries, but not limited to those countries alone, the universities of technology and the engineering domain as a whole seems to be more engaged in open access publishing, given the shares of open access outputs among their total outputs resulting from FP-7 outputs, and the impact scores related to the open access published outputs.
- Regarding the main research question, What are the effects of publishing FP-7 publications as Open Access?, the project revealed a number of complex challenges related to establishing a reliable bibliographic dataset. Though many of these challenges remain unresolved, they are outlined in the report for consideration in future research on the topic.

The study of Open Access in general, and this study in particular, raises a number of important questions. Keep in mind that the outcome of this analysis does not address FP7 as a whole, as the OpenAIRE data is aggregated from open access repositories throughout Europe. As such, it is not possible to determine what portion of all FP7 output that our dataset represents (see Data and Limitations section above for details), from the perspective of research assessment, and consequently the production of reliable indicators on both the output and the impact dimension. One of these questions is related to the principles and standards to which analysis of output and impact of open access publishing should be held against. An important issue relates, particularly in the light of the various studies on open access publishing, to the possibility to reproduce the outcomes of a current day analysis in the (near) future. This seems to be an obvious requirement, but we all know now that replication and reproducibility are not always that easy to guarantee. Over the most recent period, these issues are in the middle of debates, both in academic, in policy as well as in wider societal circles. However, the issue of reproducibility is not a single, stand-alone aspect. It is closely related to the issue of the principles on which indicators of openness could or should be based upon. As stated above, the various analyses conducted in our institute on open access, and the challenges

offered by the Web of Science database to distinguish Open Access publications, sparked an ambition to create an in-house database of Open Access publications. This made us think about the requirements for such a development. Given the fact that reproducibility is of utmost importance, in particular in the light of being able to inform science policy with metrics on Open Access, some methods of data collection were dropped. One of such methods was random sampling.

Although very appealing given the large quantity of information available to harvest, the problem with random sampling is that it is impossible to reproduce exactly what you did the previous time. So that made us think of other methods that would be more comprehensive and focused on full populations of publications. This conclusion has consequences for the data sources that can be used for creating an environment to conduct reproducible analyses on openness in scientific publishing, as not all available data sources are set-up according to guidelines in the exact same manner. As core principle of creating an environment to conduct metric analyses on open access, from the perspective of replicability, we choose for legality and sustainability. This means that we discarded a number of data sources for harvesting openness, to be linked to WoS.

The two most prolific sources that were discarded are ResearchGate and SciHub. Both systems contain many publications that were made openly available by (some of) their authors, although these publications officially belong behind a paywall. It is the combination of illegality and/sustainability (being cut off for data collection either due to getting penalized legally, or disappearing behind a paywall, in case either of the two systems is incorporated into one of the major actors in the registration of scientific outputs). So therefore we have started an experiment, to collect information on openness. OpenAIRE information is part of that experiment, as we currently consider the OpenAIRE system as a system that is publicly available, that harvests in a legal manner from publicly available sources such as repositories as well as from systems as DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) that will highly likely not disappear behind a paywall. Preliminary results have shown very relevant results and there are high stakes of achieving relevant outcomes through this development.

In this study we have focused on whether and to what extent research publications forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects, and registered as such, in both Closed and Open access format, were cited within either scientific literature, patents, or mentioned in social media. The study covers a period of 2008-2015/2016 and is based upon the WoS bibliometric database within CWTS, which covers mostly journal literature. As such, the main focus of the study is on the scientific disciplines best covered by the WoS, in which the main standard way of communication is formed by journal literature, including the natural and life sciences, biomedicine, the engineering sciences, and to a smaller extent those social sciences in which journal publishing is also important. This does not mean that the other social sciences, the humanities and law are intentionally ignored simply because the database does not cover their main ways of communication, such as books, chapters, and non-English journal literature, advanced bibliometric analysis does not work here. This means that we cannot say anything of those domains in the study, except for the parts of the outputs from the FP-7 funded research projects that is published in journals processed for the WoS. As indicated in the introductory parts of this report, we have managed to link a substantial part of the registered

outputs from the FP-7 funded research projects to the WoS database, however, for that part where we did not succeed in linking up to the WoS, we probably have a relatively large quantity of outputs from SSH projects.

In the current study we have focused on three different aspects of measuring impact of research outputs forthcoming from FP-7 funded research projects. The first is focusing on the academic research performance, i.e., on academic impact, while the other two elements of the study focus on what is nowadays considered as part of the societal impact, namely the economic impact dimension and the societal impact dimension. The first part is based upon a classical bibliometric approach on the journal publications registered as outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects, while the second centers around the interlinkage between science and technology, in the sense that research papers are cited within the content of patents indicates that science is important for technological development. And finally, we focus on the ways social media communication focuses on research outputs from FP-7 funded research projects, as that tells us about the way science is interpreted and becomes meaningful from a wider societal perspective. In both of these latter two approaches, we stayed close to the research outputs from the funded projects, that is, we focused on the journal publications, and their position in the world of journal literature. An important reason for that is that both in the world of patent citation analysis as well as in the world of social media attention analysis, the issue of comparison or normalization is not yet resolved. This means that it is impossible to make comparisons between the number of hits in a social media analysis across countries and/or fields, or likewise, to assess the way journal publications are cited by patents. Therefore, we went back to the journal publications used in the two societally oriented impact dimensions, in order to assess the impacts these publications had in the world of science, in order to be able to at least assess their position within that scientific environment.

The study has clearly shown that the academic performance analysis of the outcomes of FP-7 funded research projects do stand out. The impact levels are high, also for the Open access format outputs. In terms of comparison with regular bibliometric analysis, these publications follow the regular outcomes: international cooperation rewards as the highest impact levels are found for publications that result from international cooperation, both in the Closed as the Open realm. Next, we observe that the scientifically larger European countries do stand out in this analysis as well, both in output and in impact scores. However, we also found some very intriguing new features, which tell us that the 'younger' EU Member States MS do have relatively high impact scores on their Open access format research outputs, and that this is especially visible for some 'older' EU MS in southern Europe (Greece is a clear example of this, where the Open access output is relatively large, but also combined with a high impact score). Open access seems to have landed somewhat more among institutions with a focus on technology and engineering sciences, as compared to the more classical oriented institutions, and again, and perhaps not surprisingly, this is very well visible for the younger EU MS and those in southern Europe.

The study clearly shows that the research from the FP-7 funded research projects do generate high impact scores across most disciplines, and that the research particularly in the STM domains is very well represented by this study (see above). However, the coverage of the WoS for even the social sciences and humanities is somewhat higher in

this set of publications as compared to a national selection of outputs, which indicates that the researchers from SSH funded through the FP-7 apparently have a somewhat stronger focus on journal publishing.

The study of patent citations to journal literature from FP-7 funded research shows that there is a clear preference for science of a certain nature, namely a strong orientation towards basic research. The higher numbers of cited scientific literature in the closed format suggest at least that in the more fundamental areas, in particular in biomedicine, openness is not as far progressed as for example in the engineering fields. The interesting part is here that the impact of those publications cited by patents do belong to the top scientific journal literature in their respective field(s).

The analysis of social media attention made clear that this can be a fruitful way of adding to our understanding of the broader impacts of academic research. The analysis showed that Closed and Open access outputs from FP-7 funded research projects received higher impact scores as compared to the overall impacts of these research outputs from an academic impact perspective. The increasing research intensity around social media analysis indicates that more research is done on the topic, but also that more is needed to solve a number of existing problems with this type of analysis (which actually is far larger than only the research output dimension, this type of altmetrics analysis expands to the realm of open data, open review, etc.).

In 2014, we conducted a study on the situation around openness in the Dutch science system, in an international comparative way. In that study, the questions were: to what extent is the research output from Dutch academics already available through open access, and what are the trends associated with open access publishing. We compared Dutch national output covered in the WoS database with the outputs of both Switzerland and Denmark, as more or less comparable countries for the Netherlands (van Leeuwen, 2014; van Leeuwen et al, 2015). From this study we learned that Open Access publishing is growing in these countries, and becomes increasingly important, as can be found in the impact scores related to the growing output, with increasing impact scores for the OA outputs. However, as far as we can conclude from data retrieved from the WoS database, that is, based upon journal communication patterns, the impact scores related to the OA shares of the outputs of these three countries remains at a somewhat low(er) level, and is not approaching the country overall impact scores for the three countries under study. In the current study we focused not on the total national research output (as can bibliometrically be measured through WoS journal literature), but on the part of the country's output that results from the successful applicants of EU-funding under the FP-7 framework. As this is not a random selection of researchers (FP7 grantees), the impact scores in the study exceed the overall national impact scores observed for these countries. Next, we can also see that the Open access portion of the outputs resulting from FP-7 funded research projects exceeds the national impact scores. This indicates two things. First, the current study is focused on a part of Europe's research community that is successful in applying for EC grants, and also in the results from their research as their research papers belong to the top of their field(s). Second, the focus on Open access output is relatively well developed among this group of researchers as compared to a national level analysis of open access, which is shown by

relative higher number of papers published as Open access, and the impact levels related to this Open access output.

This studies mentioned in the previous paragraph (van Leeuwen, 2014, van Leeuwen et al, 2015) made very clear that the bibliometric analysis of open access in the research assessment context is quite complex, and as most bibliometric systems do not yet have fully operational and accessible labels for open access, let alone the various types, there are many challenges. At the moment it is still not possible to distinguish within the systems between Gold OA, Green OA, and hybrid OA. For example, in WoS, only the desktop version presently labels open access publications (thus representing Gold OA), which makes collecting this information quite involved and time consuming, and thus quite costly. Within CWTS we are working on adding this metadata to our internal WoS database, based on a variety of data sources. In this study we worked with the labels added in the OpenAIRE platform, for which we followed the basic rule that the applied labels were considered valid of the open access state of publications.

In the study, no data on authors were supplied. However, based upon the internal databases at CWTS we could have worked on lower levels on analysis, for example projects and or groups. This should always be considered as proxies of reality, as we do not know exactly who worked on the projects funded under the FP-7 framework. However, that might get into conflicting situation with the privacy regulations and legislation in some of the EU MS. Therefore, it was decided to refrain from analysis on the level below that of institutions.

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APPENDIXES

14 Appendix 1: OVERVIEW IN PERCENTAGES OF THE CONCORDANCE OF document types in OpenAIRE and WoS related to FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015

WoS
Classificatio

OpenAIRE classification	Article	Review	Editorial Material	Letter	Correction	Meeting Abstract	New Item	Reprint	Hardware Review	Software Review
Article	93%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Review	0%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Unknown/Other	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

14 Appendix 2: Numbers of publications per cooperation types across output formats, 2008-2015

n_authors	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
CLOSED / IC	156	931	2914	5736	8567	11731	4956	125
CLOSED / NC	54	334	1023	1899	2874	3874	1589	61
CLOSED / SI	110	544	1458	2673	3740	4973	2077	44
EMBARGO / IC				3	10	13	36	34
EMBARGO / NC			1	1	7	7	14	17
EMBARGO / SI					6	5	18	8
OPEN / IC	31	257	702	1527	2534	3704	3421	1264
OPEN / NC	11	75	190	376	708	1049	986	399
OPEN / SI	16	123	236	442	767	1093	1107	417
RESTRICTED / IC	6	10	27	55	42	40	55	39
RESTRICTED / NC	1	4	14	11	19	13	15	9
RESTRICTED / SI	1	5	9	17	22	12	23	15
UNKNOWN / IC			1		4	4	6	22
UNKNOWN / NC						1	4	4

14 Appendix 3a: Numbers of publications/number of countries, Closed access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015

n_countries	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	164	877	2481	4571	6612	8845	3665	105
2	95	576	1759	3412	4925	6670	2800	69
3	39	225	684	1373	2094	2828	1167	24
4	8	75	248	478	747	1071	468	10
5	7	24	82	193	303	443	188	8
6	2	12	52	81	147	212	97	5
7	1	7	20	54	100	160	50	6
8	1	3	16	33	59	80	58	1
9	2	4	12	23	46	68	31	2
10		2	8	12	37	54	32	
11-20	1	4	31	73	95	118	62	0
>21	0	0	2	5	16	29	4	0

Appendix 3B: Numbers of publications/number of countries, Open access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015

n_countries	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	27	198	426	818	1474	2142	2093	816
2	18	145	377	822	1326	1908	1725	666
3	10	68	186	393	642	961	890	329
4		23	77	148	289	395	359	139
5	3	7	26	65	105	169	157	46
6		3	13	29	58	82	91	27
7		3	7	19	30	59	59	11
8		2	5	15	21	34	33	14
9		2	5	14	16	24	23	6
10		1	1	7	7	18	22	3
11-20	0	3	5	12	23	36	35	16
>21	0	0	0	3	18	18	27	7

14 Appendix 4a: Numbers of publications/number of authors, Closed access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015

n_authors	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	14	54	164	280	424	505	207	3
2	43	235	671	1170	1623	2212	852	14
3	68	310	916	1599	2368	3296	1313	30
4	51	289	815	1634	2326	3198	1305	38
5	37	225	632	1279	1855	2679	1104	35
6	27	160	504	1018	1505	1925	864	24
7	12	131	440	764	1181	1538	664	16
8	19	97	290	577	874	1184	511	11
9	11	79	222	461	689	869	370	16
10	7	62	166	320	507	691	298	10
11	8	40	131	266	389	499	194	3
12	7	26	93	191	298	333	176	4
13	2	17	67	137	207	265	113	1
14	1	13	60	125	148	234	97	2
15	4	17	34	80	116	152	69	5
16	1	8	26	55	76	122	48	2
17	3	6	18	46	70	105	48	1
18	1	5	14	33	52	96	49	1
19		5	18	22	45	71	42	
20	1	2	5	24	38	45	15	1
>21	3	28	109	227	390	559	283	13

14 Appendix 4b: Numbers of publications/number of authors, Open access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015

n_authors	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	2	24	42	77	125	146	152	52
2	10	71	158	266	475	617	520	206
3	11	95	208	398	656	893	791	293
4	11	76	189	377	624	857	789	260
5	6	50	120	254	438	645	648	236
6	4	32	87	211	321	513	517	195
7	4	26	58	134	286	443	405	167
8		25	43	128	221	370	340	120
9	1	10	48	104	171	258	252	100
10		10	35	75	148	215	208	82
11	3	12	34	68	104	170	166	60
12	1	4	18	42	95	141	106	63
13		1	12	30	54	77	104	37
14		1	16	33	45	78	65	34
15		1	3	22	37	51	58	27
16			4	15	18	50	56	18
17		2	7	15	15	44	49	16
18		1	5	4	20	36	26	23
19	2	1	5	8	15	25	23	4
20		2	3	9	14	21	22	6
>20	3	11	33	75	127	196	217	81

14 Appendix 5a: Output and impact of countries, Closed access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
ALBANIA	7,00	75,00	10,71	1,69	1,52	29%	0%	43%	81%
ALGERIA	54,00	537,00	9,94	1,36	1,40	16%	9%	33%	80%
ARGENTINA	338,00	5435,00	16,08	1,65	1,60	21%	6%	30%	85%
ARMENIA	102,00	1139,00	11,17	1,37	1,08	13%	11%	38%	84%
AUSTRALIA	1581,25	41874,00	26,48	2,79	2,03	32%	3%	32%	88%
AUSTRIA	2393,50	54452,00	22,75	2,30	1,78	26%	6%	28%	84%
AZERBAIJAN	13,00	370,00	28,46	3,88	1,16	41%	8%	32%	80%
BAHRAIN	2,00	49,00	24,50	4,09	1,85	50%	0%	21%	82%
BANGLADESH	15,00	151,00	10,07	1,96	1,34	20%	0%	39%	76%
BARBADOS	2,00	14,00	7,00	0,51	1,87	0%	0%	44%	86%
BELGIUM	4175,25	87359,00	20,92	2,03	1,63	23%	6%	26%	86%
BELIZE	1,00	79,00	79,00	22,21	20,10	100%	0%	26%	69%
BELORUSSIA	152,00	1880,00	12,37	1,31	1,22	14%	12%	44%	86%
BENIN	18,00	170,00	9,44	0,98	1,36	10%	11%	40%	86%
BERMUDA	4,00	43,00	10,75	1,32	2,29	18%	0%	31%	91%
BOLIVIA	21,00	279,00	13,29	1,74	1,47	28%	0%	31%	69%
BOSNIA & HERCEGOVINA	6,00	26,00	4,33	0,91	1,00	8%	0%	28%	55%
BRAZIL	623,00	13103,00	21,03	2,25	1,60	22%	7%	27%	85%
BRUNEI	2,00	8,00	4,00	0,51	0,80	0%	0%	38%	87%
BULGARIA	230,00	3559,00	15,47	1,63	1,28	16%	9%	33%	81%
BURKINA FASO	19,00	129,00	6,79	0,70	1,05	6%	11%	38%	82%
CAMBODIA	6,00	121,00	20,17	2,19	2,21	17%	0%	22%	82%
CAMEROON	21,00	372,00	17,71	1,98	1,77	31%	0%	35%	88%
CANADA	1634,50	51209,50	31,33	2,99	2,03	34%	3%	29%	87%
CAPE VERDE	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,75	0,58	0%	0%	67%	50%
CENT AFR REPubL	1,00	154,00	154,00	12,53	3,06	100%	0%	22%	97%
CHAD	1,00	13,00	13,00	0,95	0,83	0%	0%	55%	83%
CHILE	454,00	8253,00	18,18	1,92	1,44	20%	6%	41%	87%
COLOMBIA	111,00	1436,00	12,94	1,57	1,26	18%	6%	32%	77%
CONGO	5,00	41,00	8,20	0,88	1,03	20%	40%	37%	93%
COSTA RICA	9,00	83,00	9,22	1,27	1,32	33%	11%	34%	84%
CROATIA	275,00	6681,00	24,29	1,83	1,67	19%	10%	35%	86%
CUBA	33,00	294,00	8,91	1,27	1,38	23%	3%	23%	88%
CYPRUS	193,00	2228,00	11,54	1,48	1,39	17%	5%	25%	74%

Impact of Open Access published research PUBLIC

CZECH REPUBLIC	1219,00	19272,00	15,81	1,63	1,51	18%	7%	29%	86%
DEM REPUBL CONGO	7,00	310,00	44,29	3,82	5,89	29%	0%	24%	89%
DENMARK	2546,75	63710,25	25,02	2,34	1,79	25%	5%	28%	87%
DJIBOUTI	1,00	34,00	34,00	6,94	1,57	100%	0%	6%	73%
DOMINICAN REPUBLIC	1,00	2,00	2,00	0,25	0,69	0%	0%	50%	50%
ECUADOR	20,00	423,00	21,15	2,78	2,25	30%	0%	24%	64%
EGYPT	108,00	2165,00	20,05	1,95	1,68	20%	6%	23%	87%
ESTONIA	318,25	10699,25	33,62	2,72	1,93	35%	5%	30%	85%
ETHIOPIA	14,00	430,00	30,71	2,25	1,51	14%	0%	21%	84%
FINLAND	2166,75	47054,25	21,72	2,00	1,61	22%	7%	29%	86%
FR POLYNESIA	2,00	14,00	7,00	0,69	1,07	0%	0%	73%	79%
FRANCE	11176,25	241540,25	21,61	2,16	1,73	25%	6%	26%	87%
FRENCH GUYANA	2,00	13,00	6,50	0,60	0,73	0%	0%	24%	86%
GABON	7,00	309,00	44,14	3,84	1,65	43%	0%	23%	88%
GAMBIA	9,00	194,00	21,56	1,89	2,50	35%	0%	41%	94%
GERMANY	13751,50	301153,00	21,90	2,19	1,76	25%	5%	26%	87%
GHANA	17,00	614,00	36,12	3,13	2,13	40%	12%	23%	87%
GREAT BRITAIN	13454,00	309242,75	22,99	2,35	1,79	26%	5%	24%	85%
GREECE	2545,25	36047,25	14,16	1,55	1,37	18%	8%	28%	81%
GREENLAND	38,00	638,00	16,79	1,78	1,81	20%	0%	36%	84%
GRENADA	0,25	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,49	0%	100%	100%	100%
GUADELOUPE	2,00	13,00	6,50	0,83	0,77	0%	0%	24%	80%
GUATEMALA	1,00	10,00	10,00	1,10	1,23	0%	0%	0%	83%
GUINEA	5,00	73,00	14,60	1,39	1,02	20%	0%	44%	71%
GUINEA BISSAU	17,00	101,00	5,94	0,63	2,02	10%	18%	47%	91%
GUYANA	1,00	8,00	8,00	1,48	1,12	0%	0%	11%	62%
HONDURAS	1,00	10,00	10,00	1,10	1,23	0%	0%	0%	83%
HUNGARY	1207,25	17735,50	14,69	1,56	1,27	18%	9%	29%	87%
ICELAND	214,25	12148,50	56,70	4,02	3,01	44%	2%	32%	88%
INDIA	533,00	10122,00	18,99	2,00	1,66	18%	6%	31%	86%
INDONESIA	24,00	368,00	15,33	1,86	1,30	27%	4%	29%	83%
IRAN	145,00	2431,00	16,77	1,75	1,44	16%	8%	30%	85%
IRAQ	5,00	51,00	10,20	0,82	1,19	20%	0%	33%	90%
IRELAND	1205,00	31024,00	25,75	2,48	1,78	26%	6%	25%	86%
ISRAEL	1781,50	41539,75	23,32	2,24	1,94	27%	7%	22%	87%
ITALY	10962,00	201978,00	18,43	1,92	1,55	21%	7%	27%	84%
IVORY COAST	6,00	67,00	11,17	0,84	1,27	2%	17%	25%	89%
JAMAICA	1,00	38,00	38,00	4,16	2,90	100%	0%	14%	65%
JAPAN	1413,00	39439,00	27,91	2,82	2,08	28%	6%	28%	88%
JORDAN	14,00	153,00	10,93	1,29	1,38	20%	14%	22%	74%

PUBLIC

KAZACHSTAN	23,00	181,00	7,87	0,82	1,22	11%	13%	27%	81%
KENYA	29,00	532,00	18,34	2,79	2,50	25%	0%	31%	77%
KUWAIT	12,00	355,00	29,58	3,90	2,51	58%	0%	22%	84%
LAOS	2,00	5,00	2,50	0,42	1,09	0%	0%	29%	73%
LATVIA	91,00	1001,00	11,00	1,19	1,14	15%	12%	39%	84%
LEBANON	23,00	559,00	24,30	2,70	1,94	32%	13%	20%	74%
LIBYA	4,00	44,00	11,00	2,03	1,68	25%	25%	15%	87%
LIECHTENSTEIN	8,00	52,00	6,50	0,87	0,94	6%	13%	35%	80%
LITHUANIA	193,25	2092,00	10,83	1,32	1,04	14%	9%	43%	86%
LUXEMBOURG	94,00	1445,00	15,37	1,99	1,50	26%	7%	29%	80%
MACEDONIA	34,00	398,00	11,71	1,54	1,40	18%	9%	23%	72%
MADAGASCAR	3,00	37,00	12,33	3,01	2,61	42%	0%	30%	78%
MALAWI	3,00	57,00	19,00	2,53	1,70	52%	0%	28%	80%
MALAYSIA	66,00	1056,00	16,00	1,62	1,51	18%	5%	48%	83%
MALI	8,00	63,00	7,88	0,83	1,03	2%	0%	28%	61%
MALTA	22,00	418,00	19,00	1,90	1,51	24%	5%	28%	73%
MARTINIQUE	2,00	55,00	27,50	1,63	1,43	11%	0%	28%	84%
MAURITANIA	5,00	91,00	18,20	2,55	1,13	40%	0%	42%	68%
MAURITIUS	5,00	154,00	30,80	4,44	1,99	30%	20%	43%	84%
MEXICO	286,00	5533,00	19,35	1,91	1,48	20%	9%	28%	85%
MOLDAVIA	28,00	194,00	6,93	0,82	0,85	13%	11%	36%	84%
MONACO	21,00	588,00	28,00	3,15	1,72	55%	0%	24%	85%
MONGOL PEO REP	1,00	31,00	31,00	3,86	0,96	100%	0%	44%	89%
MONTENEGRO	7,00	39,00	5,57	0,84	0,72	14%	14%	42%	72%
MOROCCO	79,00	1415,00	17,91	2,46	1,67	29%	13%	31%	80%
MOZAMBIQUE	7,00	47,00	6,71	0,63	1,38	0%	0%	36%	82%
NAMIBIA	6,00	135,00	22,50	2,93	1,35	17%	0%	31%	89%
NEPAL	12,00	347,00	28,92	3,02	1,35	33%	0%	32%	88%
NETHERLANDS	6459,75	157619,50	24,40	2,34	1,84	28%	4%	26%	87%
NEW CALEDONIA	7,00	34,00	4,86	1,04	1,22	14%	0%	46%	81%
NEW ZEALAND	265,00	6242,00	23,55	2,46	1,93	25%	7%	31%	86%
NIGER	2,00	12,00	6,00	0,44	0,62	0%	50%	25%	90%
NIGERIA	14,00	275,00	19,64	2,04	2,05	30%	7%	29%	86%
NORTH KOREA	4,00	24,00	6,00	1,11	1,21	0%	0%	23%	90%
NORWAY	1268,25	29508,50	23,27	2,49	1,75	27%	6%	30%	82%
OMAN	11,00	422,00	38,36	3,60	2,38	42%	0%	22%	84%
PAKISTAN	55,00	1550,00	28,18	2,39	1,81	26%	11%	32%	85%
PANAMA	9,00	331,00	36,78	3,30	1,74	33%	11%	24%	80%
PAPUA N GUINEA	1,00	12,00	12,00	0,95	1,38	0%	0%	29%	96%
PARAGUAY	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,20	1,02	0%	0%	0%	32%

PEOPLES R CHINA	2130,25	46062,00	21,62	2,35	1,71	25%	7%	25%	85%
PERU	30,00	938,00	31,27	3,54	2,30	33%	3%	25%	74%
PHILIPPINES	14,00	398,00	28,43	3,26	2,42	42%	7%	37%	83%
POLAND	1842,25	23489,25	12,75	1,39	1,28	15%	9%	37%	85%
PORTUGAL	1741,25	25690,25	14,75	1,66	1,42	19%	8%	30%	84%
QATAR	68,00	1433,00	21,07	2,61	2,01	25%	13%	34%	82%
REP OF GEORGIA	65,00	744,00	11,45	1,52	1,10	14%	20%	35%	83%
REUNION	11,00	1071,00	97,36	5,85	1,11	10%	0%	9%	85%
ROMANIA	477,00	5546,00	11,63	1,48	1,21	17%	10%	32%	80%
RUSSIA	1574,25	21103,75	13,41	1,44	1,27	15%	12%	33%	85%
SAUDI ARABIA	207,00	5721,00	27,64	3,38	2,36	33%	3%	25%	86%
SENEGAL	11,00	93,00	8,45	0,96	0,97	9%	0%	47%	74%
SERBIA	296,00	3403,00	11,50	1,40	1,23	13%	10%	25%	82%
SEYCHELLES	3,00	19,00	6,33	1,06	0,90	0%	0%	39%	71%
SINGAPORE	292,25	17872,00	61,15	5,58	3,00	39%	4%	21%	87%
SLOVAKIA	303,00	3893,00	12,85	1,39	1,21	14%	8%	31%	86%
SLOVENIA	493,00	7588,00	15,39	1,62	1,50	19%	8%	31%	84%
SOUTH AFRICA	409,00	8657,00	21,17	2,35	1,66	28%	6%	32%	83%
SOUTH KOREA	559,25	16055,25	28,71	3,02	1,92	24%	8%	27%	88%
SPAIN	9185,25	175279,50	19,08	1,96	1,62	22%	7%	26%	85%
SRI LANKA	11,00	245,00	22,27	2,90	1,90	27%	0%	33%	79%
SUDAN	4,00	199,00	49,75	6,48	1,10	50%	0%	19%	83%
SURINAM	1,00	25,00	25,00	3,93	1,35	100%	0%	17%	70%
SWEDEN	3941,00	86550,75	21,96	2,10	1,72	24%	5%	27%	87%
SWITZERLAND	5439,25	153771,00	28,27	2,79	1,88	29%	5%	22%	86%
SYRIA	12,00	89,00	7,42	1,11	1,34	18%	17%	34%	82%
TAIWAN	205,00	8683,00	42,36	3,52	1,74	29%	3%	25%	87%
TAJKISTAN	1,00	13,00	13,00	1,50	0,95	0%	0%	38%	70%
TANZANIA	19,00	289,00	15,21	1,79	1,03	26%	0%	29%	87%
THAILAND	106,00	2800,00	26,42	2,33	2,14	28%	6%	34%	87%
TOGO	2,00	4,00	2,00	0,16	0,88	0%	50%	33%	99%
TRINIDAD & TOBAGO	5,00	49,00	9,80	1,09	1,31	20%	20%	28%	78%
TUNISIA	66,00	1145,00	17,35	1,81	1,63	21%	9%	29%	81%
TURKEY	547,25	8833,00	16,14	1,90	1,43	21%	11%	27%	78%
TURKMENISTAN	1,00	13,00	13,00	2,04	1,69	0%	0%	41%	63%
U ARAB EMIRATES	44,00	637,00	14,48	1,99	2,64	25%	2%	28%	84%
UGANDA	27,00	430,00	15,93	1,64	1,69	15%	7%	28%	81%
UKRAINE	374,00	3751,00	10,03	1,22	1,15	12%	14%	34%	83%
URUGUAY	55,00	1086,00	19,75	1,79	1,33	22%	5%	23%	88%
USA	10076,75	285312,75	28,31	2,76	2,03	31%	4%	24%	88%

PUBLIC

UZBEKISTAN	12,00	101,00	8,42	0,94	0,97	8%	8%	32%	76%
VANUATU	2,00	22,00	11,00	1,87	1,18	33%	0%	31%	80%
VATICAN	2,00	4,00	2,00	0,16	1,04	0%	0%	64%	92%
VENEZUELA	33,00	1015,00	30,76	3,67	2,19	36%	3%	25%	88%
VIETNAM	43,00	446,00	10,37	1,55	1,13	12%	21%	24%	80%
ZAMBIA	1,00	12,00	12,00	5,71	3,95	100%	0%	8%	72%
ZIMBABWE	7,00	166,00	23,71	2,20	2,69	29%	0%	21%	78%

14 Appendix 5b: Output and impact of countries, Open access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015/2016

	p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
ALBANIA	3,00	22,00	7,33	0,83	1,58	0%	0%	49%	78%
ALGERIA	12,00	126,00	10,50	1,72	1,60	27%	8%	43%	89%
ARGENTINA	180,50	2806,75	15,55	2,25	1,43	28%	7%	32%	85%
ARMENIA	100,00	1636,00	16,36	2,40	1,21	31%	6%	36%	82%
AUSTRALIA	839,25	15408,75	18,36	2,26	1,55	27%	5%	34%	87%
AUSTRIA	1033,50	17107,25	16,55	2,08	1,61	26%	7%	28%	86%
AZERBAIJAN	55,00	1282,00	23,31	3,56	1,39	43%	4%	33%	77%
BANGLADESH	8,00	71,00	8,88	0,86	1,81	13%	13%	16%	92%
BARBADOS	4,00	21,00	5,25	0,99	1,44	14%	0%	52%	84%
BELGIUM	1058,50	14931,75	14,11	1,76	1,44	22%	6%	32%	87%
BELORUSSIA	87,00	1554,00	17,86	2,73	1,38	33%	6%	34%	80%
BENIN	14,00	89,00	6,36	0,87	1,32	10%	7%	36%	85%
BOLIVIA	8,00	165,00	20,63	2,41	1,85	38%	0%	32%	85%
BOSNIA & HERCEGOVINA	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,20	0,87	0%	0%	67%	67%
BOTSWANA	1,00	5,00	5,00	0,44	1,18	0%	0%	44%	82%
BRAZIL	358,00	4489,00	12,54	1,82	1,41	21%	8%	35%	88%
BULGARIA	57,00	552,00	9,68	1,63	1,10	20%	11%	30%	81%
BURKINA FASO	23,00	199,00	8,65	1,45	1,28	22%	9%	37%	83%
CAMBODIA	8,00	41,00	5,13	0,66	1,22	0%	13%	25%	83%
CAMEROON	16,00	205,00	12,81	1,67	1,18	21%	13%	29%	90%
CANADA	827,25	18681,75	22,58	2,63	1,57	31%	5%	31%	88%
CAPE VERDE	1,00	2,00	2,00	0,32	0,73	0%	0%	33%	41%
CENT AFR REPubL	1,00	12,00	12,00	1,20	1,36	0%	0%	48%	87%
CHILE	317,25	5911,50	18,63	2,11	1,32	24%	5%	39%	88%
COLOMBIA	96,00	1693,00	17,64	2,62	1,34	32%	6%	33%	84%
CONGO	5,00	68,00	13,60	1,31	1,39	13%	0%	24%	84%
COSTA RICA	11,00	101,00	9,18	1,20	1,07	14%	9%	55%	83%
CROATIA	121,25	2247,75	18,54	1,90	1,62	21%	7%	34%	89%
CUBA	9,00	868,00	96,44	9,04	1,39	22%	22%	4%	80%
CYPRUS	75,00	807,00	10,76	1,41	1,26	19%	8%	35%	85%
CZECH REPUBLIC	434,25	6016,50	13,85	1,75	1,48	20%	9%	31%	87%
DEM REPubL CONGO	3,00	70,00	23,33	2,06	0,96	34%	0%	31%	87%
DENMARK	920,00	16501,00	17,94	2,15	1,51	26%	6%	30%	87%
DOMINICAN REPUBLIC	2,00	29,00	14,50	2,58	1,08	50%	0%	12%	73%

PUBLIC

ECUADOR	5,00	75,00	15,00	3,23	1,88	66%	0%	35%	83%
EGYPT	37,00	495,00	13,38	1,48	1,71	18%	5%	27%	91%
ESTONIA	154,00	4445,00	28,86	2,91	1,56	36%	7%	30%	87%
ETHIOPIA	9,00	235,00	26,11	1,97	1,26	18%	0%	20%	87%
FIJI ISLANDS	1,00	6,00	6,00	0,55	1,37	0%	0%	57%	73%
FINLAND	821,00	14260,00	17,37	1,96	1,39	24%	8%	32%	89%
FR POLYNESIA	2,00	64,00	32,00	4,53	1,22	62%	0%	26%	74%
FRANCE	3934,25	60707,00	15,43	1,85	1,42	22%	7%	30%	89%
FRENCH GUYANA	4,00	114,00	28,50	3,50	1,33	25%	25%	18%	89%
GABON	6,00	84,00	14,00	1,61	1,23	17%	17%	22%	95%
GAMBIA	8,00	111,00	13,88	1,35	1,21	18%	50%	46%	87%
GERMANY	5282,25	84631,50	16,02	1,96	1,42	22%	6%	29%	89%
GHANA	25,00	364,00	14,56	1,66	1,25	16%	16%	27%	85%
GREAT BRITAIN	5450,00	93934,75	17,24	2,15	1,50	25%	6%	26%	88%
GREECE	735,00	11241,00	15,29	1,78	1,31	20%	9%	32%	87%
GREENLAND	13,00	97,00	7,46	1,52	1,33	17%	15%	41%	87%
GRENADA	1,00	3,00	3,00	0,79	1,54	0%	0%	0%	75%
GUADELOUPE	3,00	13,00	4,33	0,75	1,16	4%	0%	13%	84%
GUATEMALA	2,00	14,00	7,00	0,79	1,17	0%	0%	44%	87%
GUINEA	2,00	26,00	13,00	1,63	1,03	17%	0%	4%	65%
GUINEA BISSAU	15,00	64,00	4,27	0,70	1,00	13%	13%	54%	86%
GUYANA	1,00	14,00	14,00	7,14	4,16	100%	0%	33%	95%
HUNGARY	522,00	7376,00	14,13	1,87	1,39	23%	9%	30%	86%
ICELAND	84,00	3091,00	36,80	3,42	2,51	33%	2%	35%	87%
INDIA	279,00	4199,00	15,05	1,88	1,41	18%	9%	34%	87%
INDONESIA	23,00	233,00	10,13	1,32	1,39	15%	0%	35%	87%
IRAN	71,00	627,00	8,83	1,28	1,10	16%	7%	35%	89%
IRAQ	5,00	25,00	5,00	0,76	1,23	0%	0%	39%	90%
IRELAND	333,00	5660,00	17,00	2,04	1,46	24%	7%	31%	87%
ISRAEL	746,00	11634,00	15,60	1,94	1,55	24%	8%	26%	88%
ITALY	3708,25	53944,25	14,55	1,80	1,36	20%	7%	29%	88%
IVORY COAST	9,00	148,00	16,44	1,84	1,23	29%	11%	40%	87%
JAMAICA	3,00	496,00	165,33	16,92	10,22	67%	0%	40%	90%
JAPAN	672,00	11950,00	17,78	2,09	1,57	26%	6%	33%	88%
JORDAN	2,00	20,00	10,00	3,58	0,64	50%	0%	20%	70%
KAZACHSTAN	7,00	65,00	9,29	1,24	1,32	22%	29%	23%	86%
KENYA	38,00	330,00	8,68	1,46	1,21	18%	13%	33%	82%
KOSOVO	1,00	7,00	7,00	1,85	1,54	0%	0%	22%	91%
KUWAIT	1,00	84,00	84,00	5,06	1,61	100%	0%	21%	85%
KYRGYZSTAN	1,00	3,00	3,00	0,62	1,54	0%	0%	40%	70%

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LAOS	2,00	7,00	3,50	0,43	1,21	0%	0%	42%	78%
LATVIA	30,00	465,00	15,50	1,79	1,53	27%	7%	43%	83%
LEBANON	9,00	66,00	7,33	1,66	1,61	33%	0%	32%	86%
LIECHTENSTEIN	1,00	7,00	7,00	0,48	0,55	0%	0%	13%	96%
LITHUANIA	56,00	611,00	10,91	1,59	1,61	24%	5%	39%	85%
LUXEMBOURG	27,00	318,00	11,78	1,61	1,24	21%	0%	26%	89%
MACEDONIA	18,00	392,00	21,78	2,10	1,12	9%	17%	25%	77%
MADAGASCAR	2,00	31,00	15,50	1,32	1,07	6%	0%	18%	89%
MALAWI	7,00	50,00	7,14	0,94	1,19	9%	0%	19%	64%
MALAYSIA	43,00	522,00	12,14	2,01	1,41	29%	5%	41%	82%
MALI	6,00	103,00	17,17	1,78	2,12	31%	0%	38%	93%
MALTA	7,00	195,00	27,86	3,75	1,12	43%	14%	18%	68%
MARTINIQUE	1,00	10,00	10,00	0,82	0,95	0%	0%	29%	89%
MEXICO	172,25	2202,75	12,79	1,48	1,26	16%	9%	34%	86%
MOLDAVIA	7,00	46,00	6,57	1,07	1,24	7%	14%	32%	79%
MONACO	6,00	105,00	17,50	1,87	1,31	32%	0%	19%	88%
MONGOL PEO REP	3,00	20,00	6,67	2,30	1,64	58%	0%	29%	61%
MONTENEGRO	2,00	2,00	1,00	0,14	0,50	0%	0%	50%	74%
MOROCCO	81,00	1488,00	18,37	2,80	1,34	33%	7%	33%	79%
MOZAMBIQUE	11,00	110,00	10,00	1,78	1,40	32%	0%	19%	76%
NAMIBIA	5,00	25,00	5,00	0,93	1,27	10%	0%	52%	86%
NEPAL	16,00	258,00	16,13	1,83	1,49	20%	0%	38%	91%
NETH ANTILLES	3,00	45,00	15,00	2,02	1,63	47%	0%	27%	87%
NETHERLANDS	2219,75	37051,00	16,69	2,02	1,43	25%	5%	31%	89%
NEW CALEDONIA	2,00	65,00	32,50	5,11	1,60	99%	0%	25%	92%
NEW ZEALAND	84,00	1198,00	14,26	2,05	1,41	28%	7%	38%	88%
NICARAGUA	1,00	22,00	22,00	2,71	1,44	100%	0%	12%	90%
NIGERIA	13,50	494,25	36,61	2,50	2,19	8%	7%	40%	71%
NORWAY	547,00	10083,00	18,43	2,50	1,43	27%	5%	32%	84%
OMAN	10,00	99,00	9,90	1,55	1,31	28%	10%	30%	86%
PAKISTAN	16,00	959,00	59,94	5,52	3,29	29%	6%	38%	93%
PANAMA	12,00	210,00	17,50	2,67	1,43	26%	0%	30%	80%
PAPUA N GUINEA	5,00	27,00	5,40	1,27	1,16	26%	0%	49%	79%
PARAGUAY	1,00	28,00	28,00	2,89	1,82	100%	0%	42%	94%
PEOPLES R CHINA	802,50	11621,75	14,48	1,95	1,34	23%	9%	32%	88%
PERU	15,00	297,00	19,80	3,44	1,77	55%	0%	22%	83%
PHILIPPINES	11,00	749,00	68,09	7,06	3,72	55%	0%	40%	89%
POLAND	790,50	9623,00	12,17	1,54	1,26	16%	9%	36%	87%
PORTUGAL	889,25	11851,75	13,33	1,79	1,29	20%	9%	31%	86%
QATAR	25,00	382,00	15,28	1,94	1,72	29%	16%	34%	90%

PUBLIC

REP OF GEORGIA	84,00	1909,00	22,73	3,14	1,41	33%	7%	32%	81%
REUNION	9,00	90,00	10,00	1,63	1,24	22%	11%	26%	81%
ROMANIA	184,00	2515,00	13,67	2,08	1,19	28%	9%	34%	82%
RUSSIA	647,25	8864,00	13,69	1,81	1,41	21%	10%	35%	86%
RWANDA	5,00	26,00	5,20	1,03	1,10	1%	0%	41%	82%
SAUDI ARABIA	78,25	1275,50	16,30	2,37	1,76	29%	5%	31%	89%
SENEGAL	12,00	48,00	4,00	0,61	1,10	2%	0%	41%	86%
SERBIA	131,00	2282,00	17,42	2,39	1,18	26%	7%	30%	80%
SEYCHELLES	2,00	8,00	4,00	1,63	1,84	34%	0%	60%	82%
SIERRA LEONE	2,00	31,00	15,50	2,22	1,12	57%	0%	24%	88%
SINGAPORE	121,00	2973,00	24,57	2,77	2,07	31%	11%	28%	87%
SLOVAKIA	154,25	2324,00	15,07	2,17	1,48	26%	8%	33%	85%
SLOVENIA	256,00	3872,00	15,13	1,93	1,34	24%	6%	36%	84%
SOUTH AFRICA	271,25	4508,75	16,62	2,16	1,35	27%	8%	33%	84%
SOUTH KOREA	201,00	5924,00	29,47	3,22	1,62	25%	12%	29%	89%
SPAIN	3537,75	50188,50	14,19	1,77	1,38	20%	8%	29%	87%
SRI LANKA	3,00	32,00	10,67	1,32	1,41	33%	0%	48%	80%
SUDAN	4,00	66,00	16,50	1,65	1,37	25%	25%	20%	79%
SWEDEN	1364,50	20148,25	14,77	1,77	1,36	20%	7%	31%	87%
SWITZERLAND	1922,50	40683,00	21,16	2,50	1,46	28%	7%	25%	87%
SYRIA	5,00	28,00	5,60	1,06	1,45	22%	0%	40%	73%
TAIWAN	152,00	2548,00	16,76	2,27	1,29	29%	8%	35%	85%
TAJKISTAN	1,00	8,00	8,00	1,21	1,34	0%	0%	53%	66%
TANZANIA	36,00	371,00	10,31	1,42	1,23	15%	0%	27%	83%
THAILAND	42,00	720,00	17,14	1,88	1,73	21%	10%	29%	87%
TOGO	5,00	60,00	12,00	2,14	1,52	33%	0%	33%	83%
TRINIDAD & TOBAGO	4,00	51,00	12,75	1,26	1,32	25%	0%	42%	89%
TUNISIA	27,00	293,00	10,85	1,45	0,95	21%	7%	29%	85%
TURKEY	215,00	3027,00	14,08	2,00	1,21	24%	12%	29%	80%
U ARAB EMIRATES	9,25	37,25	4,03	0,96	1,40	14%	43%	49%	80%
UGANDA	28,00	204,00	7,29	1,11	1,07	16%	14%	35%	72%
UKRAINE	140,00	1150,00	8,21	1,04	1,01	12%	17%	33%	84%
URUGUAY	9,00	79,00	8,78	1,37	1,12	22%	22%	19%	91%
USA	4571,25	86536,50	18,93	2,25	1,58	27%	5%	28%	89%
UZBEKISTAN	8,00	73,00	9,13	1,39	1,00	25%	0%	30%	77%
VANUATU	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,28	0,88	0%	0%	67%	52%
VATICAN	3,00	20,00	6,67	0,91	1,14	33%	0%	47%	91%
VENEZUELA	13,00	260,00	20,00	2,15	1,51	38%	0%	28%	91%
VIETNAM	45,00	463,00	10,29	1,21	1,29	16%	18%	35%	83%
W IND ASSOC ST	1,00	5,00	5,00	0,83	1,18	0%	0%	0%	85%

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ZAMBIA	5,00	39,00	7,80	0,95	1,24	1%	0%	40%	88%
ZIMBABWE	2,00	30,00	15,00	2,14	1,16	52%	0%	23%	70%

14 Appendix 6: Output and impact of scientific cooperation types across access modes, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015/2016

			P	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
CLOSED	SI	2008 - 2011	4664,50	27598,25	5,92	1,61	1,42	18%	26%	23%	83%
	SI	2009 - 2012	8221,00	59405,75	7,23	1,62	1,42	18%	22%	23%	83%
	SI	2010 - 2013	12564,00	99883,25	7,95	1,63	1,43	18%	20%	23%	83%
	SI	2011 - 2014	13173,50	137116,00	10,41	1,73	1,43	19%	14%	22%	83%
	SI	2012 - 2015	10606,00	139745,75	13,18	1,70	1,43	19%	10%	21%	83%
CLOSED	NC	2008 - 2011	3258,25	20542,50	6,30	1,65	1,52	19%	21%	26%	87%
	NC	2009 - 2012	6021,25	46083,50	7,65	1,69	1,53	19%	17%	25%	87%
	NC	2010 - 2013	9488,75	82274,75	8,67	1,67	1,51	19%	16%	24%	86%
	NC	2011 - 2014	10041,75	111680,00	11,12	1,75	1,52	20%	11%	22%	86%
	NC	2012 - 2015	8231,75	116328,00	14,13	1,72	1,52	20%	8%	21%	86%
CLOSED	IC	2008 - 2011	9625,75	73302,50	7,62	2,00	1,72	22%	20%	29%	86%
	IC	2009 - 2012	17958,25	164711,25	9,17	1,99	1,69	22%	16%	28%	86%
	IC	2010 - 2013	28629,25	294329,75	10,28	2,00	1,68	22%	15%	28%	86%
	IC	2011 - 2014	30643,75	401318,75	13,10	2,11	1,68	24%	10%	27%	86%
	IC	2012 - 2015	25092,25	421383,75	16,79	2,09	1,68	24%	7%	25%	86%
OPEN	SI	2008 - 2011	803,75	5680,50	7,07	1,73	1,30	19%	22%	20%	85%
	SI	2009 - 2012	1549,00	12091,75	7,81	1,66	1,24	17%	23%	20%	86%
	SI	2010 - 2013	2510,75	19419,75	7,73	1,53	1,24	17%	20%	21%	86%
	SI	2011 - 2014	3351,75	28781,50	8,59	1,56	1,28	17%	16%	21%	87%
	SI	2012 - 2015	3311,75	37266,75	11,25	1,72	1,31	18%	11%	20%	87%
OPEN	NC	2008 - 2011	646,00	3882,50	6,01	1,39	1,26	16%	22%	26%	88%
	NC	2009 - 2012	1334,50	9299,00	6,97	1,49	1,30	17%	17%	25%	88%
	NC	2010 - 2013	2293,00	16836,50	7,34	1,48	1,28	17%	17%	25%	88%
	NC	2011 - 2014	3080,50	26259,00	8,52	1,56	1,30	16%	14%	24%	89%
	NC	2012 - 2015	3099,50	34088,50	11,00	1,67	1,32	18%	9%	22%	89%
OPEN	IC	2008 - 2011	2501,50	17083,50	6,83	1,70	1,42	20%	17%	30%	88%
	IC	2009 - 2012	4987,00	39447,75	7,91	1,72	1,38	20%	15%	30%	88%
	IC	2010 - 2013	8397,00	72507,00	8,63	1,74	1,36	20%	14%	30%	88%
	IC	2011 - 2014	11086,25	111149,00	10,03	1,77	1,40	20%	12%	29%	88%
	IC	2012 - 2015	10813,25	137396,75	12,71	1,85	1,43	22%	8%	28%	88%

14 Appendix 7a: Output and impact of institutions in the EU Member States Closed access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov
AUSTRIA	UNIV WIEN	635,50	15470,00	24,34	2,27	1,95	28%	4%	27%	89%
	TECH UNIV WIEN	367,00	4153,00	11,32	1,56	1,37	17%	12%	30%	70%
	LEOPOLD FRANZENS UNIV INNSBRUCK	299,00	10269,00	34,34	3,26	2,17	36%	3%	31%	88%
	KARL FRANZENS UNIV GRAZ	278,00	7172,00	25,80	2,22	1,86	25%	2%	28%	90%
	TECH UNIV GRAZ	169,00	3207,00	18,98	1,76	1,49	22%	2%	26%	82%
	UNIV BODENKULTUR WIEN	107,00	1863,00	17,41	2,37	1,38	31%	6%	36%	77%
	AUSTRIAN ACAD SCI	102,00	4813,00	47,19	4,06	3,84	46%	5%	13%	92%
	JOHANNES KEPLER UNIV LINZ	100,00	1274,00	12,74	1,74	1,71	22%	7%	26%	84%
	AUSTRIAN ACAD SCI-SPACE RES INST	59,00	735,00	12,46	1,13	1,06	8%	3%	42%	92%
	AIT AUSTRIAN INST TECHNOLOG GMBH	51,00	822,00	16,12	1,50	1,47	17%	0%	28%	87%
	PARACELSUS MED UNIV	22,00	360,00	16,36	1,42	2,10	22%	0%	27%	92%
BELGIUM	KATHOL UNIV LEUVEN	1398,25	27584,00	19,73	1,91	1,65	22%	6%	28%	85%
	UNIV GHENT	838,00	18142,00	21,65	2,03	1,65	25%	6%	24%	88%
	UNIV CATHOL LOUVAIN	503,00	11698,00	23,26	2,34	1,61	26%	6%	24%	87%
	UNIV ANTWERP	375,00	7281,00	19,42	2,08	2,01	25%	5%	28%	89%
	UNIV LIEGE	289,00	4512,00	15,61	1,64	1,59	23%	4%	38%	88%
	UNIV LIBRE BRUXELLES	246,00	6137,00	24,95	2,49	1,78	25%	3%	23%	84%
	INTERUNIV MICROELECT CTR	234,00	3661,00	15,65	1,59	1,31	20%	11%	22%	80%
	VRIJE UNIV BRUSSEL	163,00	3575,00	21,93	2,69	1,86	22%	8%	26%	84%
	FLANDERS INTERUNIV BIOTECHNOL INST	154,00	8938,00	58,04	4,41	2,96	47%	3%	20%	96%
	UNIV MONS	119,00	2981,00	25,05	1,99	1,97	21%	3%	21%	92%
	ROYAL OBSERVATORY	56,00	495,00	8,84	0,73	1,14	7%	5%	45%	82%

PUBLIC

	INST TROP MED	55,00	796,00	14,47	1,41	1,32	15%	0%	31%	90%
BULGARIA	BULGARIAN ACAD SCI	113,00	993,00	8,79	1,17	1,10	14%	12%	33%	79%
	SOFIA UNIV ST.KLIMENT OHRIDSKI	47,00	384,00	8,17	0,98	1,19	9%	2%	39%	86%
	MED UNIV SOFIA	7,00	1160,00	165,71	13,37	5,14	71%	0%	30%	96%
	PLOVDIV STATE UNIV	7,00	104,00	14,86	1,33	0,85	7%	0%	27%	93%
	VARNA UNIV MEDICINE	5,00	57,00	11,40	0,83	2,05	0%	0%	51%	69%
CYPRUS	UNIV CYPRUS	133,00	1504,00	11,31	1,56	1,40	17%	5%	24%	72%
	CYPRUS INST	23,00	306,00	13,30	1,49	1,27	24%	0%	31%	78%
	CYPRUS UNIV TECHNOL	20,00	127,00	6,35	1,02	1,48	8%	10%	26%	59%
	MAKARIOS HOSP	10,00	229,00	22,90	1,48	1,45	30%	0%	20%	92%
CZECH REPUBLIC	ACAD SCI CZECH REPUBLIC	521,00	9238,00	17,73	1,72	1,65	19%	7%	28%	90%
	CHARLES UNIV PRAGUE	331,00	6440,00	19,46	1,89	1,68	25%	6%	30%	87%
	MASARYK UNIV BRNO	139,00	1744,00	12,55	1,27	1,26	14%	8%	29%	87%
	INST CHEM TECHNOL PRAGUE	105,00	1018,00	9,70	1,29	1,09	12%	8%	30%	89%
	CZECH TECH UNIV PRAGUE	100,00	1177,00	11,77	1,93	1,38	16%	9%	29%	68%
	PALACKY UNIV OLOMOUC	65,00	1747,00	26,88	2,34	1,77	30%	0%	27%	91%
	UNIV SOUTH BOHEMIA	40,00	656,00	16,40	1,66	1,52	16%	5%	30%	89%
	BRNO UNIV TECHNOL	31,00	218,00	7,03	0,97	1,14	5%	16%	25%	74%
	INST CLIN & EXPT MED	16,00	289,00	18,06	1,16	1,17	6%	6%	33%	92%
	NATL INST PUBL HLTH	10,00	216,00	21,60	1,96	1,31	17%	0%	31%	86%
	INST EXPT BOT	7,00	253,00	36,14	2,31	2,98	38%	0%	44%	95%
DENMARK	UNIV COPENHAGEN	992,25	34886,25	35,16	2,97	2,09	30%	3%	26%	91%
	AARHUS UNIV	698,00	20811,00	29,82	2,60	2,00	26%	3%	29%	87%

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	TECH DENMARK UNIV	501,50	14474,00	28,86	2,73	1,76	24%	6%	21%	84%
	UNIV SOUTHERN DENMARK	214,00	6786,00	31,71	2,58	1,91	26%	7%	30%	89%
	AALBORG UNIV	147,00	2701,00	18,37	2,03	1,48	20%	9%	25%	76%
	STATE SERUM INST	70,00	1752,00	25,03	1,83	1,91	24%	4%	34%	94%
	DANISH CANC SOC	67,00	2223,00	33,18	2,68	1,78	39%	0%	33%	95%
	NOVO NORDISK AS	43,00	6751,00	157,00	9,95	3,63	41%	2%	17%	95%
	DANISH METEOROL INST	32,00	719,00	22,47	2,87	1,21	38%	6%	29%	81%
	GEOL SURVEY DENMARK GREENLAND	24,00	345,00	14,38	1,88	1,60	22%	0%	31%	84%
ESTONIA	UNIV TARTU	199,25	8685,25	43,59	3,15	2,34	38%	5%	31%	88%
	TALLINN TECH UNIV	45,00	841,00	18,69	1,93	1,08	17%	9%	25%	82%
	ESTONIAN UNIV LIFE SCI	37,00	804,00	21,73	2,47	1,29	38%	0%	29%	78%
	ESTONIAN BIOCTR	34,00	2306,00	67,82	3,49	3,87	44%	6%	32%	93%
	NICPB	27,00	693,00	25,67	2,65	1,48	41%	0%	19%	88%
	TALLINN UNIV	15,00	351,00	23,40	3,31	1,85	53%	0%	22%	78%
	TARTU ASTROPHYS OBSERV	14,00	328,00	23,43	1,92	1,21	37%	0%	31%	89%
	ESTONIAN ACAD SCI	13,00	227,00	17,46	1,33	1,30	8%	8%	37%	86%
FINLAND	UNIV HELSINKI	826,00	27633,00	33,45	2,68	1,97	27%	4%	29%	89%
	AALTO UNIV	392,00	5306,00	13,54	1,57	1,49	17%	10%	27%	82%
	UNIV OULU	279,00	11763,00	42,16	2,80	1,97	28%	6%	31%	87%
	UNIV TURKU	229,00	6576,00	28,72	2,14	1,86	30%	3%	34%	93%
	UNIV EASTERN FINLAND	177,00	6148,00	34,73	3,04	2,18	32%	2%	33%	92%
	VTT TECH RES CTR FINLAND	155,25	2802,50	18,05	1,70	1,32	22%	10%	21%	85%
	NATL INST HLTH & WELF	147,00	9470,00	64,42	3,96	3,06	47%	2%	33%	91%
	UNIV TAMPERE	114,25	6719,50	58,81	3,93	2,77	49%	2%	31%	95%
	FINNISH METEOROL INST	103,00	1504,00	14,60	1,65	1,54	14%	5%	43%	83%
	UNIV JYVASKYLA	103,00	1486,00	14,43	1,56	1,63	17%	6%	40%	89%
FRANCE	UNIV PARIS VI PIERRE & MARIE	1199,00	32251,00	26,90	2,59	1,94	30%	6%	26%	90%

PUBLIC

	CURIE										
	UNIV PARIS XI SUD	879,00	23857,00	27,14	2,62	1,87	27%	6%	28%	89%	
	CEA	863,00	20918,00	24,24	2,33	1,49	23%	7%	26%	88%	
	UNIV PARIS VII DENIS DIDEROT	808,00	18104,00	22,41	2,03	1,69	24%	4%	34%	90%	
	UNIV TOULOUSE	490,00	11722,00	23,92	2,51	1,81	27%	5%	31%	87%	
	UNIV STRASBOURG	447,00	12675,00	28,36	2,17	2,22	28%	2%	22%	92%	
	UNIV GRENOBLE I JOSEPH FOURIER	446,00	11705,00	26,24	2,44	1,93	27%	3%	28%	90%	
	UNIV LYON I CLAUDE BERNARD	440,00	9997,00	22,72	2,06	1,87	27%	4%	28%	90%	
	INRA	427,50	15448,75	36,14	3,49	2,18	35%	6%	19%	89%	
	UNIV MONTPELLIER SUD DE FRANCE	379,00	9838,00	25,96	2,35	1,91	29%	4%	29%	89%	
	AIX MARSEILLE UNIV	374,00	8675,00	23,20	2,70	1,92	29%	4%	27%	90%	
	INST PASTEUR	311,00	13646,00	43,88	2,88	2,45	32%	3%	22%	97%	
GERMANY	UNIV MUNICH	721,00	23923,00	33,18	2,79	2,18	33%	3%	28%	90%	
	TECH UNIV MUNICH	692,00	20452,00	29,55	2,78	2,20	32%	5%	29%	86%	
	UNIV HEIDELBERG	562,00	15383,00	27,37	2,50	1,95	30%	5%	31%	91%	
	UNIV BONN	432,25	13490,25	31,21	2,76	1,99	32%	3%	27%	90%	
	UNIV ERLANGEN NURNBERG	423,00	10296,00	24,34	2,15	2,08	26%	3%	30%	88%	
	UNIV FREIBURG	396,00	10325,00	26,07	2,49	1,96	30%	5%	24%	88%	
	TECH UNIV DRESDEN	380,00	9857,00	25,94	2,49	2,22	30%	4%	28%	86%	
	HELMHOLTZ ASSOCRES CTR JULICH	373,00	9071,00	24,32	2,66	1,75	24%	9%	28%	88%	
	UNIV TUBINGEN	317,00	7464,00	23,55	2,03	1,86	24%	3%	31%	90%	
	UNIV MAINZ	307,00	6868,00	22,37	2,14	2,02	25%	5%	33%	90%	
	UNIV WURZBURG	304,00	11702,00	38,49	3,25	1,85	30%	4%	22%	89%	
	UNIV GOTTINGEN	300,00	7000,00	23,33	2,39	1,82	29%	7%	31%	87%	
	UNIV HAMBURG	294,00	6656,00	22,64	2,26	1,87	28%	4%	31%	86%	
	EUROP STHN OBSERV	254,00	3709,00	14,60	1,34	1,14	14%	5%	48%	91%	
	MAX PLANCK SOC- MAX PLANCK INST EXTRATERR PHYS	246,00	5759,00	23,41	2,11	1,28	24%	3%	43%	92%	
GREAT BRITAIN	UNIV CAMBRIDGE	1575,00	50092,00	31,80	2,72	2,21	32%	4%	25%	90%	
	UNIV OXFORD	1548,00	60616,50	39,16	3,74	2,32	35%	4%	22%	88%	
	IMPERIAL COLL LONDON	1255,00	38712,00	30,85	2,79	2,14	30%	5%	25%	86%	

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	UNIV COLL LONDON	1126,25	29906,00	26,55	2,47	1,98	30%	4%	28%	88%
	UNIV SOUTHAMPTON	677,00	14587,00	21,55	2,23	1,80	26%	4%	30%	85%
	UNIV EDINBURGH	672,25	22147,00	32,94	3,19	2,19	34%	4%	29%	84%
	KINGS COLL UNIV LONDON	621,50	25101,75	40,39	3,33	2,24	35%	2%	26%	88%
	UNIV MANCHESTER INST SCI & TECHNOL	571,25	13801,50	24,16	2,35	1,76	27%	6%	30%	87%
	UNIV BRISTOL	420,00	12241,00	29,15	2,75	2,30	36%	4%	31%	86%
	UNIV WARWICK	397,25	9507,25	23,93	2,22	1,79	22%	5%	32%	88%
	UNIV SHEFFIELD	365,00	8470,00	23,21	2,27	1,70	26%	3%	31%	87%
	UNIV LIVERPOOL	308,00	6474,00	21,02	2,27	1,84	22%	5%	27%	87%
GREECE	UNIV CRETE	432,00	6481,00	15,00	1,50	1,42	17%	7%	31%	89%
	NATL & KAPODISTRIAN UNIV ATHENS	340,00	6303,00	18,54	1,82	1,51	22%	8%	31%	83%
	NATL TECH UNIV	326,00	3506,00	10,75	1,62	1,10	17%	10%	29%	70%
	ARISTOTLE UNIV THESSALONIKI	287,00	3301,00	11,50	1,49	1,18	18%	9%	31%	77%
	UNIV PATRAS	252,00	3615,00	14,35	1,35	1,40	15%	8%	23%	87%
	NCSR DEMOKRITOS	246,00	3741,00	15,21	1,51	1,29	16%	7%	29%	88%
	UNIV IOANNINA	172,25	2808,25	16,30	1,51	1,53	18%	8%	30%	87%
	FORTH	172,00	2214,00	12,87	1,18	1,36	12%	5%	25%	88%
	UNIV THESSALY	84,00	921,00	10,96	1,33	1,36	12%	7%	34%	73%
	ACAD ATHENS	81,00	1465,00	18,09	1,63	1,49	21%	1%	30%	93%
	UNIV AEGEAN	40,00	629,00	15,73	2,35	1,13	30%	10%	33%	66%
HUNGARY	HUNGARIAN ACAD SCI	426,00	4755,00	11,16	1,13	1,16	12%	11%	32%	89%
	EOTVOS LORAND UNIV BUDAPEST	219,00	4073,00	18,60	2,03	1,37	20%	5%	23%	87%
	BUDAPEST UNIV TECHNOL & ECON	174,00	1981,00	11,39	1,37	1,25	15%	11%	24%	84%
	UNIV SZEGED	139,00	2193,00	15,78	1,38	1,32	18%	7%	25%	89%
	SEMMELWEIS UNIV BUDAPEST	72,25	2005,50	27,76	2,17	1,44	26%	1%	26%	95%
	UNIV DEBRECEN	62,25	859,50	13,81	1,40	1,25	17%	3%	27%	91%
	HAS INST NUCL RES ATOMKI	41,00	330,00	8,05	1,04	1,19	11%	12%	44%	86%
	SZENT ISTVAN UNIV	39,00	271,00	6,95	1,25	0,90	12%	3%	37%	89%
	UNIV PECS	37,00	408,00	11,03	1,14	1,33	14%	8%	30%	90%
	WIGNER RES CTR	35,00	532,00	15,20	2,11	1,36	21%	17%	32%	86%

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	PHYS										
	ELTE GOTTHARD LENDULET RES GRP	10,00	168,00	16,80	1,75	1,10	30%	0%	30%	87%	
IRELAND	UNIV DUBLIN TRINITY COLL	289,00	9752,00	33,74	2,98	2,14	30%	7%	23%	89%	
	UNIV COLL CORK, NATL UNIV IRELAND	254,00	4031,00	15,87	1,56	1,67	17%	6%	28%	89%	
	UNIV COLL DUBLIN, NATL UNIV IRELAND	247,00	8265,00	33,46	3,01	1,93	33%	4%	24%	88%	
	NATL UNIV IRELAND GALWAY	125,00	2070,00	16,56	1,74	1,37	19%	7%	34%	84%	
	DUBLIN CITY UNIV	78,00	1316,00	16,87	2,21	1,70	26%	13%	23%	86%	
	TYNDALL NATL INST	53,00	509,00	9,60	1,28	1,35	10%	8%	34%	91%	
	UNIV LIMERICK	53,00	557,00	10,51	1,51	1,66	19%	6%	29%	82%	
	ROYAL COLL SURGEONS IRELAND	41,00	992,00	24,20	2,02	1,88	34%	2%	30%	92%	
	NATL UNIV IRELAND MAYNOOTH	33,00	426,00	12,91	1,57	1,40	24%	0%	33%	85%	
	DUBLIN INST ADV STUD	30,00	478,00	15,93	1,62	1,13	17%	0%	39%	88%	
	BEAUMONT HOSP	24,00	1105,00	46,04	4,52	2,67	67%	0%	24%	95%	
ITALY	UNIV ROMA SAPIENZA	837,00	13731,00	16,41	1,76	1,54	20%	6%	33%	84%	
	INFN NATL INST NUCL PHYS	807,00	13300,00	16,48	1,92	1,21	21%	9%	34%	86%	
	UNIV BOLOGNA	737,00	11188,00	15,18	1,70	1,37	20%	7%	32%	81%	
	UNIV PADOVA	704,25	15733,00	22,34	2,10	1,66	25%	4%	29%	85%	
	UNIV MILANO	620,25	20897,75	33,69	2,99	1,91	27%	4%	24%	91%	
	POLITECNICO MILANO	529,00	7511,00	14,20	1,98	1,69	21%	7%	26%	71%	
	UNIV NAPOLI FEDERICO II	472,00	9238,00	19,57	1,77	1,50	22%	6%	25%	87%	
	UNIV FIRENZE	450,25	10588,50	23,52	2,22	1,73	25%	6%	28%	88%	
	UNIV ROMA TOR VERGATA	423,00	7214,00	17,05	2,05	1,39	17%	8%	32%	86%	
	UNIV PISA	399,00	5453,00	13,67	1,75	1,29	19%	11%	33%	80%	
	UNIV PAVIA	271,00	5136,00	18,95	2,37	1,59	30%	4%	32%	84%	
	INT SCH ADV STUD	224,00	4023,00	17,96	2,27	1,64	27%	6%	27%	89%	
LATVIA	UNIV LATVIA	49,00	437,00	8,92	1,07	0,98	17%	10%	39%	84%	

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	RIGA TECH UNIV	13,00	62,00	4,77	0,75	0,99	2%	8%	42%	87%
	LATVIAN BIOMED RES & STUDY CTR	7,00	240,00	34,29	2,92	1,81	43%	14%	46%	96%
LITHUANIA	VILNIUS UNIV	107,00	735,00	6,87	0,78	1,00	5%	8%	46%	89%
	CTR PHYS SCI & TECHNOL	27,00	207,00	7,67	0,93	0,99	7%	11%	37%	90%
	KAUNAS UNIV TECHNOL	19,00	184,00	9,68	0,98	1,19	10%	16%	35%	93%
	KLAIPEDA UNIV	12,00	231,00	19,25	2,75	1,27	26%	0%	34%	66%
	VYTAUTAS MAGNUS UNIV KAUNAS	10,00	240,00	24,00	2,75	1,31	45%	0%	63%	82%
	NAT RES CTR	7,00	38,00	5,43	0,96	0,72	14%	14%	31%	74%
	VILNIUS UNIV HOSP SANTARISKIU CLIN	6,00	158,00	26,33	2,14	1,29	33%	0%	46%	96%
LUXEMBOURG	UNIV LUXEMBOURG	60,00	1033,00	17,22	2,34	1,65	34%	7%	26%	75%
	HOP KIRCHBERG	8,00	101,00	12,63	1,11	1,31	13%	0%	39%	93%
	LUXEMBOURG PUBL RES CTR HLTH CRP SANTE	6,00	55,00	9,17	0,78	0,87	0%	0%	44%	93%
MALTA	UNIV MALTA	10,00	237,00	23,70	1,81	2,23	22%	0%	23%	77%
NETHERLANDS	UNIV UTRECHT	945,25	28113,50	29,74	2,75	2,18	35%	2%	26%	91%
	LEIDEN UNIV	856,25	22591,50	26,38	2,14	1,76	28%	1%	32%	92%
	RADBOUD UNIV NIJMEGEN	798,25	22064,50	27,64	2,31	2,05	28%	4%	26%	90%
	UNIV AMSTERDAM	792,25	18188,50	22,96	2,03	1,74	24%	4%	31%	87%
	UNIV GRONINGEN	642,00	17994,00	28,03	2,26	2,15	29%	3%	30%	92%
	FREE UNIV AMSTERDAM	622,00	19903,00	32,00	2,79	2,05	31%	3%	29%	89%
	ERASMUS UNIV	557,50	24749,75	44,39	3,41	2,35	37%	1%	25%	92%
	WAGENINGEN UR	548,25	11401,25	20,80	2,62	1,75	31%	2%	25%	83%
	DELFT UNIV TECHNOL	447,00	8241,00	18,44	2,17	1,79	28%	6%	23%	74%
	EINDHOVEN UNIV TECHNOL	439,00	7503,00	17,09	1,86	1,72	20%	7%	24%	83%
	UNIV MAASTRICHT	258,25	6150,00	23,81	2,04	1,69	27%	4%	27%	90%

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POLAND	POLISH ACAD SCI	438,00	5218,00	11,91	1,48	1,28	13%	8%	35%	88%
	JAGIELLONIAN UNIV KRAKOW	287,25	4307,25	14,99	1,62	1,25	15%	7%	33%	87%
	WARSAW UNIV	282,00	3737,00	13,25	1,52	1,36	16%	5%	38%	87%
	AGH UNIV SCI & TECHNOL KRAKOW	129,00	1162,00	9,01	1,41	1,03	14%	18%	33%	74%
	ADAM MICKIEWICZ UNIV POZNAN	79,00	551,00	6,97	0,90	1,06	4%	8%	44%	87%
	WARSAW UNIV TECHNOL	78,00	515,00	6,60	1,01	1,09	11%	15%	37%	81%
	UNIV WROCLAW	56,00	487,00	8,70	0,98	1,07	16%	9%	56%	85%
	MED UNIV WARSAW	49,00	1178,00	24,04	2,00	1,56	27%	2%	40%	93%
	WROCLAW UNIV TECHNOL	48,00	320,00	6,67	0,78	1,08	8%	15%	42%	89%
	NATL CTR NUCL RES	43,00	612,00	14,23	1,82	1,22	26%	7%	39%	86%
	NICHOLAS COPERNICUS UNIV TORUN	41,00	535,00	13,05	1,45	1,53	16%	5%	33%	86%
	UNIV GDANSK	38,00	362,00	9,53	1,32	1,30	20%	18%	29%	86%
	INT INST MOL & CELL BIOL	24,00	439,00	18,29	1,24	1,60	13%	0%	15%	97%
PORTUGAL	UNIV PORTO	390,25	5642,25	14,46	1,57	1,40	20%	6%	35%	87%
	UNIV TECNICA LISBOA	345,00	3937,00	11,41	1,30	1,24	16%	12%	32%	79%
	UNIV LISBOA	234,00	4603,00	19,67	2,13	1,66	23%	10%	30%	86%
	UNIV NOVA LISBOA	203,00	3874,00	19,08	2,03	1,44	20%	7%	22%	87%
	UNIV AVEIRO	182,00	2700,00	14,84	1,87	1,38	20%	8%	29%	85%
	UNIV COIMBRA	177,00	2247,00	12,69	1,52	1,24	15%	7%	33%	85%
	UNIV DO MINHO BRAGA	157,00	2047,00	13,04	1,45	1,43	14%	8%	33%	91%
	UNIV ALGARVE	54,00	409,00	7,57	1,23	1,17	11%	6%	38%	82%
	GULBENKIAN INST SCI	45,00	1035,00	23,00	1,74	2,12	29%	2%	20%	95%
	ICVS 3BS PT GOVT ASSOCIATE LAB	37,00	335,00	9,05	0,99	1,96	7%	5%	42%	94%
	LAB INSTRUMENTACAO & FIS EXPT PARTICULAS LIP	7,00	156,00	22,29	2,94	1,32	43%	0%	29%	77%
ROMANIA	PETRU PONI INST MACROMOL CHEM	68,00	268,00	3,94	0,54	0,89	3%	21%	39%	90%
	ROMANIAN ACAD	47,00	319,00	6,79	0,95	1,14	11%	9%	49%	83%
	NATL INST PHYS &	44,00	746,00	16,95	2,32	1,06	23%	16%	38%	82%

	NUCL ENGN										
	UNIV POLYTECN BUCAREST	41,00	518,00	12,63	2,09	1,03	23%	7%	32%	74%	
	UNIV BUCHAREST	36,00	267,00	7,42	0,91	0,98	12%	14%	39%	81%	
	UNIV WEST TIMISOARA	30,00	706,00	23,53	3,50	1,23	42%	3%	24%	65%	
	BABES BOLYAI UNIV CLUJ NAPOCA	23,00	435,00	18,91	2,32	1,77	30%	0%	25%	84%	
	ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA UNIV IASI	22,00	148,00	6,73	0,97	0,99	12%	18%	30%	81%	
	INST ISOTOPE & MOL TECHNOL	17,00	343,00	20,18	2,61	1,26	27%	6%	29%	90%	
	POLITEHNICA UNIV TIMISOARA	15,00	71,00	4,73	1,17	1,07	17%	13%	41%	67%	
SLOVAKIA	SLOVAK ACAD SCI	181,00	1909,00	10,55	1,17	1,13	11%	7%	34%	85%	
	COMENIUS UNIV BRATISLAVA	85,00	1291,00	15,19	1,75	1,31	15%	6%	31%	88%	
	PAVOL JOSEF SAFARIK UNIV KOSICE	15,00	73,00	4,87	0,59	1,17	7%	13%	28%	90%	
	SLOVAK MED UNIV BRATISLAVA	15,00	198,00	13,20	1,43	1,39	18%	7%	31%	90%	
	SLOVAK UNIV TECHNOL BRATISLAVA	14,00	83,00	5,93	0,78	0,83	7%	21%	37%	92%	
SLOVENIA	UNIV LJUBLJANA	253,00	4440,00	17,55	1,70	1,51	20%	8%	31%	85%	
	JOZEF STEFAN INST	169,00	2408,00	14,25	1,59	1,64	18%	9%	28%	82%	
	UNIV MARIBOR	57,00	477,00	8,37	0,95	1,28	7%	12%	39%	86%	
	NATL INST CHEM	48,00	638,00	13,29	1,22	1,33	14%	8%	24%	91%	
	EN FIST CTR EXCELLENCE	31,00	249,00	8,03	0,69	1,21	0%	6%	35%	91%	
	UNIV NOVA GORICA	31,00	390,00	12,58	1,38	1,95	20%	16%	25%	91%	
	CTR EXCELLENCE SPACE SI	27,00	441,00	16,33	1,66	1,15	19%	4%	46%	89%	
	NATL INST BIOL	7,00	45,00	6,43	1,40	1,31	14%	0%	34%	75%	
	CTR EXCELLENCE INTEGRATED APPROACHES CHEM & BIOL	6,00	46,00	7,67	1,18	1,12	17%	0%	35%	74%	
	SLOVENIAN NMR CTR	6,00	54,00	9,00	0,67	0,84	0%	17%	29%	94%	
	SLOVENIAN HEART FDN	3,00	41,00	13,67	2,04	1,77	52%	0%	40%	88%	

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SPAIN	UNIV BARCELONA	740,50	14354,25	19,38	1,84	1,71	24%	4%	26%	89%
	UNIV AUTONOMA MADRID	574,00	11397,00	19,86	1,97	1,59	24%	5%	29%	90%
	UNIV AUTONOMA BARCELONA	524,25	13158,25	25,10	2,29	1,81	25%	6%	23%	85%
	UNIV VALENCIA	460,00	7587,00	16,49	1,88	1,45	17%	8%	29%	88%
	UNIV COMPLUTENSE MADRID	450,00	6928,00	15,40	1,63	1,54	21%	7%	30%	86%
	ICREA	365,25	11896,25	32,57	2,97	2,42	38%	2%	22%	91%
	UNIV POLITECN CATALUNYA	356,00	2821,00	7,92	1,39	1,26	17%	17%	29%	65%
	UNIV POLITECN VALENCIA	282,00	3163,00	11,22	1,23	1,31	15%	13%	26%	74%
	UNIV POMPEU FABRA BARCELONA	279,00	8117,00	29,09	2,66	2,39	28%	5%	18%	87%
	UNIV ZARAGOZA	279,00	4999,00	17,92	1,86	1,69	25%	8%	28%	80%
	UNIV GRANADA	260,00	4383,00	16,86	1,82	1,48	22%	6%	29%	86%
	INST ASTROFIS CANARIAS	127,00	1507,00	11,87	1,20	1,16	16%	1%	53%	89%
SWEDEN	KAROLINSKA INST STOCKHOLM	695,75	25105,25	36,08	2,87	2,24	32%	2%	27%	94%
	UPPSALA UNIV	658,50	18512,50	28,11	2,48	1,98	25%	6%	27%	90%
	LUNDS UNIV	640,00	17078,00	26,68	2,24	1,80	25%	4%	30%	90%
	STOCKHOLM UNIV	499,25	11316,00	22,67	2,32	1,63	20%	3%	31%	88%
	KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOGSKOLAN	498,25	8634,00	17,33	2,04	1,46	20%	8%	27%	78%
	GOTEBORG UNIV	388,00	11424,00	29,44	2,36	1,83	30%	2%	28%	91%
	CHALMERS	335,00	4512,00	13,47	1,44	1,47	18%	7%	30%	83%
	SWED UNIV AGR SCI UPPSALA	201,00	4593,00	22,85	2,59	1,79	30%	0%	27%	86%
	LINKOPING UNIV	200,25	3676,50	18,36	2,00	1,87	21%	4%	27%	85%
	UMEA UNIV	199,00	5263,00	26,45	2,24	1,65	29%	4%	28%	91%
	OSKAR KLEIN CTR	11,00	369,00	33,55	4,58	1,26	48%	0%	31%	77%

14 Appendix 7b: Output and impact of institutions in the EU Member States Open Access mode, in FP-7 funded projects, 2008-2015/2016

		p	tcs	mcs	mncs	mnjs	pp_top_perc	pp_uncited	prop_self_cits	int_cov	
AUSTRIA	UNIV WIEN	326,25	4045,50	12,40	1,78	1,60	23%	6%	30%	89%	
	LEOPOLD FRANZENS UNIV INNSBRUCK	185,25	3837,75	20,72	2,80	1,90	34%	4%	30%	86%	
	KARL FRANZENS UNIV GRAZ	105,00	1872,00	17,83	2,11	1,61	26%	4%	30%	89%	
	TECH UNIV WIEN	98,00	1272,00	12,98	1,91	1,92	27%	9%	32%	85%	
	TECH UNIV GRAZ	62,00	879,00	14,18	1,52	1,30	22%	15%	20%	79%	
	AUSTRIAN ACAD SCI	54,00	2073,00	38,39	4,05	2,55	35%	9%	9%	89%	
	JOHANNES KEPLER UNIV LINZ	31,00	200,00	6,45	0,97	1,27	10%	23%	38%	87%	
	AUSTRIAN ACAD SCI- SPACE RES INST	24,00	236,00	9,83	0,98	0,89	13%	4%	41%	92%	
	PARACELSUS MED UNIV	24,00	154,00	6,42	0,65	0,77	5%	13%	46%	96%	
	UNIV BODENKULTUR WIEN	24,00	283,00	11,79	1,54	1,28	19%	8%	37%	86%	
	AIT AUSTRIAN INST TECHNOL GMBH	11,00	179,00	16,27	1,72	1,05	20%	9%	22%	84%	
BELGIUM	KATHOL UNIV LEUVEN	381,25	4818,00	12,64	1,58	1,44	16%	5%	36%	88%	
	UNIV GHENT	174,00	2689,00	15,45	1,88	1,44	29%	7%	30%	88%	
	UNIV ANTWERP	107,25	1417,75	13,22	1,90	1,54	22%	7%	33%	90%	
	UNIV CATHOL LOUVAIN	104,25	1703,00	16,34	1,92	1,55	24%	4%	31%	88%	
	UNIV LIBRE BRUXELLES	98,00	1909,00	19,48	2,12	1,59	29%	7%	24%	86%	
	UNIV LIEGE	79,00	948,00	12,00	1,50	1,30	24%	6%	42%	88%	
	VRIJE UNIV BRUSSEL	56,00	680,00	12,14	1,96	1,34	26%	13%	28%	86%	
	FLANDERS INTERUNIV INST BIOTECHNOL	51,00	1167,00	22,88	2,27	1,74	32%	4%	16%	94%	
	INST TROP MED	44,00	422,00	9,59	1,29	1,25	18%	7%	36%	84%	
	ROYAL OBSERVATORY	33,00	183,00	5,55	0,57	0,96	0%	3%	50%	86%	
	UNIV MONS	18,00	140,00	7,78	0,95	1,18	9%	6%	28%	87%	
	INTERUNIV MICROELECT CTR	10,00	100,00	10,00	1,92	2,12	23%	0%	18%	92%	

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BULGARIA	BULGARIAN ACAD SCI		26,00	252,00	9,69	1,32	1,28	20%	8%	27%	85%
	SOFIA ST.KLIMENT OHRIDSKI UNIV		9,00	49,00	5,44	0,62	0,94	11%	11%	49%	87%
	MED UNIV SOFIA		1,00	20,00	20,00	6,23	1,31	100%	0%	31%	94%
	PLOVDIV UNIV	STATE	1,00	39,00	39,00	4,04	0,46	100%	0%	3%	95%
	VARNA MEDICINE UNIV		1,00	15,00	15,00	2,67	1,08	100%	0%	32%	79%
CYPRUS	CYPRUS INST		34,00	428,00	12,59	1,57	1,34	26%	3%	30%	84%
	UNIV CYPRUS		32,00	184,00	5,75	0,72	1,15	3%	13%	37%	89%
	CYPRUS TECHNOL UNIV		4,00	12,00	3,00	0,49	1,27	0%	0%	40%	78%
	MAKARIOS HOSP		3,00	11,00	3,67	0,56	0,68	0%	0%	31%	94%
CZECH REPUBLIC	ACAD SCI CZECH REPUBLIC		206,00	3256,00	15,81	1,98	1,53	24%	8%	33%	86%
	CHARLES PRAGUE UNIV		171,25	2522,50	14,73	2,01	1,53	23%	9%	32%	82%
	PALACKY OLOMOUC UNIV		98,00	2042,00	20,84	2,73	1,58	35%	6%	32%	81%
	MASARYK BRNO UNIV		75,00	962,00	12,83	1,59	1,55	14%	4%	24%	91%
	CZECH TECH PRAGUE UNIV		72,00	1515,00	21,04	3,13	1,42	36%	4%	33%	79%
	UNIV BOHEMIA SOUTH		20,00	142,00	7,10	1,06	1,30	6%	5%	35%	89%
	INST TECHNOL PRAGUE CHEM		14,00	154,00	11,00	1,88	1,22	28%	21%	23%	90%
	NATL INST HLTH PUBL		7,00	101,00	14,43	2,00	1,28	43%	0%	32%	81%
	BRNO TECHNOL UNIV		4,00	29,00	7,25	0,69	0,76	8%	25%	12%	78%
	INST EXPT BOT		3,00	15,00	5,00	0,59	1,24	0%	0%	50%	92%
DENMARK	UNIV COPENHAGEN		489,00	9023,00	18,45	2,15	1,46	26%	6%	31%	88%
	AARHUS UNIV		254,00	3805,00	14,98	1,90	1,49	27%	8%	36%	88%
	TECH DENMARK UNIV		121,00	3148,00	26,02	3,12	1,97	32%	6%	21%	85%
	UNIV SOUTHERN DENMARK		73,00	1067,00	14,62	1,66	1,47	30%	4%	36%	91%
	STATE SERUM INST		23,00	551,00	23,96	2,25	1,58	24%	9%	32%	90%

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	AALBORG UNIV	20,00	277,00	13,85	2,02	1,21	31%	10%	33%	84%
	DANISH CANC SOC	15,00	296,00	19,73	3,28	2,48	53%	0%	28%	92%
	DANISH METEOROL INST	13,00	232,00	17,85	1,97	1,49	31%	0%	38%	77%
	NOVO NORDISK AS	10,00	373,00	37,30	3,66	1,72	51%	0%	16%	94%
	GEOL SURVEY DENMARK GREENLAND	8,00	143,00	17,88	1,78	1,40	25%	0%	24%	82%
ESTONIA	UNIV TARTU	94,00	2898,00	30,83	2,98	1,77	37%	6%	34%	87%
	NICPB	29,00	1163,00	40,10	4,13	1,35	47%	0%	12%	91%
	ESTONIAN BIOCTR	15,00	206,00	13,73	1,17	1,16	20%	7%	33%	93%
	TALLINN TECH UNIV	14,00	705,00	50,36	4,35	1,72	24%	29%	32%	87%
	TARTU ASTROPHYS OBSERV	13,00	293,00	22,54	1,98	1,09	35%	0%	19%	89%
	ESTONIAN ACAD SCI	10,00	72,00	7,20	1,23	1,22	13%	0%	31%	86%
	ESTONIAN UNIV LIFE SCI	8,00	91,00	11,38	1,68	1,57	27%	0%	30%	87%
	TALLINN UNIV	5,00	64,00	12,80	2,24	1,23	27%	0%	36%	81%
FINLAND	UNIV HELSINKI	388,00	7554,00	19,47	1,92	1,45	23%	6%	34%	89%
	AALTO UNIV	174,00	2896,00	16,64	2,44	1,58	28%	8%	28%	87%
	UNIV TURKU	100,00	2277,00	22,77	2,32	1,73	29%	9%	38%	92%
	UNIV OULU	89,00	3081,00	34,62	3,03	1,93	30%	8%	35%	92%
	NATL INST HLTH & WELF	80,00	2712,00	33,90	3,23	1,93	37%	1%	32%	91%
	FINNISH METEOROL INST	79,00	901,00	11,41	1,24	1,09	13%	6%	52%	85%
	UNIV EASTERN FINLAND	56,00	1569,00	28,02	2,86	1,84	31%	5%	40%	89%
	UNIV TAMPERE	48,00	1402,00	29,21	2,69	2,08	32%	6%	37%	92%
	UNIV JYVASKYLA	40,00	841,00	21,03	2,46	1,36	24%	3%	34%	91%
	VTT TECH RES CTR FINLAND	34,00	875,00	25,74	2,23	1,28	26%	6%	15%	93%
FRANCE	UNIV PARIS VI PIERRE & MARIE CURIE	548,00	10402,00	18,98	2,29	1,42	26%	7%	30%	88%
	UNIV PARIS VII DENIS DIDEROT	392,00	6032,00	15,39	1,80	1,35	21%	5%	36%	87%
	CEA	377,00	5728,00	15,19	2,02	1,37	25%	5%	33%	88%
	UNIV PARIS XI SUD	337,25	5513,50	16,35	2,04	1,42	24%	9%	34%	88%

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	AIX MARSEILLE UNIV	245,25	3902,00	15,91	2,30	1,46	31%	7%	33%	88%
	INST PASTEUR	178,00	3760,00	21,12	2,09	1,60	29%	2%	24%	95%
	UNIV TOULOUSE	162,00	3102,00	19,15	2,43	1,56	25%	5%	32%	90%
	UNIV GRENOBLE I JOSEPH FOURIER	161,00	2970,00	18,45	2,11	1,60	25%	4%	35%	87%
	INRA	159,25	2306,75	14,49	1,91	1,48	22%	4%	26%	90%
	UNIV LYON I CLAUDE BERNARD	148,00	3264,00	22,05	2,42	1,36	29%	5%	23%	91%
	UNIV STRASBOURG	116,00	2267,00	19,54	2,93	1,58	29%	6%	27%	93%
	UNIV MONTPELLIER SUD DE FRANCE	113,00	2640,00	23,36	2,29	1,49	24%	4%	23%	91%
GERMANY	UNIV HEIDELBERG	363,00	5599,00	15,42	1,93	1,32	26%	5%	36%	89%
	UNIV MUNICH	332,25	7389,50	22,24	2,38	1,58	29%	5%	30%	89%
	UNIV BONN	310,25	5239,25	16,89	2,07	1,47	24%	6%	32%	89%
	TECH UNIV MUNICH	253,00	5558,00	21,97	2,35	1,55	25%	5%	29%	89%
	UNIV WURZBURG	192,00	3200,00	16,67	2,27	1,39	29%	2%	32%	86%
	UNIV FREIBURG	189,00	3446,00	18,23	2,43	1,45	29%	4%	31%	86%
	MAX PLANCK SOC- MAX PLANCK INST EXTRATERR PHYS	187,00	3094,00	16,55	1,65	1,19	20%	4%	40%	91%
	UNIV HAMBURG	186,00	2924,00	15,72	2,14	1,38	28%	6%	34%	85%
	UNIV GOTTINGEN	169,50	2845,25	16,79	2,35	1,41	32%	8%	34%	85%
	EUROP STHN OBSERV	169,00	2115,00	12,51	1,27	1,12	13%	7%	44%	90%
	UNIV TUBINGEN	168,25	1886,25	11,21	1,28	1,15	16%	5%	36%	90%
	HELMHOLTZ ASSOCRES CTR JULICH	168,00	3001,00	17,86	1,93	1,48	24%	8%	37%	90%
	UNIV MAINZ	157,00	2603,00	16,58	2,28	1,50	25%	4%	36%	84%
	TECH UNIV DRESDEN	155,00	3183,00	20,54	2,72	1,57	31%	5%	32%	84%
	UNIV ERLANGEN NURNBERG	116,00	1587,00	13,68	1,69	1,71	25%	3%	35%	89%
GREAT BRITAIN	UNIV CAMBRIDGE	804,25	16405,50	20,40	2,32	1,64	29%	4%	28%	90%
	UNIV OXFORD	731,00	14586,00	19,95	2,41	1,64	31%	6%	27%	89%
	UNIV COLL LONDON	492,25	9585,50	19,47	2,32	1,61	27%	4%	31%	87%
	IMPERIAL COLL LONDON	447,25	8387,50	18,75	2,15	1,70	26%	6%	28%	90%
	UNIV EDINBURGH	380,25	9667,50	25,42	2,85	1,69	31%	4%	28%	87%
	KINGS COLL UNIV LONDON	289,00	7197,00	24,90	2,66	1,78	31%	7%	27%	87%
	UNIV	265,00	5734,00	21,64	2,35	1,46	24%	5%	28%	86%

	SOUTHAMPTON									
	UNIV MANCHESTER INST SCI & TECHNOL	258,00	4936,00	19,13	2,29	1,46	26%	5%	32%	85%
	UNIV LIVERPOOL	201,00	2865,00	14,25	2,27	1,40	26%	6%	31%	84%
	UNIV SHEFFIELD	200,25	3216,75	16,06	2,24	1,41	29%	6%	32%	86%
	UNIV BRISTOL	184,00	5844,00	31,76	3,35	1,99	37%	2%	30%	90%
	UNIV WARWICK	178,00	2995,00	16,83	2,32	1,37	23%	8%	31%	84%
GREECE	UNIV CRETE	223,00	3711,00	16,64	1,53	1,27	16%	7%	29%	90%
	NATL & KAPODISTRIAN UNIV ATHENS	152,00	2349,00	15,45	2,20	1,31	25%	7%	33%	83%
	ARISTOTLE UNIV THESSALONIKI	118,00	2093,00	17,74	2,51	1,29	32%	9%	31%	81%
	NATL TECH UNIV	105,00	1655,00	15,76	2,36	1,30	30%	10%	33%	81%
	FORTH	71,00	681,00	9,59	0,93	1,18	10%	10%	30%	90%
	UNIV IOANNINA	55,00	1470,00	26,73	2,67	1,77	25%	4%	34%	90%
	UNIV PATRAS	53,00	559,00	10,55	1,54	1,19	19%	4%	29%	87%
	NCSR DEMOKRITOS	46,00	528,00	11,48	1,50	1,26	20%	11%	34%	88%
	UNIV AEGEAN	41,00	1037,00	25,29	4,00	1,37	42%	5%	36%	79%
	ACAD ATHENS	38,00	552,00	14,53	1,61	1,35	21%	8%	34%	91%
	UNIV THESSALY	13,00	346,00	26,62	2,61	1,50	31%	23%	31%	86%
HUNGARY	HUNGARIAN ACAD SCI	156,00	2175,00	13,94	1,57	1,28	20%	6%	26%	89%
	EOTVOS LORAND UNIV BUDAPEST	103,00	1259,00	12,22	1,56	1,44	18%	12%	29%	84%
	BUDAPEST UNIV TECHNOL & ECON	69,00	850,00	12,32	1,96	1,43	24%	9%	22%	83%
	WIGNER RES CTR PHYS	55,00	1251,00	22,75	3,49	1,45	39%	7%	33%	79%
	UNIV SZEGED	44,00	537,00	12,20	1,02	1,39	9%	11%	25%	91%
	SEMMELWEIS UNIV BUDAPEST	38,00	285,00	7,50	0,88	1,19	6%	8%	33%	94%
	UNIV DEBRECEN	38,00	540,00	14,21	2,20	1,11	29%	3%	26%	91%
	HAS INST NUCL RES ATOMKI	28,00	157,00	5,61	0,77	1,24	7%	11%	55%	92%
	UNIV PECS	17,00	314,00	18,47	1,74	1,47	27%	18%	37%	90%
	ELTE GOTHARD LENDELET RES GRP	13,00	179,00	13,77	1,47	1,14	23%	0%	30%	85%
	SZENT ISTVAN UNIV	13,00	99,00	7,62	1,48	1,08	23%	8%	28%	91%

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IRELAND	UNIV COLL DUBLIN, NATL UNIV IRELAND	82,00	1652,00	20,15	2,51	1,73	25%	5%	28%	86%
	UNIV DUBLIN TRINITY COLL	71,00	1624,00	22,87	2,49	1,69	27%	11%	23%	91%
	UNIV COLL CORK, NATL UNIV IRELAND	68,00	1051,00	15,46	1,73	1,17	25%	1%	34%	92%
	NATL UNIV IRELAND GALWAY	37,00	392,00	10,59	1,42	1,22	15%	8%	50%	88%
	DUBLIN INST ADV STUD	21,00	185,00	8,81	0,83	1,13	5%	0%	48%	90%
	DUBLIN CITY UNIV	16,00	209,00	13,06	2,15	1,14	24%	6%	16%	86%
	TYNDALL NATL INST	12,00	181,00	15,08	2,15	0,98	35%	0%	28%	86%
	UNIV LIMERICK	11,00	106,00	9,64	1,66	2,72	26%	9%	32%	80%
	BEAUMONT HOSP	8,00	228,00	28,50	3,10	1,65	29%	13%	14%	86%
	NATL UNIV IRELAND MAYNOOTH	8,00	98,00	12,25	1,45	1,16	18%	13%	26%	79%
	ROYAL COLL SURGEONS IRELAND	8,00	137,00	17,13	2,09	1,09	41%	0%	22%	93%
ITALY	INFN NATL INST NUCL PHYS	591,00	9786,00	16,56	2,10	1,27	24%	8%	29%	88%
	UNIV ROMA SAPIENZA	424,00	6564,00	15,48	1,98	1,44	22%	5%	29%	87%
	UNIV BOLOGNA	279,00	4097,00	14,68	1,90	1,25	23%	6%	33%	88%
	UNIV MILANO	265,00	5366,00	20,25	2,79	1,41	27%	7%	28%	88%
	UNIV ROMA TOR VERGATA	218,00	3696,00	16,95	2,63	1,35	22%	10%	29%	84%
	UNIV PADOVA	211,25	3887,50	18,40	1,98	1,42	21%	5%	26%	89%
	UNIV NAPOLI FEDERICO II	191,00	3195,00	16,73	2,04	1,41	23%	5%	30%	87%
	INT SCH ADV STUD	184,00	2869,00	15,59	2,27	1,34	27%	5%	28%	89%
	UNIV PISA	178,00	3757,00	21,11	2,98	1,46	33%	5%	28%	82%
	UNIV PAVIA	147,00	1953,00	13,29	2,01	1,25	24%	7%	36%	85%
	UNIV FIRENZE	117,25	1724,50	14,71	1,86	1,67	25%	6%	32%	87%
	POLITECNICO MILANO	68,00	1147,00	16,87	2,28	2,24	22%	4%	28%	85%
LATVIA	UNIV LATVIA	13,00	123,00	9,46	1,04	1,32	19%	8%	41%	73%
	LATVIAN BIOMED RES & STUDY CTR	4,00	74,00	18,50	2,36	3,41	50%	0%	54%	96%
	RIGA TECH UNIV	3,00	13,00	4,33	0,58	0,50	0%	0%	19%	90%

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LITHUANIA	VILNIUS UNIV	31,00	209,00	6,74	0,87	1,48	6%	3%	43%	93%
	KLAIPEDA UNIV	9,00	140,00	15,56	3,09	1,42	48%	11%	30%	68%
	VYTAUTAS MAGNUS UNIV KAUNAS	4,00	50,00	12,50	2,37	1,87	50%	0%	36%	86%
	CTR PHYS SCI & TECHNOL	3,00	4,00	1,33	0,31	0,86	0%	33%	69%	96%
	NAT RES CTR	2,00	4,00	2,00	0,17	0,77	0%	50%	67%	75%
	VILNIUS UNIV HOSP SANTARISKIU CLIN	2,00	48,00	24,00	3,48	4,39	100%	0%	61%	93%
	KAUNAS UNIV TECHNOL	1,00	49,00	49,00	4,92	2,38	100%	0%	26%	100%
LUXEMBOURG	UNIV LUXEMBOURG	17,00	233,00	13,71	1,59	1,20	19%	0%	25%	88%
	HOP KIRCHBERG	1,00	16,00	16,00	1,90	1,26	50%	0%	24%	97%
	LUXEMBOURG PUBL RES CTR HLTH CRP SANTE	1,00	8,00	8,00	1,21	1,15	0%	0%	33%	100%
MALTA	UNIV MALTA	3,00	82,00	27,33	3,77	1,13	33%	0%	6%	42%
NETHERLANDS	LEIDEN UNIV	450,00	8186,00	18,19	1,97	1,32	28%	6%	33%	92%
	UNIV AMSTERDAM	337,00	5239,00	15,55	1,90	1,42	22%	4%	35%	87%
	UNIV UTRECHT	298,00	6745,00	22,63	2,70	1,71	33%	3%	27%	90%
	UNIV GRONINGEN	290,00	5363,00	18,49	1,97	1,52	23%	3%	37%	91%
	RADBOUD UNIV NIJMEGEN	288,00	4802,00	16,67	2,01	1,48	24%	6%	31%	88%
	FREE UNIV AMSTERDAM	220,00	4460,00	20,27	2,40	1,48	26%	6%	31%	88%
	ERASMUS UNIV	219,50	5742,50	26,16	2,49	1,78	30%	4%	30%	92%
	WAGENINGEN UR	148,00	2422,00	16,36	2,07	1,50	26%	5%	30%	85%
	UNIV MAASTRICHT	94,25	1207,50	12,81	1,64	1,42	20%	10%	33%	89%
	DELFT UNIV TECHNOL	63,00	1155,00	18,33	3,13	1,74	28%	6%	22%	85%
	EINDHOVEN UNIV TECHNOL	38,00	236,00	6,21	1,04	1,25	12%	8%	36%	86%
POLAND	POLISH ACAD SCI	274,25	3266,00	11,91	1,66	1,24	16%	8%	37%	87%
	JAGIELLONIAN UNIV KRAKOW	166,00	2198,00	13,24	1,90	1,24	21%	4%	36%	85%
	WARSAW UNIV	148,00	1628,00	11,00	1,39	1,29	13%	8%	38%	91%
	AGH UNIV SCI &	84,00	1454,00	17,31	2,70	1,21	31%	8%	34%	78%

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	TECHNOL KRAKOW									
	ADAM MICKIEWICZ UNIV POZNAN	43,00	521,00	12,12	1,18	1,48	6%	7%	26%	89%
	INT INST MOL & CELL BIOL	33,00	548,00	16,61	1,48	1,33	8%	0%	14%	96%
	UNIV GDANSK	26,00	112,00	4,31	1,23	1,50	6%	12%	36%	91%
	NICHOLAS COPERNICUS UNIV TORUN	23,00	126,00	5,48	0,76	1,13	1%	9%	50%	90%
	NATL CTR NUCL RES	21,00	393,00	18,71	2,56	1,39	37%	5%	34%	90%
	UNIV WROCLAW	19,00	152,00	8,00	0,82	1,15	13%	5%	59%	89%
	MED UNIV WARSAW	18,50	263,00	14,22	1,76	1,51	27%	3%	39%	94%
	WROCLAW UNIV TECHNOL	13,00	133,00	10,23	1,07	1,74	8%	0%	34%	90%
	WARSAW UNIV TECHNOL	10,00	47,00	4,70	0,81	1,16	9%	20%	48%	75%
PORTUGAL	UNIV LISBOA	234,00	3462,00	14,79	2,08	1,34	25%	9%	32%	85%
	UNIV PORTO	148,00	1715,00	11,59	1,32	1,18	17%	8%	39%	89%
	UNIV TECNICA LISBOA	137,25	1935,75	14,10	1,50	1,29	21%	7%	30%	85%
	UNIV NOVA LISBOA	136,00	2328,00	17,12	2,68	1,31	30%	5%	31%	86%
	UNIV DO MINHO BRAGA	134,00	1866,00	13,93	2,11	1,31	24%	10%	32%	83%
	UNIV COIMBRA	111,00	1734,00	15,62	2,28	1,28	27%	7%	33%	83%
	UNIV AVEIRO	97,00	984,00	10,14	1,61	1,16	19%	14%	36%	82%
	GULBENKIAN INST SCI	50,00	441,00	8,82	1,19	1,60	18%	2%	25%	91%
	UNIV ALGARVE	30,00	380,00	12,67	1,92	1,09	20%	3%	27%	86%
	LAB INSTRUMENTACAO & FIS EXPT PARTICULAS LIP	29,00	719,00	24,79	3,54	1,45	43%	3%	31%	77%
	ICVS 3BS PT GOVT ASSOCIATE LAB	19,00	133,00	7,00	1,13	1,40	13%	5%	28%	92%
ROMANIA	NATL INST PHYS & NUCL ENGN	69,00	1458,00	21,13	3,16	1,36	39%	6%	34%	79%
	UNIV POLYTECN BUCAREST	68,00	1314,00	19,32	3,04	1,32	36%	9%	34%	77%
	UNIV WEST TIMISOARA	62,00	1449,00	23,37	3,62	1,39	47%	3%	31%	77%
	INST ISOTOPE & MOL TECHNOL	38,00	927,00	24,39	4,07	1,40	44%	5%	34%	78%
	ROMANIAN ACAD	18,00	91,00	5,06	0,79	0,95	13%	11%	37%	85%

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	BABES BOLYAI UNIV CLUJ NAPOCA	9,00	133,00	14,78	2,41	1,00	25%	0%	19%	83%
	UNIV BUCHAREST	9,00	25,00	2,78	0,38	0,99	0%	11%	62%	84%
	PETRU PONI INST MACROMOL CHEM	5,00	11,00	2,20	0,16	0,47	0%	40%	21%	85%
	ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA UNIV IASI	4,00	7,00	1,75	1,57	0,85	25%	25%	59%	67%
	POLITEHNICA UNIV TIMISOARA	4,00	5,00	1,25	0,11	0,88	0%	25%	64%	83%
SLOVAKIA	SLOVAK ACAD SCI	104,25	1740,00	16,69	2,45	1,41	30%	8%	32%	85%
	COMENIUS UNIV BRATISLAVA	88,00	1659,00	18,85	2,75	1,49	33%	9%	31%	81%
	PAVOL JOSEF SAFARIK UNIV KOSICE	9,00	43,00	4,78	0,54	1,02	0%	22%	45%	94%
	SLOVAK MED UNIV BRATISLAVA	8,00	144,00	18,00	2,15	2,44	38%	0%	45%	87%
	SLOVAK UNIV TECHNOL BRATISLAVA	3,00	11,00	3,67	0,49	1,68	0%	0%	45%	89%
SLOVENIA	UNIV LJUBLJANA	167,00	2703,00	16,19	2,01	1,34	25%	4%	36%	84%
	JOZEF STEFAN INST	112,00	1797,00	16,04	2,29	1,38	28%	7%	34%	81%
	UNIV NOVA GORICA	24,00	298,00	12,42	1,76	1,39	19%	17%	37%	84%
	CTR EXCELLENCE SPACE SI	22,00	350,00	15,91	1,51	1,16	23%	0%	50%	90%
	EN FIST CTR EXCELLENCE	16,00	116,00	7,25	0,69	1,71	0%	0%	41%	92%
	NATL INST CHEM	16,00	118,00	7,38	0,62	1,18	0%	13%	36%	93%
	UNIV MARIBOR	12,00	208,00	17,33	2,57	1,19	38%	17%	22%	84%
	SLOVENIAN HEART FDN	5,00	90,00	18,00	2,06	1,31	20%	0%	57%	89%
	CTR EXCELLENCE INTEGRATED APPROACHES CHEM & BIOL	4,00	17,00	4,25	0,62	1,08	0%	0%	37%	81%
	NATL INST BIOL	3,00	13,00	4,33	0,46	0,92	0%	0%	38%	85%
	SLOVENIAN NMR CTR	3,00	22,00	7,33	0,82	1,50	0%	0%	33%	95%
SPAIN	UNIV VALENCIA	337,00	4990,00	14,81	1,79	1,22	22%	7%	30%	88%
	UNIV AUTONOMA MADRID	319,00	5858,00	18,36	2,24	1,42	27%	8%	31%	87%

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	UNIV BARCELONA	297,50	4247,25	14,28	1,78	1,52	22%	5%	29%	87%
	UNIV AUTONOMA BARCELONA	260,25	4568,25	17,55	2,22	1,49	27%	4%	26%	86%
	UNIV COMPLUTENSE MADRID	186,00	2048,00	11,01	1,42	1,44	18%	9%	33%	85%
	ICREA	176,25	3308,25	18,77	2,32	1,73	28%	5%	27%	86%
	UNIV GRANADA	159,00	2099,00	13,20	1,91	1,27	21%	14%	35%	84%
	UNIV POMPEU FABRA BARCELONA	148,00	1683,00	11,37	1,50	1,65	19%	7%	22%	88%
	UNIV ZARAGOZA	124,00	2007,00	16,19	2,64	1,62	26%	12%	30%	86%
	INST ASTROFIS CANARIAS	109,00	1055,00	9,68	1,09	1,16	12%	4%	48%	90%
	UNIV POLITECN CATALUNYA	63,00	462,00	7,33	1,04	1,15	12%	17%	35%	67%
	UNIV POLITECN VALENCIA	63,00	632,00	10,03	1,92	1,38	14%	24%	24%	74%
SWEDEN	STOCKHOLM UNIV	324,25	4696,50	14,48	1,91	1,26	19%	7%	36%	87%
	KAROLINSKA INST STOCKHOLM	282,25	5676,50	20,11	2,05	1,59	24%	7%	29%	91%
	LUNDS UNIV	268,00	5781,00	21,57	2,34	1,51	26%	5%	34%	87%
	UPPSALA UNIV	267,00	6398,00	23,96	2,57	1,62	28%	4%	32%	88%
	KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOGSKOLAN	188,00	2649,00	14,09	2,14	1,34	24%	11%	31%	83%
	GOTEBORG UNIV	141,00	2534,00	17,97	1,96	1,49	25%	6%	36%	89%
	CHALMERS	100,00	925,00	9,25	1,36	1,35	15%	8%	42%	86%
	UMEA UNIV	69,25	1263,75	18,25	1,86	1,53	22%	10%	34%	87%
	SWED UNIV AGR SCI UPPSALA	60,00	794,00	13,23	2,01	1,38	22%	10%	30%	86%
	OSKAR KLEIN CTR	56,00	1290,00	23,04	3,51	1,39	42%	4%	33%	77%
	LINKOPING UNIV	38,00	527,00	13,87	2,17	1,41	20%	13%	27%	82%